

A QUANTITATIVE ANALYSIS OF RESILIENCE TRAINING'S INFLUENCE ON
ARMY NATIONAL GUARDSMEN RESILIENCE AND PERFORMANCE

by

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has been approved

May 2021

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Abstract

Soldiers in the Army National Guard experience elevated perceptions of stress and demonstrate higher rates of failure on the Army Physical Fitness Test (APFT) and Army Body Composition Program (ABCP) screening when compared to their Active Duty counterparts. This study examined quantitative data regarding perception of resilience, application of resilience, and performance for National Guard soldiers that attended a two-week resilience intervention. This study built upon a framework of resilience theory as viewed through the lens of Adult Learning Theory to introduce resilience skills to National Guard soldiers. The study examined the performance data and self-reported perception and application data of 87 soldiers that attended the fiscal year 2019 Wellness Camp intervention from the research methodology and design lens of a quantitative, quasi-experimental, ex post facto study. This study analyzed pretest and posttest data from APFT performance, ABCP screening results, perception of resilience, and application of resilience skills (goal setting, emotion control, imagery, and energy activation) to fitness endeavors using a two-way ANOVA to either accept or reject the hypotheses of each research question. This study's results indicated that a statistically significant relationship was found between the intervention, pre-, and post-intervention results for all seven research questions: perception of resilience 1.76 ($SD=4.95$), $F(1,86)=10.99$, $p<0.001$; APFT performance 38.14 ($SD=28.19$), $F(1,86)=159.27$, $p<0.001$; ABCP performance -2.46 ($SD=2.20$), $F(1,86)=108.92$, $p<0.001$; application of goal setting 0.72 ($SD=0.91$), $F(1,86)=54.54$, $p<0.001$; application of emotion control 0.28 ($SD=0.51$), $F(1,86)=27.15$, $p<0.001$; application of imagery 0.65 ($SD=0.68$), $F(1,86)=80.25$, $p<0.001$; and application of emotion control 0.53 ($SD=0.68$), $F(1,86)=52.77$, $p<0.001$. The outcomes of this study hold potential in making recommended changes to Army doctrine on resilience training frequency.

Acknowledgements

This dissertation has become a reality thanks to the kind support and assistance of so many individuals. Foremost in mind, I want to thank the Lord for providing the strength and wisdom necessary to complete this herculean pursuit despite various setbacks and seemingly insurmountable odds. I would like to also acknowledge my earthly rock and inspiration, my beautiful and supporting wife, Melissa. Were it not for her, I would not be the man and researcher that I am today. I could never truly find the words to accurately capture the role she played in both support and motivation, so I will begin with simply stating my thanks for her.

I would also say that I am indebted to the amazing faculty and instructors of the University of Saint Augustine for Health Sciences, for their guidance and mentorship in the process. While there are far too many to name, I would start by highlighting Dr. Jordan Utley who mentored me in my Master's program and guided me to the EdD at USA, and both Dr. Shannon Groff and Dr. Lori Kupczynski for always keeping me headed the right direction and understanding the challenges that I faced in my pursuit as my dissertation chair/committee. I could not thank the three of you more for getting me to the finish line.

I would also like to express special gratitude to my loving and supporting father (William Howard), who raised me to be a man that never gives up and always commits to quality of work. I would also like to acknowledge the role that various educators played in sparking my passion to teach. Dr Jason Craddock and Dr Kelley Henderson inspired me to reach for the stars in academia, one day I hope to be there!

Finally, I would acknowledge the role my military career has played. I have had the honor of knowing many great military leaders, their tutelage and mentorship have formed me to be a leader. I could not be more thankful for leaders like CW3 Jose Hernandez who led me in

combat and mentored me to become a Warrant Officer; 1SG Robert Eads who helped me understand the power of resilience. The friendship and hasty mentorship you have each provided has paid dividends in my life. For every leader who remains unmentioned that guided me along my path, my thanks and appreciation go out to ALL of those who have helped me along my way. While their names could help fill an additional hundred pages easily, know that I am thankful but sadly limited on pages.

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Chapter 1: Introduction

The average failure rates for the Army Physical Fitness Test (APFT) were 11.7 percent and for the Army Body Composition Program (ABCP) screening was 4.4 percent across the total force of the Army National Guard's 54 states and territories from 2019-2020 (Headquarters, Florida Army National Guard [HQFLARNG], 2020). Russell, Kazman, and Russell (2019) explained that soldiers of the Army National Guard are more likely to fail their APFT or to fail to meet ABCP screening requirements compared to their Active Duty counterparts. In contrast the Army Active Duty failure rate was only three percent on the APFT (Meyer, 2018; Sih, & Negus, 2016). Only 3,633 soldiers across the entire 481,318 Active Duty component soldiers were reported as failing body composition (Bernstein et al., 2017; Defense Manpower Data Center [DMDC], 2019a), totaling 0.75 percent of the Army Active Duty force. Unlike other military branches, where reserve components comprise approximately 20 percent of the total force, the reserve components of the Army comprise approximately half of the total force (Russell et al., 2019). The notable lack of compliance with the Army's requirements for both fitness and body composition lends itself to form a concern for the operational and personnel readiness of the Army.

In accordance with Army Doctrine, if a soldier fails to meet the body composition and/or fitness requirements they are administratively flagged against favorable actions; which may include promotions, assignment to leadership roles, attendance of military education courses, and the use of education benefits for civilian schools (Headquarters, Department of the Army [HQDA], 2016; HQDA, 2017b). The administrative flag can be grounds for having a re-enlistment bar placed on their profile and can potentially lead to separation from service (HQDA, 2016; HQDA, 2017b). A soldier that cannot attend Army education courses cannot become

military occupation specialty (MOS) qualified for their duty position within a deployable unit (HQDA, 2016; HQDA, 2017a). A soldier that has an administrative flag placed on their profile cannot attend requisite leadership development courses required for promotion to the next rank (HQDA, 2016; HQDA, 2017a; HQDA, 2019b). The administrative flag prevents promotion and limits the available number of leaders in a rank range potentially leading to overburdening the available leader population (Pendleton, 2019). Separating a soldier from service also taxes the remaining force by lowering the available personnel for deployment (HQDA, 2014b; Pendleton, 2019).

Genger (2018) suggested that the two-fold increase in APFT failures in the Army National Guard from 6.7 percent in 2010 to 13.2 percent in 2018 coincided with the change in focus of the National Guard from a strategic reserve to that of an operational ready reserve. This focal change of the use of the National Guard resulted in increased deployment rates of soldiers to various warzones over multiple protracted war efforts in support of Operation Enduring Freedom in Afghanistan, Operations Iraqi Freedom, New Dawn, and Inherent Resolve in Iraq and other countries as part of the Global War on Terror (GWOT) (Philipps & Berkowitz, 2019). Increased exposure to war is challenging to the resilience and coping process of Service Members (Bullman et al., 2018; Martin et al., 2009).

Soldiers that experienced increased psychological stress with poor coping skills have been noted to have decreased physical performance and increased negative behaviors surrounding healthy choices in fitness and nutrition (Nindle et al., 2018). Researchers have suggested that resilience training's effect on training initiation behaviors and motivation through enhanced self-efficacy could support behavioral changes in nutrition and fitness training (Cacioppo et al., 2015; Nindle et al., 2013; Nindle et al., 2018) and those changes could

significantly decrease the elevated administrative flags affecting the operational readiness of the National Guard. These data suggested that increased exposure to resilience training could potentially increase positive behaviors, motivation, and compliance surrounding healthy activities which could in turn assist in decreasing the administrative flags for fitness testing and body composition screening being seen in the Army National Guard.

Background of the Study

The construct of resilience has seen major conversions in its defining concepts since its inception in the 1970s as a trait-based end-state. The modern definition of resilience identified a process of adaptation surrounding one's ability to positively adapt to stress and thrive during times of adversity (Dray et al., 2017; Lines et al., 2019; Luthar et al., 2000; Harms et al., 2013; Reivich et al., 2011; Tusaie & Dyer, 2004; Van Breda, 2018). By defining resilience as a process, researchers have established that resilience is not simply a fixed internal state but rather something that can be learned and adapted. The modern view of resilience argued that anyone can learn and develop improved levels of resilience (Dray et al., 2017; Lines et al., 2019; Van Breda, 2018).

Toland and Carrigan (2011) suggested that two aspects must be met to categorize a response as one of resilience: exposure to adversity and a dynamic process of positive adaptation. These criteria were in-line with the modern process-based definition of resilience in that a person must demonstrate the ability to recover from the initial stressor and thrive under a displacing adversity despite their personal traits and character strengths. While foundational views of resilience suggested that a particular set of traits would allow one to thrive in stress, modern resilience theory suggested a focus on the process of improvement of one's ability to

cope with various levels of stressors despite their personal traits (Bandura, 1982; Dray et al., 2017; Garmezy et al., 1984; Lines et al., 2019; Luthar, 2006; Van Breda, 2018).

Lower levels of perceived resilience have been suggested to increase perception of stress and have been associated with actions and behaviors that negatively affect health and fitness (Lester et al., 2011; Nindle et al., 2018). Service members experience elevated perceptions of stress in comparison to populations with similar experiences, such as Department of the Army civilians and military spouses (Thomas et al., 2018). Nassif et al. (2018) posited a link between service member combat exposure and elevated rates of both mental and physical health problems. The Army National Guard has seen an increase in operational implementation within the combat efforts across the GWOT since 2008 to the point that as of 2016 approximately half of the force had combat experience related to on-going operations in over 70 countries with the standing ability to deploy within 72 hours of an identified need (Genger, 2018; Grass, 2016).

What both Genger (2018) and Grass (2016) found began to paint the picture of increased exposure to combat stress for National Guard soldiers, which had been linked to physical fitness concerns. It has been noted that National Guard soldiers struggle more post-deployment than their Active Duty peers with stress-coping and depression (Arbisi et al., 2012; Kline et al., 2014; Russell et al., 2019). Further, soldiers that reported clinical markers for depression were more likely to fail the Army standards for fitness and/or body composition (Arbisi et al., 2012; Kline et al., 2014; Russell et al., 2019). Researchers have suggested that the increased perception of stress in the National Guard is associated with decreased levels of social support when compared to their Active Duty counterparts (Arbisi et al., 2012; Hofscher et al., 2017; Kline et al., 2014; Morgan et al., 2018; Wang et al., 2018). Additionally, there are negative physiological responses associated with distress that can affect a soldiers' physical performance capacity (Black et al.,

2017; Cacioppo et al., 2015; Dickerson & Kemeny, 2004; Sokolova, 2013). While psychological stress has been linked to negative physiological changes that affect performance, it has recently been suggested that there are also affects on self-efficacy and motivation that supported compliance with performance training (Black et al., 2017; Cacioppo et al., 2015). The National Guard demonstrated a much higher percentage of soldiers failing to meet the Army's fitness standards at 8.7 percent more than Active Duty and an increased failure to meet compliance with the Army's Body Composition Program by 3.65 percent (Bernstein et al., 2017; DMDC, 2019a; HQFLARNG, 2020; Meyer, 2018; Sih & Negus, 2016). Cassidy (2015) suggested that self-efficacy as a sub-component to resilience can help to mediate the negative effects associated with limited social support. Examining the issue through the lens of these data, the casual relationship between resilience, stress adaptation, self-efficacy, and fitness in service members was exposed.

In response to the increased stressors experienced by soldiers and the noted increase in behavioral health concerns, the United States Army created the Comprehensive Soldier Fitness (CSF) Program to develop a process to give soldiers coping skills well in advance of when they will need them (Casey, 2011; Crabtree-Nelson & DeYoung, 2017; Kent et al., 2015; Reivich et al., 2011; Zamorski et al., 2018). The CSF combined efforts with the University of Pennsylvania's Applied Positive Psychology program to develop the Army's Master Resilience Training (MRT) curriculum and certification course for soldiers (Reivich et al., 2011). One of the four major reports that spanned the MRT program addressed perception of resilience and self-efficacy on positive professional outcomes. This report retrospectively examined the high-performing Active Duty Army officers' population's (n=213) positive outcomes with special attention to promotion selection *below the zone*, which meant that the soldiers were selected for promotion ahead of their peer group. This study demonstrated that the study population had more

elevated rates of resilience than that of the average population of Active Duty Army officers (Lester et al., 2011). Physical performance on the APFT and body composition measured by the ABCP and the soldier's appearance in their Department of the Army (DA) photo were areas of emphasis for which the Army evaluates soldiers for promotion. Lester et al. (2011) noted that soldiers selected for promotion before their peers demonstrated increased perceptions of resilience. These compiled data suggested that soldiers with increased levels of resilience perception were less likely to fail to meet Army standards for physical fitness and body composition (Black et al., 2017; Cacioppo et al., 2015; Cassidy, 2015; Lester et al., 2011).

When viewing the sheer volume of National Guard soldiers that have administrative flags for lack of compliance to the Army's health related requirements for fitness and body composition through the lens of resilience a potential underlying issue presented. Army doctrine had set minimum standards for frequency of MRT training for both the Active Duty and National Guard components of the Army. HQDA (2014a; 2017a) required soldiers of the Active Duty to receive 12 of the MRT curriculum skills at a rate of one skill a month, and soldiers of the National Guard to receive 12 of the MRT curriculum skills at a rate of one skill every other month. This can be interpreted to state that Army Doctrine dictates that National Guard soldiers receive less frequent resilience training than their Active Duty counterparts.

Many of the fitness and body composition concerns can be traced to the significant differences in the National Guard and the Active Duty portions of the Army. The Active Duty Army consists of the traditional full time Soldier, while the National Guard as a reserve component of the Army only musters one-weekend-a-month and two-weeks-a-year for an annual training (Feickert & Kapp, 2014). Active Duty Army soldiers conduct physical training together a minimum of three times per week and any soldier failing to meet either the Army's physical

fitness or body composition standards can be enrolled into additional physical training sessions; as well as into other wellness and nutritional programs to support return to Army standards (HQDA, 2012b; HQDA, 2019c). Unlike the Active Duty Army, an Army National Guard soldier is only in uniform and under command authority in a duty status during the two-day monthly muster (Feickert & Kapp, 2014), leaving the soldier to their own choices, devices, will power, and self-efficacy for the remainder of the month. These data further suggested that in order to mitigate the increased administrative flags associated with failure of the Army's APFT and ABCP in the National Guard population, a resilience-based intervention that targets self-efficacy surrounding pro-healthy choice behavioral change may be beneficial to the health of the force.

In response to concerns surrounding the notable lack of compliance for Army fitness testing and body composition screenings in the National Guard and the increased stressors experienced by this component of the Army, many of the 54 states and territories' National Guard Ready & Resilient (R2) Programs had initiated a two-week Wellness Camp as a resilience-based intervention. This initiative was designed to address resilience and self-efficacy through adaptations in stressor coping, enhance perception of resilience, and to modify behavior to support enhanced training and performance by empowering soldiers to make healthy nutritional and fitness training decisions.

Wellness Camp resilience-based initiatives do not just benefit the force through decreased administrative flags associated with fitness test and body composition screening failures. These programs have seen notable outcomes such as 30-74 percent fitness test passing rates at the end of the course and long term (three years post-attendance) retention of 70 percent of the participants within the force (HQFLARNG, 2018). Additionally, the significance of the Wellness Camp as a resilience-based initiative is that the initiative has been conducted at a cost

of approximately \$80,000 per iteration and each time this initiative is conducted it has saved National Guard states, districts, and territories millions of dollars (HQFLARNG, 2018).

Statement of the Problem

This study addressed the effectiveness of a resilience-based resolution surrounding the returning of National Guard soldiers to optimal levels of peak performance in both the physical and mental capacity after failing to meet Army standards for the APFT and/or ABCP requirements. The National Guard has seen a steady increase in failure to meet the Army's fitness testing and body composition screening requirements over the last decade (Genger, 2018). There are resilience enhancing outcome benefits of motivation and initiating behavior associated with self-efficacy (Burger & Samuel, 2017; Lane et al., 2004; Schwarzer & Warner, 2013; Williams, 2010). This study examined a population of soldiers that had attended a Wellness Camp resilience-based intervention for the effects of self-efficacy, resilience, and behavior change. Each soldier in this population had an administrative flag on their personnel profiles for having failed their fitness test and/or body composition screening.

Soldier perception of resilience has been shown to be related to previous positive or negative performances (Lester et al., 2011a; Lester et al., 2011b). Though the Army's four major studies conducted on the MRT program demonstrated the effectiveness of the program, all four were conducted using only Active Duty soldiers. Due to no soldiers or units of the Army Reserve or National Guard being included in this study, it is possible that the findings of validity may be more accurate for the Active Duty population of soldiers and may not have external validity to the Reserve Components (Army Reserves and National Guard).

While increases in soldier perception of resilience have been associated with improvements in mental & cognitive stress adaptation, a soldier's resiliency can also be affected

by their physical activity demands and social support structure (Arbisi et al., 2012; Hofschler et al., 2017; Kline et al., 2014; Morgan et al., 2018; Seyed Hojjat et al., 2016; Wang et al., 2018). Deuster and Silverman (2013) suggested that deprivation of exercise had been linked to decreases in mood, but that resilience can be improved through physical fitness. The National Guard population was an optimal candidate to examine based on their higher rates of psychological distress in combat deployments and the casual association between increased mental health concerns and increased Army fitness test failure rates (Grenman, 2018; Kline et al., 2014).

Soldiers that fail to meet the Army's physical fitness and/or body composition standards are administratively flagged against favorable actions (HQDA, 2016), which represents another stress placed on the soldier. A soldier that fails to meet the Army's physical fitness standards or body composition standards during two consecutive recording periods can be administratively separated from service (HQDA, 2017b). Concerningly, a state's Army National Guard's Operations Directorate and Purchasing Directorate combined efforts to establish that the cost associated with the recruiting and re-training of a soldier to replace a soldier separated from service for failing to meet physical fitness and/or body composition standards is approximately \$180,000 per soldier (HQFLARNG, 2018).

The Army's MRT program has been shown to be effective in increasing resilience and psychological health through self-efficacy in the Active Duty Army, with specific focus on Army fitness test performance outcomes being enhanced in soldiers that report higher levels of perceived resilience (Harms et al., 2013; Lester et al., 2011). It was the intent of this study to correlate the effects of resilience training on self-efficacy, through perception of resilience, physical performance, body composition, and application of performance enhancement resilient

strategies in the National Guard population. National Guard soldiers have demonstrated a decrease in ability to return to mental and physical peak performance after exposure to stressors in garrison, civilian life, and combat zones (Arbisi et al., 2012; Hofscher et al., 2017; Kline et al., 2014; Morgan et al., 2018; Seyed Hojjat et al., 2016; Wang et al., 2018). This study addressed this concern by increasing the frequency of resilience training in this study population.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this quantitative, quasi-experimental, ex post facto, survey-based study was to examine the effectiveness of a modified method and frequency for administration of the MRT curriculum for Army National Guard soldiers that have previously failed to meet the Army's fitness and/or body composition requirements to enhance perception and application of resilience, as well as performance on the APFT and ABCP screening. This study sought to establish the statistical significance surrounding effectiveness of the curriculum administration plan in affecting soldiers' perception of resilience, application of resilience to fitness testing, performance on their fitness test, performance in their body composition screening, and the application of performance enhancement resilience skills such as: goal setting, emotional control, imagery, and energy activation to support successful performance in fitness testing.

This study obtained IRB exempt protocol approval from the University of Saint Augustine for Health Sciences (See Appendix C) and formal approval from the Army National Guard's State Training Officer (See Appendix D) to use pre-existing soldier de-identified data in order to establish the effectiveness of a modified MRT implementation intervention. The information gathered was input in SPSS and ANOVAs were conducted in order to establish statistical significance of soldier perception of resilience, application of resilience to their performances and screenings in the Army Physical Fitness Test or APFT and Army Body

Composition Screening, and their implementation of performance enhancement resilience skills to fitness endeavors. The sample of the population was the 87 soldiers that attended the Fiscal Year 2019 Wellness Camp resilience intervention. Survey-based data gathered was include the pre-existing pre- and post-intervention survey data on both the Brief Resilience Scale (BRS) (See Appendix A) and the Test of Performance Strategies (TOPS) (See Appendix B) Surveys. Quantitative performance data for soldiers on both the APFT testing and ABCP screening results for body composition was pulled from the Army's system of record, the Digital Training Management System (DTMS).

Theoretical Framework of Study

This study was designed using a framework of Adult Learning Theory and integrating the theory by establishing soldiers as adult learners. Further, this study incorporated the construct of resilience as a process in its theoretical framework for resilience theory. This study drew associations between the formal theories of Adult Learning and the processed-based resilience framework for the purpose of creating lifestyle changes through enhanced self-efficacy in soldiers that endured stressors associated with the professional repercussions for failing to meet the Army's fitness test and body composition screening standards. Combining these theories, this study used Adult Learning Theory to help teach the Soldiers, as adult learners, to increase their resilience in order to facilitate performance success in either the Army's fitness testing or body composition screening.

The construct of resilience has been a contested concept (Van Breda, 2018). This study was built upon the theory that resilience is a process rather than a fixed end-state. While resilience research has gone through a series of transitions finding its genesis was in childhood vulnerability research with overlapping origin points including in social work, medical fields,

psychology, and education (Masten & Obradovic, 2006; Masten & Reed, 2002; Olsson et al., 2015; Van Breda, 2018). The general consensus regarding resilience theory through the years has transitioned from a fixed and trait-based definition of resilience to a continuum/process approach demonstrating that a person can learn to be resilient (Joyce et al., 2018; Shaw et al., 2016; Van Breda, 2018). The process-based view of the resilience construct implied that one can learn to be resilient and that one can learn to positively adapt to adversity. The process-based resilience construct supported the mission of this study in that by enhancing soldier self-efficacy, soldiers may be more likely to make positive and healthy behavioral changes that support passing the Army's fitness testing and body composition screenings which will result in removal of administrative flags from their profiles and enhance the operational readiness of the force according to Army Doctrine (HQDA, 2014b; HQDA, 2016).

Diving deeper, this study examined the construct of resilience from the theoretical view of Adult Learning Theory. Understanding the andragogical process of adult learners supported a vehicle toward successful translation of concepts (Kenner & Weinerman, 2011; Malik, 2016; McCall et al., 2018). This study expanded on how adult learners enter the educational process, formally or informally, with different experiences that can provide hinderance or encouragement in educational endeavors (Kenner & Weinerman, 2011; Malik, 2016; McCall et al., 2018). This theory allowed this study to develop the individual learning needs of the soldier and facilitate success in lifestyle changes that support long term resilience and physical performance growth. Combining both the process-oriented construct of resilience with Adult Learning Theory supported a framework of success in this study. Through examining Adult Learning Theory process and effectively intertwining it to support the translation of the resilience process to soldiers, this study examined optimal outcomes not only in perception of resilience but also

healthy lifestyle choices that support meeting the Army's fitness and body composition requirements.

Research Questions

The research study was guided by the following research questions:

- RQ1.** To what extent does a two-week resilience intervention have an effect on perceived levels of resilience when compared before and after intervention in traditional National Guard soldiers who fail to meet the Army's physical fitness requirements and minimum standards?
- RQ2.** To what extent does a two-week resilience intervention have an effect on Army Physical Fitness Testing Scores on record fitness testing when compared to before and after record fitness testing results for National Guard soldiers who had previously failed to meet Army physical fitness requirements and minimum standards?
- RQ3.** To what extent does a two-week resilience intervention have an effect on body composition testing outcomes for record body composition screenings when compared to before and after record body composition screening results for National Guard soldiers who had previously failed to meet Army physical fitness requirements and minimum standards?
- RQ4.** To what extent does a two-week resilience intervention have an effect on the application of goal setting as a performance enhancement resilience strategy when compared to before and after self-reported perception of the strategy for National Guard soldiers who had previously failed to meet Army physical fitness requirements and minimum standards?

- RQ5.** To what extent does a two-week resilience intervention have an effect on the application of emotional control performance enhancement resilience strategies when compared to before and after self-reported perception of the strategy for National Guard soldiers who had previously failed to meet Army physical fitness requirements and minimum standards?
- RQ6.** To what extent does a two-week resilience intervention have an effect on the application of imagery performance enhancement resilience strategies when compared to before and after self-reported perception of the strategy for National Guard soldiers who had previously failed to meet Army physical fitness requirements and minimum standards?
- RQ7.** To what extent does a two-week resilience intervention have an effect on the application of energy activation performance enhancement resilience strategies when compared to before and after self-reported perception of the strategy for National Guard soldiers who had previously failed to meet Army physical fitness requirements and minimum standards?

Hypothesis

- H₁.** Traditional M-Day National Guard soldiers that attend a two-week Wellness Camp resilience intervention will demonstrate a statistically significant change in their post-screening perception of personal resilience when compared to their pre-screening resilience perception.
- H₂.** Traditional M-Day National Guard soldiers that attend a two-week Wellness Camp resilience intervention will demonstrate a statistically significant change in their

fitness performance on their next record fitness testing when compared to their initial fitness test scores.

- H3.** Traditional M-Day National Guard soldiers that attend a two-week Wellness Camp resilience intervention will demonstrate a statistically significant change in their body composition screening results on their next record body composition screening.
- H4.** Traditional M-Day National Guard soldiers that attend a two-week Wellness Camp resilience intervention will demonstrate a statistically significant change in their application of goal setting performance enhancement strategy of resilience when compared to their pre-intervention baseline ability.
- H5.** Traditional M-Day National Guard soldiers that attend a two-week Wellness Camp resilience intervention will demonstrate a statistically significant change in their application of the emotional control performance enhancement strategy of resilience when compared to their pre-intervention baseline ability.
- H6.** Traditional M-Day National Guard soldiers that attend a two-week Wellness Camp resilience intervention will demonstrate a statistically significant change in their application of the imagery performance enhancement strategy of resilience when compared to their pre-intervention baseline ability.
- H7.** Traditional M-Day National Guard soldiers that attend a two-week Wellness Camp resilience intervention will demonstrate a statistically significant change in their application of the energy activation performance enhancement strategy of resilience when compared to their pre-intervention baseline ability.

Significance of Study

This study provided positive outcomes in multiple areas of resilience, self-efficacy, fitness, and operational readiness. While the positive benefits of resilience training have been examined in the foundational research, the foundational research was only conducted on Active Duty service members which have significantly different levels of stressors and rates of stress-related mental health concerns when compared to the National Guard (Arbisi et al., 2012; Kline et al., 2014; Russell et al., 2019). There has been a concern surrounding the resilience training frequency of the National Guard when comparing the doctrinal differences in required resilience training between Active Duty and the National Guard (HQDA, 2014a; HQDA, 2017a), the link between resilience, self-efficacy, and healthy choices in fitness and nutrition; as well as the National Guard's elevated rate of fitness and body composition failures (Russell et al., 2019). This study held the potential to identify a more beneficial resilience training frequency for the National Guard that could be considered for doctrinal adaptation.

Research had previously linked those who have increased physical fitness to an increased perception of their resilience (Lines et al., 2019; Williams et al., 2013). Self-efficacy had been established as a supportive factor of resilience that can mediate concerns for limited social support (Cassidy, 2015; Crane et al., 2017; Lester et al., 2011; Rees et al., 2015; Wang et al., 2017). It has been established that the National Guard soldiers have an increased perception of stressors when compared to the Active Duty due to limited social support (Arbisi et al., 2012; Hofscher et al., 2017; Kline et al., 2014; Morgan et al., 2018; Wang et al., 2018). Further, the negative effects of soldiers of the National Guard having elevated rates of administrative flags have been shown to impact both the fiscal and operational readiness capacities of the force (HQFLARNG, 2018). This study sought to fill a research gap surrounding resilience training's

effects on National Guard soldiers' self-efficacy toward healthy behaviors. The outcomes of this research study addressed the identity of a potential correlation between resilience and overall health by establishing resilience as a vehicle toward health and wellbeing.

Assumptions

This study drew five assumptions. The areas of assumption included permissions to access data, findings of statistical significance, funding limitations on implementation of findings into the Army National Guard, soldiers having filled out the surveys honestly, and the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) specific assumptions. The primary assumption was that the Army National Guard's State Training Officer would grant permissions to use de-identified soldier data from DTMS for their APFT and body composition outcomes. This assumption was made based on the researcher's intent to de-identify the soldier's information from their performance and to de-identify the state providing the data for the research to ensure no reader could draw conclusions as to which state or soldiers were involved in the intervention being studied.

The second area of assumptions made for this study addressed the findings of statistical significance surrounding all seven research questions. The Wellness Camp intervention demonstrated anecdotal success in soldier retention and performance outcomes in fitness testing and body composition screening. It was unknown if these outcomes were associated with aspects outside the resilience intervention or if it was the resilience intervention that was driving the success. This study assumed based on the supporting resilience literature that it was the intervention driving the results and that the ANOVAs demonstrated statistical significance. In particular, the assumptions of this study presumed that the ANOVAs would prove statistical significance for the intervention's positive outcomes in soldiers' perception of resilience; application of resilience to fitness testing and training; use of performance enhancement skills of

goal setting, emotional control, imagery, and energy activation; as well as statistical significance for the soldiers' improvement of fitness test performance and body composition screening.

The third assumption made by this study was that the funding of the Army National Guard may affect implementation of the intervention on a wider scale. The current Wellness Camp resilience intervention was executed at approximately \$80,000 for 50 soldiers by the Army National Guard (HQFLARNG, 2018). While the cost avoidance of the Wellness Camp supported implementation, this study assumed that ensuring the wider scale implementation of the intervention would be a fiscal concern for each of the 54 states and territories of the Army National Guard.

The fourth assumption made in this study addressed the soldiers' honest completion of the two surveys. The 87 soldiers of this study were asked to complete two surveys at two separate time points. This study was built upon the assumption that these surveys were completed accurately and honestly by the soldiers.

The final assumption made in this study included the ANOVA specific assumptions. These are homogeneity of variance, population is of normal distribution, the ANOVA is robust, and that variance is identical and will be explained by the model (Field, 2018, p. 395-398; Neutens & Rubinson, 2014, p. 245). These statistical assumptions are in accordance with other ANOVA-style studies.

Limitations

The limitations of this study included the soldiers that participated in the intervention were command directed to attend the intervention by their chain of command, the soldiers were geographically distributed across the state and their local areas may not support their needs post-intervention, and the researcher did not have authority over the soldier participants of this study.

All three of these limitations created potential concerns surrounding effectiveness and legitimacy of this study.

Delimitations

Noting the previously mentioned limitations of this study, they were delimited with specific processes implemented. Any concerns addressing compliance of the participants such as the command directing of attendance by soldiers' chain of command and the lack of command authority of the researcher over the participants were delimited by the intervention's memorandum of information (MOI) for the intervention. This document explained the purpose and expectations of the participants, acting as a contract between the unit chain of command, the soldier participant, and the researcher. To mitigate and delimit the concern for geographic distribution of the participants, the researcher gathered military and personal emails and cell phone points of contact to ensure long-term follow-ups could be made to verify soldier actions post-intervention.

Definitions of Key Terms

ABCP. Army Body Composition Program, body composition screening used to measure soldier body composition through establishing a Body Mass Index (BMI) value and Body Fat Percentage (BF%) through first establishing height and weight on a BMI table broken down by age and sex brackets. Then performing a girth comparison ratio where males use a two-point (neck and abdomen) comparison and females use a three-point (neck, abdomen, and hip) comparison to establish circumference values and BF% (HQDA, 2016).

Administrative Flagging Actions/“Flagged”. Administrative flag placed on a soldier's personnel file and profile to signify failure to meet fitness and/or body composition

standards. Flagging actions do not allow soldiers to be in leadership roles, to draw benefits such as tuition assistance or bonuses, or attend military schools (HQDA, 2016).

APFT. Army Physical Fitness Test, fitness testing measures soldier physical performance in the areas of muscular endurance and cardiovascular endurance through a three-event fitness test with a score established by sex and age brackets per event ranging from 0-100 points based on individual performance and characteristics. Total score for the APFT is given as a numeric value in the range of 0-300. The events of the APFT are the two-minute pushup test, the two-minute sit-up test, and the two-mile run (HQDA, 2016).

ARFORGEN. Army Forces Generation, the original Army force readiness model. The ARFORGEN model is a three year process for Active Duty soldiers and five year process for Reserve Component soldiers where the soldiers cycle through a reset and recovery phase, a phase of training to prepare to deploy, and a phase of ready to deploy (HQDA, 2019a).

BattleMind. Deployment-oriented Resilience program initiated prior to the MRT program specifically for deploying soldiers that addressed common stressors experienced by soldiers and provided coping mechanisms. System consisted of a pre-deployment and post-deployment training block. (Zamorski et al., 2018).

BRS. Brief Resilience Scale, six question survey addressing perception of resilience (See Appendix A) (Smith et al., 2008).

CSF. Comprehensive Soldier Fitness program, 2009-2011 program governing resilience in the Army (Casey, 2011).

CSF2. Comprehensive Soldier and Family Fitness program, 2011-present program governing resilience in the Army (HQDA, 2014a).

DSM. Diagnostic and Statistical Manual for Mental Health Disorders, establishes diagnostic criteria per mental health disorders (Arbisi et al., 2012).

DTMS. Digital Training Management System, Army's online secured system of record managing and tracking all soldiers' training (HQDA, 2017a).

GAT. Global Assessment Tool, digital survey conducted annually by all soldiers to address the CSF areas of fitness and resilience (Peterson et al. 2011).

GWOT. Global War on Terror, the overarching military operation covering OEF, OIF, OIR, OND, and ONE (Casey, 2011)

MRT. Master Resilience Training/Trainer, Resilience training curriculum/embedded resilience instructor trained soldier (Casey, 2011).

PRP. Penn Resilience Program, the University of Pennsylvania's Applied Positive Psychology program that was re-designed to develop the Army's MRT curriculum (Reivich et al., 2011).

PTSD. Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder, any disorder on the post-traumatic stress spectrum

Resilience. The dynamic process of positive adaptation surrounding one's ability to demonstrate growth from stress and to thrive in adversity (Van Breda, 2018).

SRM. Sustainable Readiness Model, Army's new deployment generation plan for units (HQDA, 2019a)

TOPS. Test of Performance Strategy survey, 20 questions addressing application of resilience to performance enhancement strategies (See Appendix B) (Thomas et al., 1999).

Organization of the Remainder of the Study

Chapter one of this study set the stage for this study. It provided an introduction and background to the concern leading to the purpose and necessity of this study conducted. With the hypotheses and research questions explained, this study could be visualized for the IRB and researcher. Chapter two functions as a review of the literature and will elaborate on various sub points supporting the research. The chapter exhausts the findings in the literature and draws conclusions between concepts listed. This chapter provided the necessary breadth and depth that supported the approval and conduct of this study. Chapter three elaborates on the methodology of this study. This chapter dives deeper into the methodology, research design, population, and sample to better explain the details of the process to establish statistical significance. This functions to provide the necessary depth of information on the plan to produce necessary statics and how conclusions are drawn from the data. Chapter four addresses the outcomes of this study. This chapter lists statistical findings by each research question and explains the researcher's decisions in rejecting all null hypothesis. Chapter five addresses the conclusions, recommendations, and suggested future research. This chapter digests the findings from chapter four and offers recommendations for future elaboration in research.

Chapter 2: Literature Review

The purpose of this study was to examine the effectiveness of a two-week Master Resilience Training (MRT)-based Wellness Camp intervention. The Wellness Camp is a resilience and self-efficacy intervention for National Guard soldiers that are at risk of separation from service. The risk of separation from service is due to the soldiers having failed to meet the Army's fitness requirements on the APFT and/or exceeding the Army's body composition requirements on the ABCP record screenings. The interventions effectiveness was established using pre-existing soldier data on Army Physical Fitness Test (APFT) performance, Army Body Composition Program (ABCP) screening, self-reported perception of resilience using the Brief Resilience Scale (BRS) (See Appendix A), and self-reported perception of use of performance enhancement strategies using the Test of Performance Strategy (TOPS) (See Appendix B) survey.

Both the APFT and ABCP data were pulled from the Army's Digital Training Management System (DTMS), the required program for tracking soldier performance in these areas. Both the BRS and TOPS data were pulled from the National Guard host state's or territory's Ready and Resilient (R2) program records for participant soldiers. Contemporary literature supported the use of resilience training as an intervention to increase self-efficacy in both the mental and physical domains to enhance performance and healthy behaviors; thus, supporting the implementation of resilience interventions designed to address both APFT and ABCP concerns in the Army (Black et al., 2017; Cacioppo et al., 2015; Cassidy, 2015; Lester et al., 2011; Nindle et al., 2018; Nindle et al., 2013). Resilience training has been associated with positive adaptation to stressors resulting in enhanced self-efficacy, motivation, and behavioral

change surrounding peak mental and physical performance (Cacioppo et al., 2015; Nindle et al., 2018; Nindle et al., 2013).

This literature review will cover the supporting areas of the framework including resilience theory and adult learning theory, then will transition to a broad examination of the construct of resilience. The review's section on resilience will focus on the genesis of the construct of resilience, the development of the process-based view of resilience theory, and finally motivation and self-efficacy as supporting subcomponents of resilience. Once the broad overview of resilience has been examined, the review will transition to a focus on the need for resilience in the military population. The review will dive into an overarching view of resilience training's development in the Army due to increased rates of suicidality and other behavioral health concerns after prolonged bouts of conflict associated to the Global War on Terror. Next, the review will break down stressors experienced by soldiers overall, followed by a breakdown of soldier stressors by branch (Active Duty, National Guard, Army Reserves). Finally, this portion will conclude with an examination of the role of self-efficacy as a resilience by-product that has an effect on the resilience process for soldiers. This section is meant to establish the need for resilience training and will set the stage for the next section which examines the doctrinal requirements for resilience training in the Army.

The section addressing doctrinal requirements for training will establish the current doctrinal requirements of training by branch of service, the conflict surrounding the MRT curriculum and the Comprehensive Soldier Fitness (CSF)/Comprehensive Soldier and Family Fitness (CSF2) program/SHARP Ready & Resilient (SR2) programs, and the effects of resilience training on operational readiness with respect to administrative flags. Having established an understanding of each relationship between concepts addressed. The literature review will then

transition to examine what the National Guard is currently doing to combat the elevated rates of administrative flags. Here the literature review will address the Wellness Camp as it was utilized in this study. This section will discuss the Wellness Camp as a resilience-based intervention and will examine the research supporting both the BRS and TOPS surveys, the two instruments used to collect resilience perception data as part of the intervention.

Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework used for this study examined both Resilience Theory and Adult Learning Theory. In particular, this study's framework was built to examine Resilience Theory through the lens of Adult Learning Theory with a specific focus on a population of soldiers that endured increased perceptions of stress as adult learners. This study set a goal to approach a formal tie between the theories of Adult Learning to the current process-based resilience construct. The understanding that Adult Learners leverage previous experience and that one's ability to rebound from adversity were heavily leaned upon for this study. The conduction of this study through the combined lens of resilience theory and adult learning theory were important, as it set an important distinction of soldiers as adult learners that could learn the skills to overcome their current adversities. The ideal outcome of conducting a study through this combined lens was the creation of lifestyle changes in fitness training and nutritional intake. These fitness and nutritional changes were made by leveraging enhanced self-efficacy in soldiers that are dealing with the stress associated with professional repercussions of failing to make compliance with the APFT and ABCP requirements.

Implementing the Resilience Theory Framework into the Study

While the theoretical construct of resilience is a contested concept, this study chose to address resilience as a process rather than an end-state fixed in each soldier. This process-based

approach to resilience is in line with the views of multiple research groups including Dray et al. (2017), Lines et al. (2019), Van Breda (2018), and Wang et al. (2017). However, this study intended to take their works and expand upon the knowledge by applying the process-based approach and a focus on thriving through behavioral change inherent in resilience theory to a group of National Guard soldiers. These National Guard soldiers of this study held the potential to take value from the intervention.

The process-based view of resilience suggested that by enhancing one's resilience their self-efficacy is also elevated which supported the overall goal of this study (Black et al., 2017; Cacioppo et al., 2015; Cassidy, 2015; Lester et al., 2011; Nindle et al., 2018; Nindle et al., 2013). The intent of the framework was to give soldiers that were at risk of separation due to APFT/ABCP failure the skillsets to self-motivate and make positive changes into healthy behaviors supporting their overall fitness and nutrition. The general consensus in research theory has transitioned through the years from a fixed or trait-based aspect of resilience to a continuum and/or process approach demonstrating that a person can learn to be resilient and self-efficacious (Joyce et al., 2018; Van Breda, 2018; Shaw et al., 2016). It is important to note, that the previous framework of the construct combined fixed and trait-based approaches to resilience; however, the more modern view of the theory modified the trait-based approach to one of internal character strengths that can be developed and leveraged for successful adaptation to adversity (Bolton et al., 2017; Joyce et al., 2018; Van Breda, 2018; Shaw et al., 2016). This distinction is important as this study used the term of character strengths as an internal motivator and any confusion is limited by developing the understanding of difference between character strengths and traits.

Development of self-efficacy as a by-product of resilience theory was vital to this study and was built upon the foundational work of Bandura (1982) where he described a concept of self-agency inherent in self-efficacy. Bandura (1982) expanded on this empowerment of self to thrive in that enhanced internal agency promoted positive outcomes in behavioral change and task starting behaviors. Understanding that self-efficacy is a by-product of enhancing the process of resilience across a spectrum of stressors experienced supported the needs of the soldiers regarding exercise initiation behavior and healthy nutritional decision making, effectively tying together resilience and performance (Bandura, 1982; Black et al., 2017; Cassidy, 2015; Nindle et al., 2018; Nindle et al., 2013). This is an important theoretical view of the construct as the process approach suggested that the process can be learned and that anyone can improve or degress their resilience or self-efficacy.

A movement in resilience theory that further added credence to this study was described by Bolton et al. (2017), in that the process-based approach to resilience and its ability to be developed to drive positive adaptation in people under stress can be applied to practitioners using solution-focused treatments. To expand on this concept, there was a movement away from the traditional medical-model where diagnostics were the primary focal point of care, to a model of personal strengths and competency-based treatments that worked to empower the patient by leveraging their internal strengths and their external resources to thrive (Bolton et al., 2017). This movement was of value to this study in that the target population was traditional National Guardsmen that were only in uniform one-weekend a month and two-weeks a year, they did not have the continuous oversight for which their Active Duty counterparts had access. This conceptual movement in resilience theory lends itself well to the National Guard soldier population.

Examining Resilience Theory through the Lens of Adult Learning Theory

Examining the construct of resilience as a process from the perspective of Adult Learning Theory was the intent of this study. The Adult Learning Theory's implementation into the military population has been a point of contention in the Army's professional military education (PME) curriculum and courses. The Army's PME courses were designed as basic-level military education courses to transition a civilian to a soldier, develop soldiers and officers, or to have established a special skillset (Pierson, 2017). However, Pierson (2017) noted that a sizable portion of the Army's PME were designed as advanced-level education that would benefit from implementation of Adult Learning Theory. Accounting for the variance in level and purpose of military education courses, it became a point of note that military education was able to be adapted to enhance educational outcomes through implementation of Adult Learning Theory's concepts (Pierson, 2017; Wendt, 2018)

Adult Learning Theory's implementation into PME and other aspects of the Army's education systems was important due to soldiers qualifying as non-traditional or adult learners. Adult learners were defined within the Adult Learning Theory as those non-traditional learners that were 25 years of age or older (Malik, 2016; McCall et al., 2018; Pierson, 2017; Yarbrough, 2018). Soldiers can join the military with parental consent at the age of 17-years old and can serve up until they are 61-years of age, which presented with some overlap with the minimum age of an adult learner according to the Adult Learning Theory (Malik, 2016; McCall et al., 2018; Pierson, 2017). Soldiers were generally considered non-traditional learners not-solely based on their age but also on the nature of education formats implemented across both the basic- and advanced-level courses (Pierson, 2017).

Adult Learning Theory applies four principles and makes a series of assumptions regarding the adult learner population. The four principles applied through Adult Learning Theory are the need to involve adult learners in the learning process development and evaluation, role positive and negative experiences play in activities of learning, need to establish relevance to the adult learner to increase learning motivation, and problem-centered versus content-oriented approach to learning (Mukhalalati & Taylor, 2019; McCall et al., 2018). These assumptions include that adult learners are self-directed learners, in need of understanding as to why the learning must occur, known to draw heavily from their previous experiences, more drawn to problem-based learning, ready to learn as a coping mechanism to real-life scenarios, and are intrinsically motivated in their learning process (Malik, 2016; Pierson, 2017; Teaching Excellence in Adult Literacy, 2011). An educator that has developed a thorough understanding and comprehension of the learning process of adult learners supports success in conceptual translation between the learner and instructor (Kenner & Weinerman, 2011; Malik, 2016; McCall et al., 2018).

The Army's Training and Doctrine Command (TRADOC) changed its verbiage focus from terms such as 'training' to more Adult Learning Theory appropriate terms like 'education' as it more accurately reflected the intent of the Army's PME (Pierson, 2017). Adult Learning Theory has seen a research increase over the last decade as the population of adult learners has seen notable increases in academia (McCall et al., 2018). Considering both research groups' findings between McCall et al. (2018) work on general education and adult learners and Pierson's (2017) work on soldiers as adult learners, it was suggested that with the increased focus on implementing Adult Learning Theory for the appropriate audiences and non-traditional

educational nature of soldiers it was worth expanding the Army's educational training to be one of more Adult Learning Theory focus.

This study leveraged resilience theory's process-approach to build upon the informal and formal entrance to the learning process of adult learners. It was important to account for how adult learners' varied experiences acted to either hinder or reinforce their motivation to succeed (Bandura, 1982; Kenner & Weinerman, 2011; McCall et al., 2018; Malik, 2016). Adult Learning Theory was important to this study's framework in that defining the soldier as an adult learner and both leveraging their internal motivations and developing their individual learning needs helped to facilitate success in lifestyle changes that support long term resilience and growth in both physical and mental performance.

Adult Learning Theory in the MRT Curriculum

The Army's MRT curriculum was built around the needs of the adult learners. Reivich's (2014) Master Resilience Training Trainer Manual incorporated multiple Adult Learning Theory concepts to enable optimal translation of concepts to the adult learners. These concepts include self-reflection, problem-based learning, and self-directed learning (McCall et al., 2018; TEAL, 2011; Yarbrough, 2018). Colvin and Taylor (2012) described the ages of the typical unit MRT, the soldier training the skillsets, in the ranges of 26-35 years of age which qualified the trainers as adult learners. This knowledge of the age of the trainer means that the coursework should be designed to support adult learning. Thus, the previously mentioned methods are valid not just in the formal training but also in the implementation to the force to enable success in learning for all soldiers (Pierson, 2017).

Adult Learning Theory suggested that there is value in self-reflection for adult learners (McCall et al., 2018; Mukhalalati & Taylor, 2019; TEAL, 2011; Yarbrough, 2018). Three of the

MRT skills (Hunt the Good Stuff, ATC Model, and Detect Icebergs) were built around the concept or skill of self-reflection and its ability to enhance either optimism or self-awareness (McCall et al., 2018; Mukhalalati & Taylor, 2019; Reivich, 2014; TEAL, 2011; Yarbrough, 2018). Yarbrough (2018) suggested that self-reflection was nested within Vygotsky's 'Zone of Proximal Development', a component of Social Development Theory. In the Zone of Proximal Development, the learners worked to identify gaps of ability and developed their skills around the identified gap (Yarbrough, 2018). The skill of self-reflection acted to enable self-awareness and sets the stage for problem-based learning's implementation in education.

Problem-based learning has also been cited as an effective approach to Adult Learning Theory's implementation (Malik, 2016; Mukhalalati & Taylor, 2019; TEAL, 2011; Yarbrough, 2018). Yarbrough (2018) described how problem-based learning falls within both transformational learning and critical reflection which were supported theories to the Adult Learning Theory. The problem-based learning approach was seen nested in almost every MRT skillset's participant guide, which allowed the learners to see how to implement resilience into their daily lives (Reivich, 2014). Problem-based learning assisted in demonstrating to the adult learner their motivation for self-determined learning.

Self-directed learning has been described as a necessity for adult learners (Malik, 2016; Mukhalalati & Taylor, 2019; Pierson, 2017; TEAL, 2011; Yarbrough, 2018). Mukhalalati and Taylor (2019) described adult learners as intrinsically motivated learners. This concept of intrinsic motivation supports Pierson's (2017) description of self-directed learners as learners that require little to no guidance or direction in their studies. The CSF2 program required soldiers to take the GAT annually, the GAT identifies soldier strengths and weaknesses in each of the supported areas of fitness that comprise the Army's view of resilience (HQDA, 2014a; HQDA,

2017a; Peterson et al., 2011). Lester et al. (2013) described a series of 27 self-directed courses that the CSF2 program provided to soldiers to enhance their resilience. Each soldier's GAT results were used to provide them with a series of self-directed courses that they could progress through to improve areas of weakness (Lester et al., 2013).

Application of the Framework to the Study

The MRT curriculum was designed to teach soldiers the skills to become more resilient when dealing with stress and strife by using Adult Learning Theory (Casey, 2011; McCall et al., 2018; Reivich, 2020a; Reivich et al., 2011). The MRT curriculum was further developed to enhance the competencies of self-awareness, self-regulation, mental agility, optimism, strengths of character, and connection (Casey, 2011; Reivich, 2020a; Reivich et al., 2011). McCall et al. (2018) described a constructivist approach to Adult Learning Theory where learners were exposed to strategies supporting self-inquiry, discovery, and problem-based learning to drive awareness of skills for critical thinking and overall awareness of overarching themes. This conceptually applied to all six of the MRT curriculum's competencies (Casey, 2011; McCall et al., 2018; Reivich, 2020a; Reivich et al., 2011).

The theory that the construct of resilience is a process that promotes self-efficacy when combined with the Adult Learning Theory's assumptions of adult learners provided this study a framework for success based on the research questions and hypotheses (Black et al., 2017; Cacioppo et al., 2015; Dray et al., 2017; Kenner & Weinerman, 2011; Lines et al., 2019; McCall et al., 2018; Malik, 2016). Through examining Adult Learning Theory and how the theory could effectively support the translation of the resilience process to the soldiers it was possible to establish optimal outcomes not only in perception of resilience in the face of strife but also in healthy lifestyle choices that supported meeting the Army's fitness and body composition

requirements (Black et al., 2017; Cacioppo et al., 2015; Dray et al., 2017; Kenner & Weinerman, 2011; Lines et al., 2019; Malik, 2016; McCall et al., 2018). These supporting theories appeared to build a bridge of educational success in support of soldier improvement in the areas of physical performance and nutritional choices to decrease body composition.

The Development of the Construct of Resilience in Literature

The construct of resilience has seen multiple evolutions in a conceptual renaissance that has expanded over the last five decades (Masten & Obradovic, 2006; Olsson et al., 2015; Van Breda, 2018). The modern definition of resilience embodied the process of one's ability to demonstrate positive adaptation in the face of stressors and to thrive against adversity (Dray et al., 2017; Lines et al., 2019; Van Breda, 2018; Wang et al., 2017). The process-focused aspect of resilience's definition was an important component in that it represents a continuum-like response across a lifespan that could fluctuate and could be learned (Wang et al., 2017). Most modern researchers supported the process-based definition of resilience, but it was important to understand where the construct found its genesis to more accurately understand the modern definition of resilience.

The seed of resilience theory first began to form in the early 1970s as part of research focused on early childhood development and vulnerability. Research conducted by Garmezy (1971) was designed to discover psychopathological preventative concepts with the assumption that childhood experiences dictated vulnerability and enhanced frequency of adult-onset psychopathology. Garmezy's approach to vulnerability established a fixed origin in one's early lifecycle that would ultimately result in psychopathology (Garmezy, 1971; Van Breda, 2018). In particular, the research of that era was origin-focused and addressed outcomes with a fixed perspective. The research groups suggested that children with elevated levels of exposure to

genetic, nurtured, and environmental risk factors such as mental illness, parental smoking and substance abuse, poverty and violence would ultimately have increased potential for psychopathology (Van Breda; 2018). Toward the mid-1970s researchers shifted to examining how lifecycle transitions affected maturation throughout the human lifespan, this suggested that a human's response to various stressor stimuli was dictated by their 'exosystem' or external environment and not their internal processes and coping skills (Bronfenbrenner, 1977; Luthar, Cicchetti, & Becker, 2000; Van Breda, 2018). This transition in resilience theory's focus from internal to external would continue to be contested as the construct's definition advanced until later in the 1980s (Lines et al., 2019; Luthar, 2006; Rutter, 1987; Van Breda, 2018).

In the late 1970s some researchers returned to the internal focus of resilience theory by expanding upon the concept of skills usage to support development. Kobasa (1979) examined business executives and noted a trait set that seemed to make the executives hardier and less prone to illness. Sroufe (1979) also examined trait focused outcomes in children, this suggested that a resilient child was one who had traits that allow them to be flexible and react in control to stimulus. This trait focused approach was more in line with the construct of ego-resilience and ego-control, where the focus was on character traits and personality style and suggested only particular groups of traits and personality styles would have success in the face of stress and adversity (Constatine et al., 1999; Luthar, 2006; Luthar & Zigler, 1991; Sroufe, 1979; Stainton et al., 2019; Ungar, 2011). Under the trait-based view of resilience theory, it was believed that the effective traits supporting ego-resiliency and ego-control would always result in positive adaptation, this suggested that resilience described an enduring set of traits that never fluctuated (Stainton et al., 2019; Sroufe, 1979; Ungar, 2011). The trait and personality focal approaches taken by researchers in early resilience construct development suggested that resilience was a

fixed aspect across humanity; one either has it or they do not (Stainton et al., 2019; Sroufe, 1979; Ungar, 2011). The trait-based approach to the construct of resilience would later be adapted as the ‘assets’ component of resilience seen in more modern definitions (Stainton et al., 2019).

An arguably defining moment in what is known as modern resilience theory was the change in resilience research seen in the 1980s where researchers began to examine how particular exposures to developmental stimuli resulted in enhanced human agency and self-efficacy (Bandura, 1982; Luthar, 2006; Van Breda, 2018). This significant shift from resilience as a fixed state to that of resilience as a developmental process marked the beginning of what would many years later become the Army’s definition of resilience. Much of this era’s research in resilience focused on protective factors that not only mitigated vulnerability during maturation but suggested risk inoculation and hardening against stressors (Lines et al., 2019; Luthar, 2006; Van Breda, 2018). One of the classic research articles on resilience from this era by Garmezy et al. (1984) began by establishing working models on challenges, compensatory mechanisms, and protective factors in resilience. These models were instrumental in the future development of theories surrounding protective factor development skills (Luthar, 2006). A second landmark study conducted later in the 1980s by Rutter (1987) began the paradigm shift from the internal to external focus more globally in the field of resilience research by identifying resilience as a multi-process approach including self-efficacy and esteem maintenance, creation of opportunity, risk impact reduction, and negative reaction chain reduction (Dray et al., 2017; Lines et al., 2019; Luthar, 2006; Rutter, 1987). Weick et al. (1989) further expanded the research in this area by establishing a philosophical and practical level approach to develop strengths through social work. These major changes in resilience research would begin to shape the modern definition of resilience.

The 1990s were formative for the modern definition of resilience. The outcome and trait-based approach to the construct of resilience began to transition to a continuum supported by a process-based view where resilience traits were described as assets that worked to integrate both the internal perspective and the external resources to set the stage for positive adaptation (Luthar & Zigler, 1991; Stainton et al., 2019; Van Breda, 2018). Research of the era failed to accurately capture the broad array of individual experiences and sources that can lead to enhanced perception of stress and adversity (Van Breda, 2018). As an example, research by Luthar and Zigler (1991) suggested that the resilience definitions of their era did not accurately explain the current discoveries surrounding stress and adversity associated with the effects of individual experiential aspects of social and emotional, intelligence, and self-efficacy in social interactions. Contrary to much of the contemporary literature of the time Masten et al. (1990) conducted research that suggested children that matured under chronic adversity were better postured to recover and thrive if exposed to supportive factors such as positive relationships. This research would begin to demonstrate a process- and continuum-oriented movement in resilience theory as concepts of processes such as hope, optimism, and self-efficacy began to be associated with resilience (Lines et al., 2019). Luthar et al. (2000) described a resilience definition that mirrored the modern definition of resilience as a process-oriented approach that drove positive adaptation within exposure to adversity. This was the era of research that recognized the role external factors played in the development of resilience and the fluid and fluctuating nature of resilience (Lines et al., 2019; Luthar, 2006; Van Breda, 2018). The conceptual view of resilience being both fluid and fluctuating along a continuum supported this study in that the intent was to measure the effectiveness of the MRT curriculum in enhancing the perception and application of resilience.

Though the modern definition of resilience was beginning to form, there were still notable discrepancies in some schools of thought surrounding resilience. Luthar et al. (2000) suggested that there were primarily four areas of discrepancy with regard to the construct of resilience, while broad in nature they were: theoretical framework discrepancies, interdomain variance, ambiguity in definition, and instability in the perception of the resilience phenomenon. Extreme variance existed in the aspects of theoretical frameworks of resilience, where between the early 2000s and the mid-2010s over 12 different theories were suggested for resilience causing additional defining discrepancies on the topic (Fletcher & Sarkar, 2013; Luthar et al., 2000). Kolar (2011) voiced a concern for confusion surrounding the construct of resilience's definition consistency between interlocking domains that addressed the construct. To further illustrate this, concerns were discussed by many researchers that surrounded the perception of resilience as a trait versus a process (Fletcher & Sarkar, 2013; Olsson et al., 2015; Stainton et al., 2019; Van Breda, 2018).

Tusaie and Dyer (2004) described the multitude of views defining the construct of resilience as ranging anywhere from a qualitative categorical construct with a defined end-state to a never-ending adaptation continuum lending itself to success in multiple experiences. Fletcher and Sarker (2013) advanced the discussions in their suggestion that inconsistent definitions of the construct, particularly regarding delineation of adversity and positive adaptation were some areas of concern regarding the number of discrepancies in resilience theory. Globally speaking, the areas of concern caused wide-scale instability in the research and affecting the experts' views of the phenomenon of resilience in that era (Luthar et al., 2000). The areas of concern noted by Fletcher and Sarkar (2013), Kollar (2011), Luthar et al. (2000), and Tusaie and Dyer (2004) surrounding the credibility of resilience research created notable issues

between research groups that resulted in concerns for the credibility of resilience's foundational research.

The ambiguity surrounding resilience definition was of concern in the study, as the time frame noted by the research groups of Fletcher and Sarkar (2013) coincided with the launch of the Army's Master Resilience Training (MRT) curriculum which was based on a process-based view of the construct of resilience (Casey, 2011; Doobey et al., 2018; Peterson et al., 2011; Reivich et al., 2011; Zamorski et al., 2018). Stainton et al. (2019) addressed the concern for issues in the theoretical framework in that despite the notable hinderances associated to discrepancies in schools of thought the research still supported value in the concept of resilience. The concern for interdomain variance in resilience research could be broadly addressed with the noted transference of resilience process skills across domains be they previously experienced or novel in nature to the individual (Lines et al., 2019).

While some trait-based and fixed-state research have been published in the modern era of resilience the vast consensus of resilience researchers have found validity in viewing the construct from the process-oriented perspective, where an individual's perception and level of resilience falls upon a continuum that has multiple internal and external factors affecting its potency to drive positive adaptation (Lines et al., 2019; Stainton et al., 2019; Van Breda, 2018). Considering the common schools of thought in the late 2010s era of resilience research it was safe to assume that many of the concerns for instability in the phenomenon of resilience across research domains have been mitigated. Understanding the effects of both the internal and external factors on an individual's adaptation process across the continuum of life created a clearer picture to the functionality of resilience as a process.

The Construct of Resilience in Contemporary Literature: Process-Based View

While the construct of resilience's definition has undergone dynamic shifts from conceptual inception in the 1970s through the mid-2010s, some leading to conceptual argument and disagreement between research groups, most modern researchers have come to a consensus, having agreed to define resilience as a process (Dray et al., 2017; Lines et al., 2019; Stainton et al., 2019; Van Breda, 2018). Nindle et al. (2018) and Ungar (2011) posited that resilience was seen as a dynamic process that supported positive adaptation as a protective function in stress coping and management. This dynamic process included an interplay between the perception of risk and stress to the individual's inherent compensatory and coping responses (Nindle et al., 2018; Stainton et al., 2019). Protective factors included in this process view include both personal and environmental factors that set the stage for individual positive adaptation (Stainton et al., 2019). These common consensuses on the process-based view of resilience and positive adaptation coincided with the Army's view of resilience and the MRT curriculum's approach to teaching resilience to soldiers (Casey, 2011; Doobey et al., 2018; Peterson et al., 2011; Reivich et al., 2011).

An individual's resilience perception process could be affected by their supporting mechanisms affecting stress perception, available external and internal assets, and resources used to enable successful adaptation to stressors (Lines et al., 2019; Stainton et al., 2019; Van Breda, 2018). This concept of support mechanisms was equivalent to the Army's doctrinal description of mental agility as a supporting mechanism for resilience. Army doctrine required leaders to develop a resilient and mentally agile adaptation process as part of their leader presence (HQDA, 2012a). Maximizing an individual's behavioral, cognitive, and emotional mechanisms supported the resilience process through the creation of a multi-faceted internal support structure that

results in optimal adaptation (Lines et al., 2019). Stainton et al. (2019) suggested that the utilization of inherent character traits supporting positive adaptation was the characterization of assets regarding the resilience process. While assets are an internal process to the individual, resources supporting resilience as a process are considered external to the individual including their familial, social, and community support structures that enabled positive adaptation (Stainton et al., 2019; Van Breda, 2018). The MRT curriculum was designed as a resilience training program to address the internal processes of the individual to enable enhanced acquisition of external resources. Categorically aligning protective factors, mechanisms, resources, and assets with the process of stress mitigation in resilience demonstrated the exclusivity and individuality of the process in that no two individuals would respond in similar adaptations to the same stressors (Stainton et al., 2019).

The process of resilience was found to act across an individual's lifespan at points of exchange between perception of risk and coping response (Nindle et al., 2018). Other researchers have argued that the process can only exist if the individual is exposed to adversity and demonstrated a positive adaptation in response to adversity (Lines et al., 2019; Olsson et al., 2015). January (2016) suggested a third point must exist between adversity exposure and adaptation in the resilience process, she argued that nested between the end-points must exist an appraisal of the situation resulting in an interpretation of a growth opportunity by the individual thereby enabling the positive adaptation described by Lines et al. (2019), Nindle et al., (2018) and Olsson et al. (2015). January's (2016) concept when included into the resilience process painted a more accurate picture of the resilience continuum response to adversity by having established the existence of an unseen and internal positive coding of the stressor. The researchers' views on resilience as a process across the lifespan supports the Army's description

of ideal levels of resilience in leadership in that Army leaders should be adaptive and should continuously learn and grow from experiences (HQDA, 2012).

The resilience process addressed positive adaptations to stressors; however, these are not the only form of adaptation an individual can demonstrate when meeting adversity. An individual can demonstrate a range of adaptations to an adversity exposure. Processes resulting in the viewing of the stressor from a growth mindset, improved perception of self-efficacy, and application of coping skills to mitigate stress are commonly viewed as beneficial adaptation (Black et al., 2017; Cacioppo et al., 2015; January, 2016; Stainton et al., 2019). Lines et al. (2019), Van Breda (2018), and Wang et al. (2017) suggested that trauma and adversity are more commonly coded negatively by an individual and thus result in negative outcomes such as law and rule breaking behaviors, decreased motivation levels, decreased physical performance, demonstration of depressive symptoms, development of post-traumatic stress continuum disorders, and substance abuse. While there are multiple potential response directions which an individual can demonstrate in reaction to adversity, productive adaptations are more desirable than counter-productive adaptations.

Morgan et al. (2018) argued that despite the older definition of resilience's view, resilience is not a static or trait-based concept. Morgan et al. (2018) argued that the process-based definition of resilience and its ability to be learned by anyone most accurately supported natural and appropriate human adaptation to adversity. Stainton et al. (2019) suggested that an individual who failed to demonstrate positive adaptation to adversity exposure in the past can learn from the experience and could be taught to apply appropriate coping skills in future adversity exposures based on the previous experience; thus, acting as a stress inoculation for the individual. Further, Nindle et al. (2018) and Wang et al. (2017) argued that experiential learning

can enable appropriate behavioral responses to internal, external, and environmental adversity that promote positive adaptation in line with the modern construct of resilience. The noted positive outcomes in behavioral change and self-efficacy supported a need for additional resilience training in the population of soldiers who fail to meet the Army's APFT and ABCP requirements. While resilience is a process, this process is supported by sub-concepts that further enable desired outcomes in fitness and nutritional choices that were targeted by this study.

The Six Competencies that Support Resilience

Researchers described the process of resilience as an individual's efficacy in six focal areas or competencies (Harms et al, 2013; Lester et al., 2011; Reivich, 2011; Reivich, 2014; Reivich, 2020a; Reivich et al., 2011). The six supporting competencies included optimism, self-awareness, self-regulation, mental agility/self-efficacy, interpersonal connection, and the ability to harness one's strengths of character (Dooby et al., 2019; Griffith & West, 2013; Harms et al., 2013; Lester et al., 2011; Reivich, 2014; Reivich, 2020a; Reivich et al., 2011). These were the same 'core competencies' for which the Army's Master Resilience Training (MRT) curriculum was built to enhance in soldiers (Griffith & West, 2013; Lester et al., 2011; Reivich, 2014; Reivich et al., 2011). The MRT curriculum targeted these competencies to train soldiers to be able to thrive in adversity as it is suggested that they contribute to the process of resilience (Reivich, 2014; Reivich et al., 2011).

Optimism was an important competency that supported the resilience process and was the initial competency addressed in the MRT curriculum (Reivich, 2014). Reivich and Shatte (2003, p. 40) described the role of optimism in resilience as a view of a positive future despite the current adversity experienced that drives positive adaptation. Reivich (2020c) further suggested that optimism functioned as a foundational 'engine' of resilience, in that optimism allows for the

development of resilience. Further, the MRT curriculum incorporates three optimism-based skills (Hunt the Good Stuff, Real-Time Resilience, and Put It In Perspective) that are designed to overcome what was described as the negativity bias and act as the ‘engine’ in the resilience process (Reivich, 2014; Reivich & Shatte, 2003, p. 40-41).

Skills building and/or developing optimism enable the resilience process (Reivich, 2014; Reivich & Shatte, 2002, p. 186; Seligman & Csikszentmihalyi, 2000). The skill of ‘Hunt the Good Stuff’ was adapted from Seligman’s concept of the ‘Three Blessings’ skill used to overcome negativity bias and reinforce both optimism and hope through positive psychology techniques (Reivich, 2014; Reivich, 2020a; Seligman, 2002; Seligman, 2006; Seligman, 2012; Seligman, 2020c; Seligman & Csikszentmihalyi, 2000). The skill of ‘Real-Time Resilience’ was adapted from the positive psychology skill of the same name to be used to empower an individual through an internal response to counterproductive thoughts (Reivich, 2014; Reivich, 2020c; Reivich & Shatte, 2002, p. 186). The skill of ‘Put It In Perspective’ (PIIP) was designed to address an individual stuck in an anxiety fueled catastrophizing state and when appropriately implemented allowed the individual to break the chain of catastrophic thoughts preventing them from taking productive actions (Reivich, 2014; Reivich, 2020f; Reivich & Shatte, 2002, p. 168-170). Each optimism-based skill has its time and place for implementation, but all are effective in allowing for one to move forward in the resilience process (Reivich, 2014; Reivich, 2020a).

By targeting the competency of optimism with the skills of ‘Hunt the Good Stuff’ and ‘Real-Time Resilience’ an individual can overcome the negativity bias and can be empowered to fight internal counterproductive thoughts to reinforce their resilience by adding a protective factor from feelings of helplessness (Reivich, 2014; Reivich, 2020a; Seligman, 2006; Seligman, 2012; Seligman, 2020a). The negativity bias was described as the increased likeliness and nature

for humans to orient toward and recall negative and threatening information or experiences at a higher frequency than non-threatening and positive information, which was also suggested to undermine the resilience process (Carstensen & DeLiema, 2018; Reivich, 2014; Reivich, 2020a; Reivich & Shatte, 2003, p. 6, 33, 40-41). The MRT curriculum was designed to enhance optimism to overcome the negativity bias, enable problem solving, enhance perception of hope, and develop self-efficacy (Reivich, 2014).

Self-awareness is the second competency supporting the resilience process (Griffith & West, 2013; Lester et al., 2011; Reivich, 2014; Reivich, 2020a; Reivich et al., 2011). The competency of self-awareness was designed to address an important pillar of resilience and aspect of cognition therapy in that awareness of cognitions/thoughts was seen as a key to resilience (Reivich, 2014; Reivich & Shatte, 2002). Self-awareness was addressed by the MRT skills of ‘Activating Events – Thoughts – Consequences’ (ATC) model and ‘Detecting Icebergs’ (Reivich, 2014). Self-awareness was an important competency for the resilience process as being aware of one’s thoughts and how one reacts to their thoughts can allow them to proactively address stressful events and enable more productive responses to the stressors, thus no real growth or change can happen without self-awareness (Reivich, 2014; Reivich & Shatte, 2002, p. 66).

The resilience skills addressing the competency of self-awareness are built upon therapies from both the cognitive behavioral and rationale emotive behavioral approaches (Reivich, 2014; Sarracino et al., 2017). The foundational skill was the ATC model, the majority of the MRT curriculum is built upon this model (Reivich, 2014). The ATC skill was adapted from the Adversity – Beliefs – Consequences (ABC) model developed by Ellis showing that there is a linkage between one’s thoughts (or beliefs) and both the emotions experienced, and reactions

displayed (Ellis, 1962, p. 15-20; Reivich, 2014; Sarracino et al., 2017). A deeper diving skill into the resilience competency of self-awareness was the skill of Detecting Icebergs. In this skill the focus was to identify underlying or core values and beliefs that affect an individual's thoughts, emotions, and behaviors (Beck, 2011, p. 228-242; Reivich, 2014; Reivich & Shatte, 2002, p. 123-125). These skills supported the resilience process by enabling the individual to become aware of their thoughts and how they affect the adaptive response and further give the individual the choice to make changes in these responses through appropriate proactive techniques (Reivich, 2014).

The third competency supporting the resilience process was self-regulation (Griffith & West, 2013; Lester et al., 2011; Reivich, 2014; Reivich, 2020a; Reivich et al., 2011). This competency was designed to be addressed in curriculum after the learners have been taught the self-awareness skills, as this competency allows for modification of discovered undesirable thoughts and beliefs from the self-awareness competency (Reivich, 2014). There are three skills used to target the resilience competency of self-awareness, 'Goal Setting', 'Energy Management', and 'Mental Games' (Reivich, 2014; Reivich & Shatte, 2002, p. 204-205). These skills provided the individual with specific coping tasks that can enable progress once a stressed state was identified and could further be used to permit the individual to make progress in positive adaptation (Reivich, 2014).

The skills that supported the resilience competency of self-regulation were designed to assist the person in regulating multiple areas affecting resilience adaptation including emotions, impulses, behaviors, and physiology (Reivich, 2014). The first self-regulation skill was 'Goal Setting' which addressed achievement of identified goals through education on various areas including extrinsic and intrinsic motivational factors of the individual, leveraging of motivation

through contrasting thoughts and alignment of values, and the development of a planning process toward goals using the Specific-Measurable-Actionable-Realistic-Time bound (SMART) approach (Gollwitzer & Oettingen, 2011; Locke & Latham, 2002; Reivich, 2014; Ryan & Deci, 2000; Sevincer et al., 2014). The second self-regulation skill was the skill of ‘Energy Management’ which taught the individual to diaphragmatically breath (deliberate breathing), proactively use the ATC model, and to leverage their autonomic nervous system to manipulate their physiology and activate the ideal level of energy for the activity at hand (Defense Centers for Excellence for Psychological Health and Traumatic Brain Injury [DCEPHTBI], 2011; Jokela & Hanin, 1999; Park, 2020; Reivich, 2014; Reivich, 2020b). The third skill addressing self-regulation as a resilience competency was the skill of ‘Mental Games’ which taught individuals a quick coping skill to re-direct or compartmentalize their attention from counterproductive thoughts allowing the individual to make progress under stress (Reivich, 2014; Reivich & Shatte, 2002, p. 204-205). These skills supported the process of resilience by providing the trained individuals with self-regulating tactics that allow them to positively adapt to stressors (Reivich, 2014).

The fourth competency supporting the resilience process was mental agility (Griffith & West, 2013; Lester et al., 2011; Reivich, 2014; Reivich, 2020a; Reivich, Seligman, & McBride, 2011). The competency supported the resilience process by enabling individuals to examine situations that occur from a multitude of angles through the lenses of flexibility, accuracy, and thoroughness to ensure they were perceiving the correct information (Reivich, 2014; Reivich, 2020e). The skills that target mental agility were ‘Avoid Thinking Traps’ and ‘Problem Solving’ (Reivich, 2014; Reivich, 2020e; Reivich & Shatte, 2002, p. 95-100, 145-155). These skills taught

individuals to be more resilient through identification of common pitfalls in perspective which allowed for avoidance of misinformation (Reivich, 2014).

The resilience skills targeting mental agility addressed target outcomes such as learning to think more accurately in times of stress, taking other's perspectives, accurately identifying the problem and understanding what was within one's control, and the willingness to take on new strategies for success (Reivich, 2014). Reivich (2020a) described mental agility to be intertwined with the concept of self-efficacy through the process of strategy modification and adoption; as well as identification and understanding of problems. The skill of 'Avoid Thinking Traps' taught learners to both identify and escape from the six common thinking traps that prevent the person from taking productive action (Reivich, 2014; Reivich, 2020b; Reivich & Shatte, 2002, p. 95-100, 145-155). The skill of 'Problem Solving' was a six-step process that first taught the learner to accurately identify the issue by removing confirmation bias then to develop a plan to address the aspects of the issue that were within one's control (Reivich, 2014; Reivich, 2020e; Reivich & Shatte, 2002, p. 95-100, 145-155). These skills allowed the learner to develop both an openness to change and a process to make productive changes (Reivich, 2014; Reivich, 2020b; Reivich, 2020e; Reivich & Shatte, 2002, p. 95-100, 145-155).

The fifth competency that supported the process of resilience was strengths of character (Griffith & West, 2013; Lester et al., 2011; Reivich, 2014; Reivich, 2020a; Reivich et al., 2011). This competency was built upon research stemming back to Aristotle that focused on identifying 24 common characteristics across cultures, religions, and ages and was designed to teach learners to identify their 'signature' character strengths and to be able to identify character strengths in others as well as how to use these character strengths to drive success in any challenge (McGrath, 2014; Park et al., 2004; Park et al., 2006; Pawelski, 2020; Reivich, 2014; Reivich,

2020g). The skills that supported the competency of strengths of character were ‘Identify Character Strengths in Self and Others’ and ‘Character Strengths: Challenges in Leadership’ (Reivich, 2014). These skills were designed to leverage the learner’s character strengths to overcome challenges and create effective teams (McGrath, 2014; Park et al., 2004; Park et al., 2006; Reivich, 2014; Reivich, 2020g).

The resilience skills that targeted strengths of character addressed outcomes such as accurately identifying one’s own signature character strengths as well as others, leveraging one’s character strengths to overcome obstacles, having faith in one’s own strengths, and enhancing one’s internal view of their strength(s) (McGrath, 2014; Park et al., 2004; Park et al., 2006; Reivich, 2014; Reivich, 2020g). In the skill of ‘Identifying Character Strengths in Self and Others’ the learner took the Values in Action (VIA) survey by the University of Pennsylvania and reviewed their results, this data was used in comparison to the norms of the United States of America population (n=84,000) from the VIA survey, then they expanded their learning by being given examples of great leaders (Rosa Parks, MLK, Abraham Lincoln, etc.) and asked to identify the character strengths of those leaders (Park et al., 2004; Park et al., 2006; Reivich, 2014). The second skill ‘Character Strengths: Challenges in Leadership’ built upon the learner’s ability to identify signature character strengths and taught them to think proactively to leverage their signature strengths to overcome any challenge or adversity they may encounter (Reivich, 2014). The competency of strengths of characters was designed to develop one’s ability to empower themselves and to actively seek engagement of others to achieve success (McGrath, 2014; Park et al., 2004; Park et al., 2006; Reivich, 2014; Reivich, 2020g).

The final competency of resilience was connection (Griffith & West, 2013; Lester et al., 2011; Reivich, 2014; Reivich, 2020a; Reivich et al., 2011). This competency was built upon

tenets such as relationship building, effective communication strategies, empathy development, help seeking behaviors, and support (Ames, 2009; Gable et al., 2006; Kamins & Dweck, 1999; Reivich, 2014; Reivich, 2020h; Reivich & Shatte, 2002, p. 221-226; Seligman, 2020b; Seligman, 2020d). The resilience skills that supported this competency were ‘Effective Praise and Active Constructive Responding’ and ‘Assertive Communication’ (Ames, 2009; Gable et al., 2006; Kamins & Dweck, 1999; Reivich, 2014; Reivich, 2020h; Seligman, 2020d). The intent of these skills was to enhance the learner’s network and quality relationships through enhanced communication strategies (Reivich, 2014).

Skills that targeted connection were beneficial in enhancing the resilience process through positive adaptations to relationships and networking that supported the positive emotion, engagement, relationships, meaning, and achievement (PERMA) model (Kern et al, 2015; Seligman, 2018; Seligman, 2020b). In the skill of ‘Effective Praise and Active Constructive Responding’ the learners were taught the process of verbalizing successful strategies to enable future success and the four style of communication with a focus on adoption of communication strategies aligned with the active constructive style (Gable et al., 2006; Kamins & Dweck, 1999; Reivich, 2014; Reivich, 2020h; Seligman, 2020b). This skill enabled quality interpersonal connections and develops empathy (Kamins & Dweck, 1999; Reivich, 2014; Reivich, 2020h). The skill of ‘Assertive Communication’ taught the learners to avoid passive and aggressive communication styles in favor of the assertive communication style by developing their process of being clear, confident, and controlled in communication (Ames, 2009; Reivich, 2014). These skills helped to improve the quality of relationships and interpersonal networks through improved and meaningful connection (Ames, 2009; Gable et al., 2006; Kamins & Dweck, 1999; Reivich, 2014; Reivich, 2020h; Seligman, 2020d).

The Army's Master Resilience Training (MRT) program was built upon the six core competencies that enabled the adaptation process to stressors and adversity (Harms et al, 2013; Lester et al., 2011; Reivich, 2014; Reivich, 2020a; Reivich et al., 2011). The competencies of optimism, self-awareness, self-regulation, mental agility, strengths of character, and connection all supported a framework of self-efficacy that supported positive adaptation and held beneficence for service members enduring increased perception of stress (Dooby et al., 2019; Griffith & West, 2013; Harms et al., 2013; Lester et al., 2011; Reivich, 2014; Reivich, 2020a; Reivich et al., 2011; Seligman, 2020a). These competencies not only supported the resilience process but resulted in improved self-efficacy (Harms et al., 2013; Lester et al., 2011; Reivich, 2020b; Reivich & Seligman, 2011; Seligman, 2020e).

Self-Efficacy as a Supporting Component of Resilience

Self-efficacy has been seen as a component supporting the process of positive adaptation to stress described in the resilience process by multiple researchers (Cassidy, 2015; Crane et al., 2017; Hong et al., 2018; Reivich, 2020b). General self-efficacy was seen as a belief structure in one's ability and capacity to apply effective strategies and achieve positive outcomes (Crane et al., 2017; Hong et al., 2018; Pickering et al., 2017). This is in-line with Bandura's (1982) concept of self-efficacy in that perception holds power of influence over choices that guide achievement through human agency. The process that supported achievement enabled coping strategies that facilitated an outcome demonstrating resilience in stressful situations and allowing for increased perception of one's human agency (Cassidy, 2015; Crane et al., 2017; Hong et al., 2018). Cassidy (2015) argued that individuals that reported elevated levels of self-efficacy were noted to have decreased markers in areas such as depression, anxiety, and malaise that affected performance-enabling activities. Wang et al. (2017) noted in a study (n=747) that self-efficacy

had a direct relationship and effect on perception of resilience. A focus on self-efficacy as an outcome in a resilience-based intervention has been noted to result in increased perception of resilience and human agency (Cassidy, 2015; Crane et al., 2017; Hong et al., 2018).

Bandura (1982) tied self-efficacy to the larger construct of human agency as a mechanism to drive effective outcomes. Two theories have assisted in the implication of self-efficacy's role in human agency, they were the Structuration and Cognitive Behavioral theories (Pickering et al., 2017; Van Breda, 2018). Opong (2014) and Van Breda (2018) described Structuration Theory as the examination of individual influences driven by external forces and internal capabilities to affect their determination and decision freedoms. Jones et al. (2018) noted that Cognitive-Behavioral Theory addressed an individual's ability to re-appraise and evaluate threats to decrease perceptions of stress. These theories described forces that effected one's perception of self and autonomy through interpretation of experience and external or internal effects on the decision-making process (Jones et al., 2018; Opong, 2014; Pickering et al., 2017; Van Breda, 2018).

From the lens of the supporting theories, human agency has been seen as one's ability to obtain professional skills, abilities, and to create and identify with an identity; while simultaneously acting as a representation of one's professional transformation and contribution (Goller & Harteis, 2017). Further aligning with Goller and Harties (2017) perspectives, Pickering et al. (2017) suggested that human agency could be viewed as a broad group and social construct that helped to drive innovation supported by self-efficacy. Combining these concepts, it appears that both professional identify and professional innovation are linked to enhanced performance (Goller & Harteis, 2017; Pickering et al., 2017). This point becomes paramount when examining soldier concern in the areas of APFT and ABCP compliance, in that if positive contributions to

the profession enhance self-efficacy and human agency, then it stands to reason that failure to meet professional requirements would act in opposition (Goller & Harteis, 2017; Pickering et al., 2017). Thus, soldiers failing their APFT testing and/or ABCP screenings would benefit from resilience training that enhanced human agency and self-efficacy outcomes.

Elaborating on human agency's definition, it has been pragmatically viewed as an individual's performance capacity regarding professional settings aligned with established and influential goals that drive professional participation (Pickering et al., 2017). Building upon Pickering et al. (2017) definition of human agency; this construct described the role an individual has in being a change agent to affect their own environment and course of life (Goller & Harteis, 2017). The construct of human agency is generally used in the context of learning and skills development by way of the underlying foundation of an individual's self-efficacy (Cassidy, 2015; Crane et al., 2017; Goller & Harteis, 2017; Hong et al., 2018).

As a construct, human agency has had an enduring concern paralleling resilience's definition confusion. Goller and Harteis (2017) suggested that some researchers have viewed human agency as a trait and others viewed it as an outcome. This was of concern regarding the modern definition of resilience's transition from state and trait-based approaches to the process-based definition. Self-efficacy appeared to play a more predominant role in the outcome perspective of human agency, in that self-efficacy's foundational role in human agency supported emotional wellbeing through the processes of cognition, affect, selection, and motivation (Cassidy, 2015). Building upon this perspective, self-efficacy allowed emotional control and regulation to support successful adaptation of professional innovation (Hong et al., 2018). Thus, self-efficacy supported human agency's effects on positive outcomes which functions in the process of resilience.

Self-Efficacy and Perception of Self's Effect on Behavior Change

An individual's perception of self-efficacy has been shown to be influential on their processes surrounding arousal of emotion, action taking behaviors, and patterns of thought in the pursuit of goals (Bandura, 1982; Cassidy, 2015; Lines et al., 2019). Self-efficacy played an important function in emotion control and regulation which was vital in making positive adaptation to stressors. Crane et al. (2017) elaborated on this role of self-efficacy in emotion control in that optimal levels of perception of self-efficacy created psychological coping strategies that allow for down-regulation of emotional responses to threat perception. Lines et al. (2019) suggested that self-efficacy's effect on emotional regulation was strongly influenced by the individual's perception and belief in their personal self-efficacy.

Conceptually speaking, self-efficacy directly modulated perceptions of stress (Burger & Samuel, 2017; Crane et al., 2017; Lines et al., 2019). Regulation and control of emotional responses to various stressors have been viewed as a protective factor (Burger & Samuel, 2017; Cassidy, 2015; Lines et al., 2019). Crane et al. (2017) suggested that self-efficacy plays a role in stressor interpretation and appraisal, and that increased levels of perception of self-efficacy were inversely correlated to appraisal of threats. Thus, self-efficacy supported the process of resilience by providing psychological resources that assisted in managing emotional response and enabling an individual to take productive actions toward a goal.

Crane et al. (2017) and Lines et al. (2019) suggested that the increased availability and usage of internal psychological resources was believed to be the driving force of association between enhanced self-efficacy and decreased stress that created an ideal environment for skill acquisition (Crane et al., 2017; Lines et al., 2019). By reducing stress appraisal, an individual can alleviate their confidence, anxiety, and distress concerns that affect skill acquisition (Hong et al.,

2018). By decreasing perceptions of stress and removing psychological barriers affecting learning, education, and skill acquisition self-efficacy enabled positive adaptation thereby supporting the process of resilience (Hong et al., 2018; Lines et al., 2019).

Self-Efficacy's Emotional Role in Resilience and Behavior Change

Self-efficacy functioned as an emotional component to resilience in its association with regulation of emotional responses that enabled behavioral change and motivation modulation (Hewitt et al., 2017; Hong et al., 2018; Lines et al., 2019). An individual's emotional resilience modifies their internal assets through adjusted perceptions of autonomy and sense of self (Constantine et al., 1999; Hewitt et al., 2017). Increased levels of perception of an individual's autonomy and sense of self have directed positive perception of meaning in work which then enabled increased motivation and sense of meaning in work (Constantine et al., 1999; Crane et al., 2017; Goller & Harteis, 2017). Burger and Samuel (2017) in a study (n=5,126 participants) independently compared both self-efficacy and perception of stress noted a positive relationship between self-efficacy and life satisfaction while also having noted a negative relationship between perception of stress and life satisfaction. Burger and Samuel's (2017) study further supported conceptual points noted by the research groups Constantine et al. (1999), Crane et al. (2017), and Goller and Harteis (2017) regarding self-efficacy's role in the process of resilience.

This study examined the need of soldiers enduring administrative flagging actions due to failure to meet the Army's requirements for the APFT and/or ABCP. These flagged soldiers learned to adopt new healthy behaviors that supported exercise and nutritional actions that supported their pursuit in passing the APFT and/or ABCP. The perception of self-efficacy's emotional component and its beneficial effects on both motivation and behavioral change for skill acquisition played an important role in the process of resilience in the adoption of new

behaviors (Constantine et al., 1999; Crane et al., 2017; Hewitt et al., 2017; Hong et al., 2018; Lines et al., 2019). Behavioral change that supported the adoption of health behaviors surrounding both enhanced physical activity and improved nutritional choices were supported by the resilience process by way of increased self-efficacy (Black et al., 2017; Cacioppo et al., 2015; Constantine et al., 1999; Crane et al., 2017; Hewitt et al., 2017; Hong et al., 2018; Lines et al., 2019). Thus, soldiers that failed to meet the Army's requirements for the APFT and ABCP would benefit from self-efficacy's by products of enhanced behavioral change strategies and motivation supporting health habits and behaviors.

An individual's perception of self has been shown to be directly correlated to their ability to not only initiate but to also sustain a behavior (Middlekamp et al., 2017). Crane et al. (2017) noted in a study (n=81 participants) that members of the population that displayed increased levels of self-efficacy and thusly resilience, demonstrated increased skill acquisition through positive changes in motivation and behavior that supported learning the skill. Both, Crane et al.'s (2017) and Middlekamp et al. (2017) concepts further supported the rationale for soldiers' need to enhance self-efficacy to decrease ABCP and APFT failures.

Self-Efficacy's Effect on Exercise and Nutrition

Positive healthy behaviors in the areas of exercise and nutrition have been shown to be positively affected by self-efficacy improving actions including education and decision autonomy (Issner et al., 2017; Kashani et al., 2016). Self-efficacy supported healthy behavior choices through empowerment associated with education and autonomous decision making (Kashani et al., 2016). Supporting this stance, a study (n=100 participants) conducted by Issner et al. (2016) noted that individuals that reported higher levels of resilience and self-efficacy successfully predicted healthy nutritional choices and exercise program compliance. Further, a

study comparing (n=80) an intervention group against a control group (n=80) by Vitali et al. (2019) demonstrated that an intervention designed to develop physical self-efficacy in exercise resulted in behaviors that enhanced exercise compliance and further resulted in enhanced outcomes in various measures of fitness. These studies demonstrated the effectiveness of self-efficacy in regulating behavioral change that supported positive outcomes in exercise.

Motivation and Self-Efficacy

Motivation has been linked to self-efficacy, in that tenants of individual self-efficacy such as initiating behaviors, competence, thought patterns, autonomy, effort persistence, and psychological resources have been noted as requirements to drive enhanced motivation (Asimakopoulos et al., 2017; Jo et al., 2018). Behavioral changes are affected directly by self-efficacy through modulation of an individual's belief in personal ability to succeed and indirectly through expectation management of goals, barriers, and outcomes (Jo et al., 2018). It has been suggested that the primary component of self-efficacy affecting positive change in motivation is autonomy, in that it has been shown to support motivation in the sustainment of participation growth (Bebeley et al., 2015). A study (n=500) by Bebeley et al. (2015) suggested that interventions targeting motivation enabled exercise self-efficacy by enhancing autonomy. Another study (n=23) demonstrates that improvements in self-efficacy were associated with self-esteem and psychological factors congruent with motivation (Jo et al., 2018). These studies supported the role motivation played in enhancing self-efficacy regarding activities that supported healthy behavior change.

Perception of self-efficacy supported resilience by operating in a stress buffering, behavioral change, and motivation moderation capacity that gives the individual internal mechanisms to drive positive adaptations (Hewitt et al., 2017; Hong et al., 2018; Lines et al.,

2019). Initiatives addressing self-efficacy have been shown to be important in the development of agency and resilience in multiple populations (Bandura, 1982; Black et al., 2017; Cassidy, 2015; Nindle et al., 2018; Nindle et al., 2013). While self-efficacy's beneficial role in civilian populations is known, it is important to also examine the role self-efficacy has played in the resilience process for the military population to support positive adaptation.

A Case for Resilience in Soldiers

Military resilience training was not implemented to enhance self-efficacy to benefit administrative flags and personnel readiness. This benefit was not realized until well after resilience training was implemented into the force's training doctrine. Resilience as an intervention for service members was implemented due to war-related stressors (Casey, 2011; Reivich et al., 2011). General William T. Sherman's quote, "War is Hell" best illustrated the original driving force for resilience training implementation in the Army (Grossman, 2009, p. 73; Grossman & Christensen, 2008, p. 142). The atrocities of war have been experienced by warfighters across every period of armed conflict. There is a strong association existing between psychological symptomatology and the exposure to the savagery and brutality of war (Arbisi et al., 2012; Casey, 2011; Hart et al., 2000; Kline et al., 2014; Laufer et al., 1984). However, not all stressors perceived by service members are directly related to combat and war, some are linked to professional performance and family life concerns.

While the nature of this study was to address the fitness and body composition outcomes associated with resilience training, it is important to understand the spectrum of stressors experienced by service members including deployment cycle and war related stressors as these stressors combine with and multiply the stressors associated with fitness and body composition failures. This generation of soldier has known on-going wartime operations on multiple fronts in

support of the global war on terror, including Operation Iraqi Freedom (OIF), Operation New Dawn (OND), Operation Inherent Resolve (OIR), Operation Enduring Freedom (OEF), and Operation Noble Eagle (ONE). The Army Force Generation (ARFORGEN) deployment cycle concept recently was modified in Army doctrine becoming the Army's Sustainable Readiness Model or SRM (Feickert, 2017; HQDA, 2019b). Under the ARFORGEN model active component soldiers were given a three-year window where the soldier deploys for a year, returns home for six months of reset and recovery, then starts an 18-month deployment training cycle. This has been modified under SRM to reflect no established times for training cycles to increase deployable and ready units to two thirds of the force (Feickert, 2017; HQDA, 2019b). Despite the change from the ARFORGEN to the SRM, the Reserve components' (National Guard and Reserves) deployment cycle remains a five-year window where soldiers are deployed for a year, spend a year in reset and recovery, then start a three-year deployment training cycle (Feickert, 2017; HQDA, 2014b; HQDA, 2019c). This equates to approximately 1,825 days in combat zones for Active Duty soldiers and 1,095 days in combat zones for reserve component soldiers. These are hefty numbers that have drastically increased exposure to psychological trauma. A thorough understanding of this deployment frequency has become instrumental to better understanding combat exposures and associated concerns for soldier stress perception, mental health, and the need for resilience in this population.

In a broader sense, research has suggested that veterans and service members experience elevated rates of stress and psychological disorders when compared to civilians (Trautmann et al., 2017; Mobbs & Bonanno, 2018; Yancbus et al., 2018). It has been noted that two of the biggest stressors for service members are relationship-oriented stressors and military professional related stressors (Nock et al., 2013). Ringer et al. (2018) suggested that many of the stressors

experienced by service members, despite belonging to either the active duty or reserve component, are unique when compared to civilians and are mostly related to differences in military and civilian cultures.

Soldiers and Stress: Family and Work

Nock et al. (2013) described both family and work-related concerns for service members that were unique to military culture. Considering the nature of the ARFORGEN and its later replacement the Sustainable Readiness Model (SRM), service members have experienced readiness for deployment and selection for deployment at rates as frequent as one year in every three (HQDA, 2014b; HQDA, 2019c). The associated separation from family can lead to an increased perception of stress surrounding family life and family care. Further, in the military, service members must not just maintain proficiency in their military job but are also required to pass fitness and body fat percentage standards that are not required of the civilian population (HQDA, 2016; HQDA, 2017b; HQDA, 2019e). An additional work-related stressor was created by the requirement of both fitness and body composition standards for service members per Army doctrine (HQDA, 2017b). Failure to meet these requirements can separate a service member from their military service removing their financial support and further compounding family-related stressors (HQDA, 2017b). These stressors are unique to the military population and not seen in the civilian experience.

Soldier Stress Related to Civilian Views of the Armed Forces

While service-related and family-related stressors have been major aspects of stress perception in the military, there has also been a concern surrounding stressors related to civilian interpretation of service members. A 2017 study (n=48 participants) examined the civilian view of service members, in this study the participants demonstrated a notable association of mental

instability with service members (Schreger & Kimble, 2017). The importance of this study was that it empirically demonstrated an overarching civilian association bias between mental instability and military service (Schreger & Kimble, 2017). The population of United States Americans currently serving in the military is approximately 803,000 service members, which represents only 0.2 percent of the total population (DMDC, 2019). As a small subset of the United States American population, additional stressors are experienced by soldiers due to a general view of mental instability by the larger population (Schreger & Kimble, 2017).

Holistically speaking, the total stress experienced by soldiers compounds and decreases soldiers' resilience which has been closely related to negative changes in soldier self-efficacy and positive behavioral change that supported compliance with the APFT and ABCP requirements.

Stressors by Army Component (Active Duty, Army Reserve, and National Guard)

It is important to also look at the differences in mental health concerns from each of the Army's components (Active Duty and reserve components: Army Reserves or National Guard) to better understand the need for resilience across the force's different components. One report found that 15 percent of an Army National Guard unit (n=348) deployed overseas met DSM diagnosable criteria for post-traumatic stress spectrum disorders and that 99 percent self-reported post-deployment at least one combat exposure (Arbisi et al., 2012). A larger study (n=922) found that National Guardsmen experienced higher rates of post-traumatic stress spectrum disorder than their Active Duty counterparts at 16.3 percent compared to 9.3 percent (Kline et al., 2014). These elevated rates were likely associated with the differences in social support and community engagement seen between Active Duty and reserve components of the force (Arbisi et al., 2012; Hofscher et al., 2017; Kline et al., 2014; Morgan et al., 2018; Wang et al., 2018).

Adding to the stressors experienced by the reserve components of the Army (Army Reserve and National Guard), Russell et al. (2019) reported that the National Guardsmen had significantly higher odds of failing the Army physical fitness test (APFT) than their Active Duty counterparts. The National Guard demonstrated a much higher percentage of soldiers failing to meet the Army's fitness standards at 8.7 percent more than Active Duty and an increased failure to meet compliance with the Army's body composition program (ABCP) by 3.65 percent when compared to their Active Duty counterparts (Bernstein et al., 2017; DMDC, 2019a; HQFLARNG, 2020; Meyer, 2018; Sih & Negus, 2016). Cacioppo et al. (2015) suggested that lower levels of resilience resulting from loneliness can cause physiological issues affecting physical performance in exercise such as hypertension and other cardiovascular disease. They go on in their suggestion that social resilience training could be integrated into fitness training and could potentially assist in exercise compliance and performance. There are negative physiological responses associated with distress that can also affect a soldier's physical performance capacity (Black et al., 2017; Cacioppo et al., 2015; Dickerson & Kemeny, 2004; Sokolova, 2013). It is suggested that psychological stressors not only affect the person physiologically but also impact self-efficacy and motivation which has been shown to support compliance with performance training (Black et al., 2017; Cacioppo et al., 2015). Nindle et al. (2013) suggested that by increasing soldier resilience the Army could decrease injury rates and increase performance. This study built upon these concerns and intended to examine how the National Guard, as a reserve component of the Army, could benefit from enhanced Master Resilience Training (MRT) considering its higher rates of stress when compared to the Active Duty component to mitigate mental health concerns and to increase self-efficacy surrounding healthy behaviors.

Service members' stress perception has not only been affected by combat service and experience, but also by stressors associated with the culture of the military, the perception of post-combat service's effect on service members by the civilian population, and component of service (Nock et al., 2013; Ringer et al., 2018; Schreger & Kimble, 2017; Trautmann et al., 2017; Mobbs & Bonanno, 2018; Yancbus et al., 2018). These stressors are unique to military service and not experienced by civilians. Stress undermines the supportive aspects of the process of resilience by decreasing motivation and behavioral change actions that allowed for positive adaption (Lines et al., 2019; Van Breda, 2018; Wang et al., 2017). This concern suggested the need for interventions to mitigate stress perception.

Self-Efficacy's Role in the Resilience Process for Soldiers

The Army has strived to develop leadership in soldiers across their career as part of a professional military education program (HQDA, 2017a). It has been suggested that the leadership development programs the Army implements inherently enhance self-efficacy and resilience in soldiers (Darr et al., 2018; HQDA, 2012a). The Army's leadership manual described an impression of a soldier's leadership to the soldiers they lead based upon their application of self-efficacy in all aspects of their military presence (HQDA, 2012). The Army values self-efficacy in their leaders.

Self-efficacy is a vital component in leadership and has been shown to act as an enabler for the leader to make appropriate decisions to accomplish assigned tasks and missions (Boe et al., 2018; HQDA, 2012a; Thompson & Dobbins, 2017). The military has been shown to develop self-efficacy through pre-existing systems that are considered key components in the enhancement of personal perceptions of resilience (HQDA, 2017a; Thompson & Dobbins, 2017). Self-efficacy does not just affect one's resilience, but it also has been shown to mediate how

individuals interact with their environment, this effect on interaction with the environment has allowed soldiers to successfully accomplish their tasks despite associated stressors (Bandura, 1977; Bandura, 1982; HQDA, 2012a; Myrseth et al., 2018). Self-efficacy plays a vital role in the performance of military tasks.

Four components have been described in developing self-efficacy for soldiers, including experiences of enactive mastery, verbal persuasion, vicarious experiences, and both mental and physiological state (Bandura, 1997; Boe & Bergstol, 2017). Regarding development of military skill, one study (n=50) suggested that military cadets found the most benefit in the areas of experience for both vicarious and enactive mastery which correlated well with Bandura's foundational rationale (Bandura, 1997; Boe & Bergstol, 2017). These findings were further supported by a second study that addressed a larger population of cadets (n= 162) and found a positive correlation between self-efficacy and development of military skills through experience that enhanced coping capacity (Myrseth et al., 2018). Thus, the research suggested that successful military operations are made possible by the confidence brought about by increased levels of self-efficacy of individual service members.

The Doctrinal Implementation of Resilience Training in the Army

In 2009 the first concepts of the U.S. Army's MRT program began to come to life in a joint project between the University of Pennsylvania Positive Psychology Department's Penn Resilience Program (PRP) and the United States Army's Comprehensive Soldier Fitness (CSF) program with two primary goals; firstly, to make soldiers' psychological fitness as important of a focus as their physical fitness; and secondly, to change the Army's culture to one that idealizes psychological resilience (Casey, 2011; Doobey et al., 2018; Peterson et al., 2011; Reivich et al., 2011; Zamorski et al., 2018). The MRT program developed around the psychological concepts of

cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT), and the joint efforts of these two institutions helped to operationalize the concepts to relatable experiences for soldiers allowing them to learn not only how to apply each of the 14 MRT curriculum skills but also when to appropriately apply them (Reivich et al., 2011; Simms & Adler, 2017). By implementing these skills across time and developing a culture of resilience, soldiers could, in theory, have reduced incidence and effects of psychological trauma exposure (Dooby et al., 2019).

One of the key components of the Army's CSF program was the development and implementation of the global assessment tool (GAT) (Peterson et al., 2011). The GAT was implemented to gauge soldier resilience by comparing annual outcomes to identify psychological domains of concern to be addressed (Lester et al., 2014; Peterson et al., 2011; Shen et al., 2017; Vie et al., 2016). The GAT was the initial aspect of the MRT CSF2's implementation goal for increasing the Army's psychological resilience culture (Casey, 2011; Lester et al., 2014). Once the GAT was successfully implemented the CSF2 addressed force wide resilience through targeted online training to enhance weaker areas of resilience as identified on the GAT, training and embedding resilience trainers in each unit, and annual training requirements for soldiers on resilience skills (Casey, 2011; Lester et al., 2014; HQDA, 2014a; HQDA, 2015; HQDA, 2017a). Currently, the GAT has been implemented annually and is used to provide soldiers an overarching view and training aids addressing their total fitness, and not just their resilience levels.

Beyond the GAT, the next major step in the implementation of a more proactive approach to psychological resilience training was the selection and training of embedded military resilience trainers (Casey, 2011; HQDA, 2014a; Simms & Adler, 2017). The joint efforts of the University of Pennsylvania and the United States Army resulted in developing a four level

Master Resilience Trainer or MRT training program. The initial level was designed to train service members to embed into units and administer the resilience training curriculum, graduates of this course are referred to as Master Resilience Trainers (HQDA, 2014a; Reivich et al., 2011). The second level of training in the MRT hierarchy was designed to focus on facilitation of practical exercises to reinforce and operationalize resilience concepts in the day-to-day operations of units, these are named MRT-Facilitators (HQDA, 2014a). The third level of the MRT hierarchy was the MRT-Assistant Primary Instructor (API) level of training and was designed for breakout training of larger groups (HQDA, 2014a). Finally, the fourth level of training for MRTs was the Primary Instructor (PI) level of training and was designed to conduct and manage MRT producing courses to train more MRTs to embed across the force (HQDA, 2014a).

The original MRT curriculum consisted of 12 skills that addressed sub-constructs that supported the processes of resilience. These sub-constructs were self-awareness, self-regulation, optimism, connection, character strengths, and mental agility (Vie et al., 2016). The supporting skills for these sub-constructs were adapted from the Penn Resilience Program's skills, they included the Activating Events-Thoughts-Consequences (ATC) model, Hunt the Good Stuff (HTGS), Detect Icebergs (DI), Put it in Perspective (PIIP), Identify Character Strengths in Self and Others (ICSSO), Character Strengths in Leadership (CSL), Avoid Thinking Traps (ATT), Problem Solving (PS), Mental Games (MG), Real Time Resilience (RTR), Assertive Communication (AC), and Active Constructive Responding/Effective Praise (ACR/EP) (Griffith & West, 2013; Hoyt, 2017; Lester et al., 2011; Lester et al., 2011; Lester et al., 2011; Vie et al., 2016; Reivich, 2014). Later, two performance enhancement skills were introduced to the curriculum to address Energy Management (EM) and Goal Setting (GS) which enabled soldiers

to learn to apply resilience to various performance tasks (Harms et al., 2013; Meyer, 2018). These skills were designed to promote resilience through regular training and not to diagnose or treat behavioral health concerns (Hoyt, 2017).

The preliminary implementation of the CSF program's GAT and MRT curriculum were released and tested using Active Duty soldiers (Lester et al., 2011). Between 2010 and 2011 the CSF program and the MRT curriculum were evaluated in three separate reports. The first report examined the GAT profiles of Active Duty soldiers that died by suicide (n= 92), were identified for drug abuse (n= 3,513), or were convicted of a violent crime (n= 132) then compared to the GAT profiles of soldiers that did not display these behaviors (n=791,000); the report demonstrated that all three categories of soldiers with negative behaviors had lower levels of overall perceived resilience (Lester et al., 2011). Lester et al., (2011) in a second report examined positive professional outcomes in soldiers by looking at Active Duty officer GAT profiles for those promoted to Brigadier General (n= 103), promoted early to field grade rank (n= 1,571), selected for ideal duty positions (n= 1,245), or serving in fields requiring professional degrees such as Jurist Doctorate (JD) or Medical Doctorate (MD) (n= 9,278). Each of these groups were compared to peer-level officers. The report demonstrated that soldiers in these areas that represented positive career outcomes demonstrated increased perceptions of resilience when compared to those peer-level officers who were not as professionally successful (Lester et al., 2011). These first two reports were important in that they establish a direct relationship between service member perception of resilience and professional outcomes.

The third report conducted in this time frame examined the effectiveness of the embedded resilience trainer, an MRT, in affecting unit wide perception of resilience over an extended time in four brigade combat teams (n= 12,529) when compared to a control group of

four other brigade combat teams (n= 9,479) (Lester et al., 2011). The study's finding demonstrated that the MRT curriculum was effective in positively affecting areas of social and emotional fitness with special regard to areas supporting unit cohesion such as adaptability, friendship, and connection (Lester et al., 2011). Bandura's (1982) self-agency and self-efficacy research could be tied to the noted outcomes of this report and further supports the role that resilience training plays in enhancing self-efficacy (Bandura, 1982; Black et al., 2017; Cassidy, 2015; Nindle et al., 2018; Nindle et al., 2013). However, the primary focus of the MRT curriculum at that time was built around the soldiers' internal resilience and did not include the other aspects of their life (Griffith & West, 2013; Lester et al., 2011; Vie et al., 2016).

By 2013, the Army's view of resilience changed to represent an understanding that resilience was not just affected by the soldiers' combat exposure, but rather that a soldier's overall resilience was affected by every facet of their life. This led to modification of the Compressive Soldier Fitness program to become the Comprehensive Soldier and Family Fitness (CSF2) program (Vie et al., 2016; Zamorski et al., 2018). The modification to the program brought additional skills and curriculum that included family resilience training and the addition of two performance enhancement skills with supporting resilience curriculum. During this time frame, a fourth and final report on the program and MRT curriculum was conducted. This report built upon the previous in that this report looked at longer term outcomes in similar areas of perception of resilience but further included an examination of the effectiveness of the curriculum to harden and buffer soldiers to decrease susceptibility to mental health or substance abuse concerns (Harms et al., 2013). The fourth report (n=7,230) compared the soldiers of units with embedded MRTs to units without embedded MRTs on their self-reported perceptions in the areas of adaptability, character, friendship, catastrophizing, optimism, and good coping; as well

as examined the soldiers' mental health diagnosis (if applicable). This report found that soldiers in units with embedded MRTs had significantly higher ratings of perception of resilience and were less likely to be diagnosed with a mental health disorder (Harms et al., 2013). This report is significant in that it played a pivotal role in establishing the beneficence associated with resilience training for mediation of mental health concerns by strengthening factors influencing resilience.

Along with the 2013 curriculum changes and additions to the MRT curriculum, the deployment cycle resilience training curriculum was removed from the MRT's level one training and was created as an additional training requirement. This requirement was created to administer the deployment cycle training referred to as Deployment Cycle Resilience Training (DCRT) Train the Trainer courses (Walter Reed Army Institute of Research [WRAIR], n.d.). The deployment cycle resilience curriculum was specifically designed to address pre- and post-deployment skills for soldiers and family member to ensure mental readiness for the challenges of deployment and to inoculate against stressors (HQDA, 2014a; WRAIR, n.d.). These changes were noted for developing more positive outcomes than pre-existing versions of the program such as decreased time of promotion for resilience trained soldiers and decreased criminal behavior (Zamorski et al., 2018).

The final prong of the Army's resilience program consisted of the development of annual training requirements of the MRT curriculum and skills, to ensure soldiers received resilience booster shots (Casey, 2011; Doobey et al. 2019; HQDA, 2017a; Reivich et al., 2011). The original 12 MRT curriculum skills were based primarily on Cognitive Behavioral Theory (CBT) but with the transition to the CSF2 nomenclature of the program came the addition of the two skills built on mindfulness concepts included into the curriculum (Dooby et al., 2019; Reivich et

al., 2011). This inclusion increased the beneficence in resilience outcomes for soldiers combining both CBT and mindfulness as a mixed resilience intervention, which had been shown to have the most beneficence in impact on an individual's psychological resilience (Joyce et al., 2018).

The MRT program had come a long way since its inception in 2009. The foundational research and reports on the CSF program's MRT curriculum demonstrated important correlations and relationships between perception of resilience and both positive and negative behaviors that can affect mental health and performance (Harms et al., 2013; Hoyt, 2017; Lester et al., 2011; Lester et al., 2011; Lester et al., 2011; Vie et al., 2016). While the reports on the CSF program and MRT curriculum demonstrated the effectiveness of the Active Duty soldiers' perception of resilience, there was still a gap in the research addressing the effectiveness of the program on the Army National Guard and Army Reserves (reserve components).

Over the last decade resilience training has seen doctrinal implementation across the Army. Current Army doctrine has a requirement for regular resilience training with the Active Duty component being required to train on one skill a month and the reserve components to conduct MRT training at a rate of one skill every other month (HQDA, 2014; HQDA, 2017a). These doctrinal requirements translate to the Active Duty training all MRT curriculum skills in a year and the reserve components training all MRT curriculum skills in a two-year period. Thus, the reserve components receive resilience training at less frequent intervals than their Active Duty counterparts. This created a concern when considering the differences in perception of stress between the Active Duty and reserve components.

Conflict Around the MRT Program in Contemporary Literature

While the Army's CSF2 program and MRT curriculum have been shown to be effective in the four major reports conducted on the program, the program and curriculum were not without conflict or criticism in some contemporary literature. The major areas of concern in the literature addressed empirical outcomes and study design of the four major reports and bias in supporting research (Brown, 2014; Eidelson, 2011; Eidelson, 2012; Eidelson & Soldz, 2012; Roy, 2013; Timmons, 2013), use of an inappropriate survey to measure resilience (Brown, 2014; Timmons, 2013), ethical considerations in the reports (Alliance for Human Research Protection [AHRP], 2016; Eidelson, 2011; Eidelson & Soldz, 2012), program perception of Army leader (Womack, 2019), a maladaptive process shifting the ownership and focus to the soldier (Smith, 2013), and cost compared to efficacy outcomes (Eidelson, 2011; McDonald, 2016; Roy, 2013). A thorough understanding of these literary conflicts helped to establish a more effective comprehension of resilience research within the military and research gaps.

A large portion of the criticism surrounding the CSF2 program and MRT curriculum addressed the study design and empirical outcomes associated with the primary program studies. Timmons (2013) discussed that a major concern was in the area of study design and empirical data with the population size. While one of the foundational studies conducted on the CSF2 program and MRT curriculum compared GAT data from eight brigade combat teams (four with an embedded MRT and four without an embedded MRT), the units experienced high rates of attrition and less than 80 percent of the collected data was accurate and usable, significantly decreasing the effective population size of the study (Timmons, 2013). Brown (2014) described a concern for the five-point Likert scale usage, as 70 percent of responses in the pre-intervention data was reported as being in the top or second highest position leaving minimal opportunity to

demonstrate improvement post-intervention and suggestion that a large portion of the initial data was not qualified as usable. A third but interlinked concern was that participation was mandatory for the soldiers and this could affect usable responses (Brown, 2014; Eidelson, 2011; Roy, 2013). While these concerns are valid, the mandatory participation and population size components qualified the research as quasi-experimental. The quasi-experimental status of the study was not as high on the Oxford Centre for Evidence Based Medicine's levels of evidence chart as a randomized control study, but still notably high (Oxford Centre for Evidence Based Medicine [OCEBM], 2020).

Regarding the concern for the resilience survey, Brown (2014) and Timmons (2013) expanded the concern for study design in their address of the use of the GAT survey as a measurement of resilience, they cited that the survey was developed in a very short window (90 days) and likely did not have the appropriate amount of time to establish validity and specificity of the survey as a measure of resilience. Further, the GAT survey is 'secret' government property and thusly cannot be evaluated externally (Brown, 2014). Roy (2013) and Timmons (2013) both argued that the selection of researchers and the GAT demonstrate a bias that skewed the research outcomes in the foundational research of the CSF2 program and MRT curriculum. Concerning the areas of GAT survey usage, bias, and potentially skewed data, these arguments are valid concerns for the validity of the effectiveness of the CSF2 program and MRT curriculum as reported in the four foundational reports. Regarding the implementation of the GAT survey, the survey was developed by established professionals in the field of positive psychology and was developed using language common to the CSF program and MRT curriculum to drive accuracy in responses (Peterson et al., 2011). Further, the GAT survey was developed using portions of previously validated psychological and resilience-based inventories, ensuring that all questions

and measures were developed for validity and specificity (Peterson, Park, & Castro, 2011). Finally, to address the concern for researcher selection it is important to understand that the research groups were evaluated and vetted for their appropriateness and expertise in the field prior to their involvement with the CSF program development (Casey, 2011).

Regarding the ethical perspective, the Alliance for Human Research Protection [AHRP] (2016) has listed the CSF2 program and MRT curriculum studies as a current controversy with specific focus on the denial of informed and voluntary consent in the study; as well as their use of the psychological skills to make soldiers resilient to a normal aversion to killing. Eidelson (2011; 2012) and Eiderlson and Soldz (2012) suggested additional ethical concerns for the legitimacy of the program and ethical concerns of blurred lines between studies and training, while also parroting the concern for lack of voluntary and informed consent of participants. While these arguments are of importance, the researchers approached the research without consideration of the effectiveness of ex post facto and quasi-experimental research. Further, concerns surrounding desensitizing soldiers to killing appear to demonstrate a lack of awareness of the role and scope of the MRT curriculum to act as a buffer against suicidality and post-traumatic stress continuum disorders associated with combat (Casey, 2011; Crabtree-Nelson & DeYoung, 2017, Lester et al., 2011; Reivich et al., 2011).

While the foundational research demonstrated effectiveness of the MRT curriculum in promoting healthy behaviors and buffering against negative outcomes, there is concern for implementation. Womack (2019) suggested that company-grade leaders, those working in direct-level leadership roles, demonstrated a generally negative and non-supportive attitude toward the administration of the MRT curriculum. This becomes a concern as a leader's attitude can reflect in their soldiers and shape their implementation of the skills (Womack, 2019). This correlated

well with Smith's (2013) concern surrounding the MRT curriculum's focus on optimism and its potential maladaptive nature regarding psychological recovery post-traumatic exposure.

Considering Womack's (2019) argument that leaders view the optimistic focus of the curriculum in a comical manner and use it to joke rather than to apply to life, there is no psychological adaptation being made. Thus, Smith's (2013) concern supports Womack's (2019) findings in leader's support and attitude toward the curriculum and demonstrated an important criticism of the CSF2 program as soldiers who will not apply the skills will not reap the psychological benefits despite how effective the research shows the program to be.

The final criticism of the CSF2 program and MRT curriculum addressed the cost of the program compared to the outcomes. The initial contract was awarded at \$31.2 million for the development of the CSF2 (CSF at the time) program, and later resulted in the CSF being funded at \$130 million to drive increased emotional fitness and resilience in soldiers (Eidelson, 2011; McDonald, 2016; Roy, 2013). However, the biggest argument is that despite the hefty price tag of the program, the actual outcomes in the areas of both resilience and psychological health have been shown to be one to two percent improvement for units implementing the MRT curriculum compared to those not implementing the curriculum (McDonald, 2016). McDonald (2016) suggested that the one to two percent increases are within the margins of error leading to the discussion on conflict as there may not be statistically significant changes associated with the intervention. Roy (2013) argued that biased methodology could have been used to manipulate the margins reported to inflate efficacy of the program. While these are fair criticisms to consider, it is important to also consider the previous concern addressing the pre-intervention data being elevated (Brown, 2014). If the pre-intervention data was inaccurate then the one to two percent margin of improvement may have demonstrated a deflated outcome associated with the

implementation of the MRT curriculum thus increasing the value of the current fiscal aspects of the program (Eidelson, 2011; McDonald, 2016; Roy, 2013).

The CSF2 program and MRT curriculum were not without their criticisms in the contemporary literature. However, all areas of criticism have been mitigated through thorough examination of the literature and viewing the studies through the lens of quasi-experimental research. The biggest concern brought to light in the contemporary literature was the company-grade leadership's generally negative view of the MRT curriculum (Womack, 2019). However, Womack's (2019) study consisted of an extremely small population (n=10) and was geographically specific to a small area, meaning that the findings of that study may not hold high external validity. The concern cited by Womack is an important consideration as it reflected soldiers' and their units' compliance with the doctrinal requirement for MRT curriculum administration. While criticisms do exist and hold concern in some cases, the majority have been mitigated and do not affect the validity of this study.

Resilience's Effects on Operational Readiness of the US Army

The purpose of this study was not to address the psychological health benefits of the Army's CSF2 program and MRT curriculum; however, it's important to understand the role the program has played in operational readiness of the total force. The Army's CSF2 program and MRT curriculum were initially designed with the purpose of promoting psychological health and resilience in the face of the stressors associated with protracted war efforts that presented with increased rates of diagnosis of post-traumatic stress continuum disorders, clinical depression, substance abuse, and suicidality in warfighters (Casey, 2011; Crabtree-Nelson & DeYoung, 2017, Lester et al., 2011; Nock et al., 2018; Reivich et al., 2011). The notable influx of service

members with these behavioral and psychological health diagnoses after deployment to combat theaters had multiple effects on the operational readiness of the armed forces.

In 2009 an increase in behavioral health concerns in soldiers was noted as surpassing that of the civilian population for the first time in history (Anetis et al., 2019; Nock et al, 2018). Curley and Warner (2017) discussed that behavioral health affects a unit's readiness to deploy through personnel readiness. They went on to discuss that during the height of the war in Iraq some units had been so negatively affected by their personnel readiness that they could not field almost 90 percent of their unit (Curley & Warner, 2017). Soldiers can receive a behavioral health profile associated with any of the diagnosable psychological concerns; however, it's important to note that the soldiers' ability to be deployed with their unit can be affected by the severity of the diagnosis and behavioral health profile they are given (Curley et al., 2020; Curley & Warner, 2017; HQDA, 2019a). Not every behavioral health profile prevents a soldier from being deployable, but those rated higher on the Army's medical readiness system will prevent deployment of the soldier (Curley et al., 2020; Curley & Warner, 2017).

The CSF2 program and MRT curriculum demonstrated the ability to empower soldiers to seek help when needed and prior to reaching exacerbated behavioral health diagnoses; as well as, demonstrated effectiveness in buffering perceptions of stressors and enabling effective coping (Harms et al., 2013; Lester et al., 2011). The stress buffering effect of the CSF2 program and MRT curriculum helped to decrease behavioral health concerns affecting the deployment of soldiers by giving them the ability to not only self-manage but also by empowering them to seek help before the issue becomes clinical (Harms et al., 2013). However, if the curriculum was not being administered to soldiers at the prescribed frequency per Army doctrine (HQDA, 2014; HQDA, 2017a), then the soldiers would not be given the intervention that has been shown to

offer beneficence across multiple psychological health domains there-by negatively affecting operational readiness of the total force (Curley et al., 2020; Curley & Warner, 2017; Harms et al., 2013; Lester et al., 2011).

While the buffering effect of the CSF2 program and MRT program on behavioral health profiles and operational readiness have been shown to be important, this was not the only way that resilience training has positively affected readiness of the force. Recalling earlier concepts of self-efficacy as an outcome of the resilience process as discussed by Bandura (1982), Cassidy (2015), Crane et al. (2017) and Hong et al. (2018), there has been potential to buffer the extensive administrative flags associated with soldiers who have failed to meet minimum standards and compliance in the APFT and ABCP screening.

Resilience Role in Decreasing Administrative Flags

When a soldier has failed to meet the minimum established standards for the either the Army physical fitness test or the Army body composition program screening an administrative flag is placed on their profiles (HQDA, 2016). This flag functions to prevent the soldier from receiving any favorable actions including promotion in rank, attendance of military education schools, assignment to a leadership position, and receipt of tuition assistance through the military (HQDA, 2016). Further, a soldier that has received an administrative flag for having failed to meet APFT and/or ABCP compliance requirements can also have an administrative ‘bar’ to re-enlist placed on their personnel profile and/or can have separation from military service initiated (HQDA, 2012b; HQDA, 2016; HQDA, 2017b; HQDA, 2019d). The ‘bar’ to re-enlist and separation from service can negatively affect the Army’s readiness by decreasing available soldiers for deployment; further, the inability for a soldier to attend the requisite military education schools prevents the soldier from meeting qualifications that may be needed for

deployment, thus further depleting the available pool of soldiers (HQDA, 2014b; Pendleton, 2019). These concerns for soldier fitness and body composition can profoundly and globally affect operational readiness of the nation's military forces.

Administrative Flags by Army Branches

The United States Army has consisted of three components including the Active Duty, the Army Reserve, and the Army National Guard. Both the Army Reserve and Army National Guard are collectively referred to as the reserve components of the Army. There have been notable differences in compliance with the APFT and ABCP between the Active Duty and the reserve components of the Army. Russell et al. (2019) suggested that the reserve components of the Army were more likely to fail to meet compliance with the APFT and/or ABCP resulting in increased administrative flags and decreased operational readiness. The reserve components of the Army were 8.7 percent more likely to fail the APFT than the Active Duty; further the reserve components ABCP noncompliance is 3.65 percent greater than that of the Active Duty Army (Bernstein et al., 2017; DMDC, 2019a; HQFLARNG, 2020; Meyer, 2018; Sih & Negus, 2016). Adding to this area of concern, the National Guard's average APFT and ABCP noncompliance rates have been noted to be 11.7 percent and 4.4 percent, respectively; while the Active Duty had a three percent APFT failure rate and 0.75 percent rate of ABCP noncompliance (Bernstein et al., 2017; DMDC, 2019a; HQFLARNG, 2020; Meyer, 2018; Sih, & Negus, 2016). This finding was of significance in that the United States Army is the largest of the Armed Forces and is the only Armed Force to be distributed evenly between Active Duty and reserve components of the force (DMDC, 2019a). Viewing these data through the lens of both negative soldier outcomes and the effects on the deployable force pool associated with the administrative flag process, these

numbers have become of concern and help to demonstrate the importance of improvement of resilience in the reserve component of the force.

The reserve component of the Army is very different than their Active Duty counterparts. Active Duty soldiers are considered full-time soldiers and reserve component soldiers only work as soldiers one-weekend a month and two-weeks a year, totaling approximately 30 days of rated time in uniform (Feickert & Kapp, 2014). Further, the Active Duty does not have to rely on self-efficacy as much as the reserve component as traditional Active Duty units conduct mandatory group physical training three to five times a week depending on their SRM cycle for deployment and Active Duty soldiers that have failed to meet compliance to the APFT and/or ABCP standards have resources available ranging from additional physical training through the ‘special populations physical readiness training program’ to nutritionists (Feickert & Kapp, 2014; HQDA, 2012; HQDA, 2019d). These available resources to the Active Duty likely lent themselves to explaining the variance in compliance between the Active Duty and the reserve components of the Army.

Understanding the reserve components’ needs for increased self-efficacy based on their elevated administrative flags and the effects those flags have on the force’s operational readiness has become a key point of comprehension (HQDA, 2014b; Pendleton, 2019). Recalling that self-efficacy has been shown to be enhanced as a by-product of improved resilience, established the importance of resilience training for the reserve components (Black et al., 2017; Cacioppo et al., 2015; Cassidy, 2015; Lester et al., 2011; Nindle et al., 2018; Nindle et al., 2013).

Army National Guard’s Resilience Intervention for Administrative Flags

In early 2020 the National Guard Bureau reported that the average failure rate across all 54 states and territories that have a National Guard force was 11.7 percent for APFT failures and

4.4 percent for ABCP failures (HQFALRNG, 2020). The highest rate of APFT failure as of that date was 21.4 percent of a state, territory, or district Army National Guard force, while the highest rate for ABCP failure was 7.6 percent of a state, territory, or district's Army National Guard force (HQFLARNG, 2020). These data were staggering as these percentages were notably higher than the average failure of compliance with Army standards for APFT and/or ABCP in the Active Duty force. Further, each soldier that failed to meet APFT and/or ABCP compliance was at risk of separation and would need to be replaced if separated to maintain readiness of the force. The average cost to replace one of these at-risk soldiers was established to be ~\$180,000.00 (HQFLARNG, 2018), making the operational readiness and fiscal issues of the total force a major concern.

A select set of states' Army National Guard forces initiated a resilience intervention in 2015 to overcome the volume of administrative flagging actions seen across the total force with regard to failed compliance to the Army's standards for both APFT and ABCP (Eads, 2018). While each state's implementation of the intervention had used different naming conventions, the National Guard Bureau referred to the intervention in a more general manner as a 'Wellness Camp'. The Wellness Camp interventions incorporated both the Army's full MRT curriculum skills and exposure to various physical fitness concepts and modalities, all actioned at ~\$80,000.00 per Wellness Camp iteration (Eads, 2018; HQFLARNG, 2018; HQFLARNG, 2020).

The Army National Guard Wellness Camp as a resilience-based intervention incorporated a cadre, or training team, of qualified Army Master Resilience Trainers and Army Master Fitness Trainers that facilitated exposure to appropriate skills and concepts that were suggested by research groups such as Black et al. (2017), Cacioppo et al. (2015), Cassidy (2015),

Lester et al. (2011), and Nindle et al, (2018) to enable healthy behavior change. The instructor to student ratio was 1:5 to ensure quality of training (Eads, 2018). The Wellness Camp was conducted over two-weeks and was considered an immersive training event designed to enhance resilience and self-efficacy in the soldier through exposure to the MRT curriculum. As part of the program, soldiers enrolled into the Wellness Camp had an initial (pre-intervention) and post-intervention APFT assessment and ABCP screening conducted to track progress over the two-week intervention. Conceptually speaking, the Wellness Camp intervention was designed to directly address the process-based view of resilience by addressing the internal character strengths of a soldier and empowering them with the ability to apply skills when the need presented across a spectrum of exposed stressors (Black et al., 2017; Cassidy, 2015; Eads, 2018; HQFLARNG, 2018; Nindle et al., 2018).

The Wellness Camp has been proven to be beneficial in multiple areas including three-year soldier retention rate, cost benefit analysis, and reduction of administrative flags (Eads, 2018; HQFLARNG, 2018; HQFLARNG 2020). These functional areas were vital to operational readiness of the Army National Guard. Soldier retention rates were important to the operational readiness of the force in that all soldiers attending the Wellness Camp intervention were at risk of separation from service and separated soldiers needed to be replaced to maintain deployable unit strengths or risk heavily tasking the remainder of the force (Pendleton, 2019).

Fiscal benefits have been seen regarding the cost benefit analysis of the Wellness Camp intervention. The average cost to replace a soldier separated for APFT and/or ABCP failure was established to be ~\$180,000.00 and by ensured retention of these soldiers from lifting their respective administrative flags, funds have been saved and potentially repurposed. Further, the cost to conduct the Wellness Camp was ~\$80,000.00 for 40-50 participant soldiers and a 10-

soldier cadre (Eads, 2018; HQFLARNG, 2018). From a mathematical perspective the cost avoidance associated with reduction of administrative flags that cause soldier separation from service through the Wellness Camp intervention demonstrated notable cost benefit to the hosting state or territory.

Removal of administrative flags from soldiers assisted in operational readiness of the force. Soldiers with an administrative flag in their personnel file were not permitted to receive any favorable action which includes attendance of military education courses to qualify them for their duty position (HQDA, 2017a; HQDA, 2016). This affected operational readiness by decreasing the pool of available soldiers for duty positions to be deployed and overburdened the qualified pool of soldiers (Pendleton, 2019). The increased deployment of the pool of deployable soldiers increased perception of stress and has reflected in retention rates.

The Wellness Camp intervention has been proven to be effective in the areas of soldier retention, cost benefit, and removal of administrative flags. Eads (2018) described that after tracking participants over a three-year window that the average retention rate for participants was 70 percent. A single Wellness Camp intervention covered 40-50 soldiers per iteration and there have been 10 iterations over the last five years in one state alone, totaling approximately 450 soldiers. With each iteration maintaining 70 percent retention of soldiers this reflected a cost avoidance of ~\$56,700,000.00 for the hosting state or territory (Eads, 2018; HQFLARNG, 2018; HQFLARNG, 2020). These retained soldiers with administrative flags removed from their personnel profiles have gone on to attend duty qualifying and promotion schools which enhanced the available deployable force and decreased stressors placed on the total force.

While the statistics on the Wellness Camp resilience-based intervention demonstrated effectiveness, the mechanism behind this effectiveness is not known. It was the intent of this

study to examine the role that the MRT curriculum played in decreasing administrative flags for APFT and ABCP failure, and the role it played in increasing both perception and application of resilience for participating soldiers. This study conducted an ex post facto quantitative examination on the outcomes of the Wellness Camp to identify the role the MRT curriculum had in the effectiveness of the intervention.

Summary

This literature review addressed a wide range of topics supporting this study. It began with an overview of this study and then moved through the framework of this study, the history of resilience theory, the supporting competencies of resilience, the roles of self-efficacy and motivation regarding resilience, the Army's implementation of resilience training, the Wellness Camp resilience-based intervention, and culminated with a discussion on the appropriate surveys to measure resilience within this study. It was the intent to establish the gap in literature and the need of the ex post facto study to address the outcomes being seen in the National Guard Wellness Camp resilience-based intervention.

This study used pre-existing data gathered by a state's National Guard force on soldiers that were at risk of separation from the Army due to failure to meet doctrinal requirements for body composition and physical fitness. The intervention examined was a two-week Wellness Camp intervention where the soldiers enrolled into the intervention were exposed to various fitness modalities, resilience skills curriculum, and nutritional concepts to illicit positive lifestyle changes. This study conducted an ex post facto pre-post quantitative examination of resilience outcomes to identify if the outcomes of the intervention were resultant of the resilience training or not.

This study was built upon a theoretical framework combining Adult Learning Theory and Resilience Theory. In particular, this study examined the Resilience Theory through the lens of Adult Learning Theory. This was accomplished by leveraging the assumptions and considerations of Adult Learning Theory to enhance the quality of the resilience training to enhance the resilience of the learners (Kenner & Weinerman, 2011; Malik, 2016; McCall et al., 2018; Pierson, 2017; Teaching Excellence in Adult Literacy, 2011). It was the hope of the researcher that by enhancing the translation of resilience materials through Adult Learning Theory the soldiers would be more likely to implement the resilience skills and enhance their physical performance thereby boosting their position along the resilience continuum.

Resilience theory has endured a series of evolutions across its existence. Over a period of five decades the theory has changed from a focus on group vulnerability to an individual process that supports positive adaptation to stressors (Dray et al., 2017; Lines et al., 2019; Masten & Obradovic, 2006; Olsson et al., 2015; Van Breda, 2018; Wang et al., 2017). The modern definition of resilience embodies a continuum for which a person falls upon, the person can be moved along this continuum through training and education in resilience skills that make them more positively adaptable to stressors (Dray et al., 2017; Lines et al., 2019; Van Breda, 2018; Wang et al., 2017). The enhancement of individual resilience along the continuum thereby makes the person more likely to be motivated and to have self-efficacy (Cacioppo et al., 2015; Nindle et al., 2018; Nindle et al., 2013). This process-based continuum definition of resilience was the definition that this study was built upon and was the outcome intent for the soldiers enrolled in the intervention.

Resilience was adapted into the Army in 2011 under the umbrella of the Comprehensive Soldier Fitness program with the intent of changing Army culture so that resilience was as

embedded into the culture as physical fitness (Casey, 2011; Doobey et al., 2018; Peterson et al., 2011; Reivich et al., 2011; Zamorski et al., 2018). The Army needed to implement resilience strategies due to increased psychological health concerns including the suicidality-spectrum disorders and post-traumatic stress-spectrum disorders among other issue areas that affected readiness of the force (Casey, 2011; Crabtree-Nelson & DeYoung, 2017, Lester et al., 2011; Nock et al., 2018; Reivich et al., 2011). The Army's resilience curriculum came about through a partnership with the University of Pennsylvania's Applied Positive Psychology program and resulted in the creation of the Master Resilience Training (MRT) curriculum (Casey, 2011; Doobey et al., 2018; Peterson et al., 2011; Reivich et al., 2011). The Army's MRT program was built upon the six competencies of resilience, which were optimism, self-awareness, self-regulation, mental agility, strengths of character, and connection (Casey, 2011; Reivich, 2011; Reivich, 2014; Reivich, 2020a). This study examined the effectiveness of this curriculum in enhancing the self-efficacy and motivation of the soldiers through training in the six competencies of resilience.

This study was built upon a strong theoretical framework supporting resilience training as an intervention for fitness concerns in soldiers. It was the researcher's opinion that there existed a gap in the resilience literature tying the soldiers' perception of resilience to their application of resilience strategies in fitness performance. This study addressed this literature gap and identified the association of perception of resilience to soldier performance.

Chapter 3: Methodology

The purpose of this study was to discover the associations between perception of resilience, application of resilience, physical performance, and healthy behavior change as it pertains to National Guard soldiers that had previously failed to meet the Army's requirements for the Army physical fitness test (APFT) and/or the Army body composition program (ABCP). This quasi-experimental, ex post facto study examined National Guard soldiers' perception and application of resilience after a two-week resilience-based intervention consisting of the Army's resilience curriculum by using a nonrandomized cohort, ex post facto, quantitative survey design study to identify the most relevant effects on the soldiers as it pertained to readiness of the force. The methodology allowed for a more thorough understanding of the effects of resilience training on soldiers enduring stressors associated with failing to meet the Army's fitness requirements and/or body composition standards. This study's methodology will be discussed in deeper detail as this chapter progresses. The primary components of this chapter include a brief overview of the rationale and purpose of this study, a review of the research questions, null hypotheses, methodology, research design, study population and sample, instrumentation, operational definitions of variables, data collection, and data analysis.

Research Questions

The quantitative quasi-experimental ex post facto survey design was guided by the following research questions:

RQ1. To what extent does a two-week resilience intervention have an effect on perceived levels of resilience when compared before and after intervention in traditional National Guard soldiers who fail to meet the Army's physical fitness requirements and minimum standards?

- RQ2.** To what extent does a two-week resilience intervention have an effect on Army Physical Fitness Testing Scores on record fitness testing when compared to before and after record fitness testing results for National Guard soldiers who had previously failed to meet Army physical fitness requirements and minimum standards?
- RQ3.** To what extent does a two-week resilience intervention have an effect on body composition testing outcomes for record body composition screenings when compared to before and after record body composition screening results for National Guard soldiers who had previously failed to meet Army physical fitness requirements and minimum standards?
- RQ4.** To what extent does a two-week resilience intervention have an effect on the application of goal setting as a performance enhancement resilience strategy when compared to before and after self-reported perception of the strategy for National Guard soldiers who had previously failed to meet Army physical fitness requirements and minimum standards?
- RQ5.** To what extent does a two-week resilience intervention have an effect on the application of emotional control performance enhancement resilience strategies when compared to before and after self-reported perception of the strategy for National Guard soldiers who had previously failed to meet Army physical fitness requirements and minimum standards?
- RQ6.** To what extent does a two-week resilience intervention have an effect on the application of imagery performance enhancement resilience strategies when compared to before and after self-reported perception of the strategy for National

Guard soldiers who had previously failed to meet Army physical fitness requirements and minimum standards?

RQ7. To what extent does a two-week resilience intervention have an effect on the application of energy activation performance enhancement resilience strategies when compared to before and after self-reported perception of the strategy for National Guard soldiers who had previously failed to meet Army physical fitness requirements and minimum standards?

Null Hypothesis

H01. Traditional M-Day National Guard soldiers that attend a two-week Wellness Camp resilience intervention will not demonstrate a statistically significant change in their post-screening perception of personal resilience when compared to their pre-screening resilience perception.

H02. Traditional M-Day National Guard soldiers that attend a two-week Wellness Camp resilience intervention will not demonstrate a statistically significant change in their fitness performance on their next record fitness testing when compared to their initial fitness test scores.

H03. Traditional M-Day National Guard soldiers that attend a two-week Wellness Camp resilience intervention will not demonstrate a statistically significant change in their body composition screening results on their next record body composition screening.

H04. Traditional M-Day National Guard soldiers that attend a two-week Wellness Camp resilience intervention will not demonstrate a statistically significant change in their

application of goal setting performance enhancement strategy of resilience when compared to their pre-intervention baseline ability.

H05. Traditional M-Day National Guard soldiers that attend a two-week Wellness Camp resilience intervention will not demonstrate a statistically significant change in their application of the emotional control performance enhancement strategy of resilience when compared to their pre-intervention baseline ability.

H06. Traditional M-Day National Guard soldiers that attend a two-week Wellness Camp resilience intervention will not demonstrate a statistically significant change in their application of the imagery performance enhancement strategy of resilience when compared to their pre-intervention baseline ability.

H07. Traditional M-Day National Guard soldiers that attend a two-week Wellness Camp resilience intervention will not demonstrate a statistically significant change in their application of the energy activation performance enhancement strategy of resilience when compared to their pre-intervention baseline ability.

Methodology

This study implemented a quantitative methodology to collect data on soldier perception of resilience and their application of resilience strategies to their physical performance. The research methodology was considered quantitative in nature, as the data gathered in this study was entirely numerical and/or ordinal when considering the soldier reported outcomes on the Brief Resilience Scale (BRS) (See Appendix A), Test of Performance Strategies (TOPS) (See Appendix B), the Army Physical Fitness Test (APFT), and the Army Body Composition Program (ABCP) screenings. Quantitative research methodology involves numerical data and traditionally hypothesis driven with the intent of drawing causal inferences and correlations to

accept or reject the hypothesis (Fields, 2018; Jacobsen, 2017; Neutens & Rubinson, 2014). The quantitative design was considered as the hypotheses of this study intended to address potential relationships between variables.

Surveys are a primary source of empirical data for descriptive quantitative research as they reveal what has occurred during an intervention (Jacobsen, 2017; Neutens & Rubinson, 2014). As a tool, a survey allows for systematic data collection from participants in a study (Jacobsen, 2017). The numerical data produced from the Likert-Scales of the closed-ended questions of the surveys in quantitative methodology allow for development of factual outcome data that paints a picture using statistical descriptions allowing researchers to draw relationship values between variables which in turn test the given hypothesis (Jacobsen, 2017; Neutens & Rubinson, 2014). While survey research is not considered to be as high a level of evidence as a randomized control trial, these foundational data points allow for the necessary statistical analysis of findings to test the given hypothesis (Jacobsen, 2017; Neutens & Rubinson, 2014). Further, due to the operational tempo of deployments and geographically distributed nature of the sample of the population of this study, observations and interviews for qualitative methodology were not feasible or appropriate.

Research Design

This study was a quasi-experimental, ex post facto design for outcome comparison. This was the most appropriate research design for this study due to the fact that the target population of soldiers chosen to receive the intervention were selected by their leadership for participation, and that the data gathered for this study already existed in the National Guard Ready & Resilient (R2) Program's archives. This research design was most appropriate to draw conclusions on the effectiveness of the resilience-based intervention.

This study was conducted as a subset of the experimental design, in that there was an intervention being conducted on a population; but there was not randomization of the participants of this study (Jacobsen, 2017; Neutens & Rubinson, 2014). Randomization of this study was not feasible as soldier participation in the intervention was mandated by their chain of command based on their inability to meet the Army's doctrinal standards for fitness testing. Ethically speaking, national funding for this intervention may only be used on soldiers that have an administrative flag placed on their administrative profiles for failure to meet fitness testing and/or body composition screening requirements. The intent of the intervention was to decrease the number of soldiers in the force with administrative flags as they negatively impact the readiness of the National Guard. Soldiers who were not administratively flagged could not be enrolled into the intervention, this removed the ability to randomize this study population into an intervention and control group. For those reasons, this study could not be conducted as a full experimental design. However, while this study's research design was not a true randomized control study or full-experimental design, the Oxford Centre for Evidence Based Medicine (OCEBM) (2020) still qualified this study as a level of evidence being produced as a '2B' level of evidence.

This study examined pre-existing data collected by the National Guard's Ready & Resilient (R2) Program on their Wellness Camp resilience-based intervention. Neutens and Rubinson (2014) described the ex post facto design as a subset of the case-control approach in which cause and effect relationships are examined by looking at previous events and data. This study was conducted on the 87 soldiers that attended one of the two iterations of the two-week Wellness Camp in fiscal year 2019. The soldiers that attended the intervention were required to complete baseline measures of perception of resilience on the BRS, application of resilience to

fitness endeavors on the TOPS, and body composition through an ABCP screening on day one of the intervention. On the morning of day two of the intervention the soldiers completed a baseline APFT for fitness baseline data. Post-intervention data was taken on the final two days of the intervention, where post-intervention data on the BRS, TOPS, and ABCP screening were taken on the second to last day and the final day soldiers were post-intervention tested on the APFT. As both their pretest and posttest self-reported survey data already existed in the R2 program's records and their pretest and posttest performance measures on the APFT and ABCP already existed in the Army's Digital Training Management System (DTMS) records, this study qualified as an ex post facto analysis of secondary data (Jacobsen, 2017).

The prospective study design was most appropriate due to the pre-existing status of the data. Soldiers that attended the fiscal year 2019 Wellness Camp interventions were geographically dispersed across various chains of command, force structures, and deployment status making collection of new data and primary analysis unfeasible at this time. Future-oriented cohort studies are currently unfeasible due to the command structure emphasis and various National Guard state and federal mission sets. Thus, the ex post facto study was the only feasible study currently.

Statistical Considerations

The quasi-experimental, ex post facto design of this study collected ordinal and numeric data from two surveys; as well as, both a fitness test and a body composition screening. The survey-driven data, and performance measures on the APFT and ABCP were used to establish measures of central tendency (mean, median, and mode) for both the pre-intervention and post-intervention time points for this study cohort. The measures of central tendency were descriptive statistics for variables that establish the location of the center of frequency distribution (Fields,

2018; Jacobsen, 2017). While these data are important, they were only the first step in the statistical analysis of the collected data and the verification and acceptance of the hypothesis. The chosen design of this study was both an ethical and appropriate way to gauge the effectiveness of the intervention. In consideration of the appropriateness, ethical-status, and producing level of evidence, this study design was effective in addressing the research questions.

Study Population and Sample

This study examined the effectiveness of the Wellness Camp intervention as a resilience-based intervention in improving soldier perception and application of resilience. The Army Public Health Center's [APHC] (2020) most recent report on the health of the force established a National Guard Bureau [NGB] wide average APFT failure rate of 13 percent and ABCP failure rate of 4.9 percent of the total force across the 54 states, territories, and districts. The state hosting this study had a total force of approximately 9000 Soldiers, of which 12 percent were flagged for APFT and 3.4 percent were flagged for ABCP (APHC, 2020; HQFLARNG, 2020). This translated to approximately 1080 soldiers flagged for APFT failure and 306 flagged for ABCP failure. Of the 1080 soldiers flagged for APFT failure and 306 soldiers flagged for ABCP failure, the intervention has had approximately 500 soldiers that have attended the Wellness Camp resilience-based intervention over 10 iterations conducted from 2015 to 2019 (HQFLARNG, 2020). This established a study population of 500 Army National Guard soldiers that have been administratively flagged for failure to comply with the Army's doctrinal standards of performance and measure in either the APFT and/or the ABCP, that have also attended the Wellness Camp resilience-based intervention.

The sample examined in this study were the soldiers that attended the fiscal year 2019 Wellness Camp classes. These two classes 009 and 010, were conducted in January and June of

2019. Class 009 had n=42 soldiers that completed the intervention and class 010 had n=45 soldiers that completed the intervention. This establishes a study sample of n=87 soldiers. An n=87 sample represented 17.4 percent of the population being studied. Using a sample size calculator, considering a population size of 500 and an available sample size of n=87 this study achieves findings with a 95 percent confidence level and a margin of error of 10 percent (Martin, 2018; Raosoft, 2004).

The n=87 sample was a subset of the population described above. Each soldier enrolled into classes 009 or 010 for fiscal year 2019 had an administrative flag placed on their profile and was at risk of separation from the Army National Guard. The sample consisted of traditional National Guard soldiers that attended drill one-weekend-a-month and two-weeks-a-year in the Summer time, giving a total of 36 days of face-to-face contact with their peers and superiors and 329 days per year where they need to rely on their resilience, self-efficacy, and motivation to make appropriate behavioral actions that support passing the APFT and ABCP to ensure they are not flagged. By studying this sample, the research questions were addressed, and the hypothesis was appropriately tested.

As this was a quasi-experimental study, there was no randomization. Both the population and sample of this study were recruited for the intervention by selection for enrollment and participation in the intervention by their leadership based on their administrative flag status on their profiles. This qualified the sample as a purposive sampling as the soldiers were selected using a non-probability technique based on meeting eligibility criterion (Jacobsen, 2017). Data for this study was obtained from the Army National Guard's historical records. Pre-intervention and post-intervention survey data from the sample was gathered from the National Guard's R2 Program's records. The National Guard's G3 (Operations) Training Division had granted

permission (See Appendix D) for gathering of the sample's performance metrics for the APFT and ABCP from the Army's Digital Training Management System (DTMS). DTMS was the electronic program that soldier performance metrics are required to be maintained in for record keeping.

Instrumentation

The National Guard hosting state's Wellness Camp had implemented two separate surveys in the measurement of both perception and application of resilience. This study used the ex post facto data gathered by the R2 Program from these surveys for quantitative measurement of soldier outcomes. These surveys were the Ohio State University's Brief Resilience Scale (BRS) and the Test of Performance Strategies (TOPS) survey (See Appendices A and B, respectfully). The surveys were selected for their validity, reliability, and consistency in their ability to measure perception of resilience as a single construct (BRS) and their ability to measure the perception of use of specific resilience strategies in fitness efforts (Hidalgo-Rasmussen & Gonzalez-Betanzos, 2019; Lourido et al., 2018; Neves et al., 2018; Okan, 2017; Smith et al., 2008; Thomas et al., 1999; Windle et al., 2011). The quantification of perception of resilience provided the researcher the ability to draw scientific conclusions.

The BRS provides a six-question survey designed to measure resilience as a single construct outcome, rather than by each of the supporting competencies (Hidalgo-Rasmussen & Gonzalez-Betanzos, 2019; Smith et al., 2008; Windle et al., 2011). The scale was designed with alternative positively worded and negatively worded questions using reverse coding on a five-point Likert scale to decrease potential influences of assent (Cantero-Garcia & Alonso-Tapia, 2018; Hidalgo-Rasmussen & Gonzalez-Betanzos, 2019; Smith et al., 2008). The BRS has been described as one of the top three resilience scales in psychometric ratings associated to its

Cronbach's alpha ranging from 0.80 to 0.91 showing notable internal consistency, a test-retest reliability at one month of 0.69 and 0.62 at three months, factor loadings from each question of the scale ranging from 0.67 to 0.91, and evidence supporting both discriminant and convergent validity (Hidalgo-Rasmussen & Gonzalez-Betanzos, 2019; Mamen & Dias, 2016; Smith et al., 2008; Windle et al., 2011). The BRS was considered for this study because of its ability to measure the soldiers' perception of their personal resilience and having a quantitative overview of each soldiers' starting perception compared to their perception of resilience after completion of the Wellness Camp allowed this study to demonstrate the soldiers' movement along the continuum of resilience and allowed the researcher to draw conclusions regarding their adaptations in the process of resilience.

The TOPS survey has multiple versions ranging from 20-64 questions designed to measure performance in competition and practice using seven factors that influence application of resilience to performance, they are goal setting, attention control, imagery, energy management (relaxation and activation), self-talk, emotional control, and automaticity using a five-point Likert scale (Fikretoglu et al., 2019; Hardy et al., 2010; Lourido et al., 2018; Okan, 2017; Thomas et al., 1999). The survey has been used in populations ranging from adolescents to military to Olympians and has been translated to multiple languages while maintaining its validity and reliability in all versions (Fikretoglu et al., 2019; Hardy et al., 2010; Lourido et al., 2018; Okan, 2017; Taylor et al., 2008; Thomas et al., 1999). The TOPS demonstrated moderate reliability with Cronbach's alpha scores for internal consistency of the factors for competition strategies ranging from 0.74 to 0.80 and 0.66 to 0.91 for practice strategies factors, while factor loading by question demonstrated a range from 0.412 to 0.845 with the majority of factor loading scores being between 0.55 and 0.79 (Hardy et al., 2010; Lane et al., 2004; Thomas et al., 1999).

However, later versions also had varied levels of reliability one study reported a reliability of factors ranging from 0.732 to 0.861 while another reported a range from 0.77 to 0.88 by factor, finally one study reported only satisfactory reliability where the Cronbach's alpha scores were all greater than 0.60 (Fernandes et al., 2019; Fikretoglu et al., 2019; Lourido et al., 2018). The TOPS has been shown to have internal, construct, face, and factorial validity in testing application of resilience strategies to competition and practice for physical events (Hardy et al., 2010; Lourido et al., 2018; Saadatifard et al., 2014; Thomas et al., 1999). The TOPS survey was considered for this study as it allowed the researcher to draw conclusions by comparing outcomes by resilience application concept based on the soldiers' pre-intervention and post-intervention scores.

The BRS and TOPS have been demonstrated to be effective in measuring perception of resilience and application of resilience concepts into fitness pursuits (Fikretoglu et al., 2019; Hardy et al., 2010; Hidalgo-Rasmussen & Gonzalez-Betanzos, 2019; Lourido et al., 2018; Okan, 2017; Smith et al., 2008; Taylor et al., 2008; Thomas et al., 1999; Windle et al., 2011). The BRS offers a global view of the soldiers' perceptions of their personal resilience levels and thusly allowed for the researcher to examine their growth and movement along the continuum of the resilience process. The TOPS offers a more resilience skill specific view of the soldiers in the sample of this study, this information allowed the researcher to demonstrate the role the resilience training had in their fitness outcomes. Having these data allowed the researcher to draw significant conclusions regarding soldier outcomes associated with the Wellness Camp intervention.

Operational Definitions of Variables

Perception of Resilience. Dependent variable, measured the perceived ability to recover from stress/stressors. This was measured using the total score outcome for the Brief Resilience Scale (See Appendix A) where the data was pulled from the historical records of the National Guard's R2 Program (Smith et al., 2008).

APFT Performance Score. Dependent variable, measured physical performance in the areas of muscular endurance and cardiovascular endurance through a three-event fitness test with a score established by sex and age brackets per event ranging from 0-100 points based on individual performance and characteristics. Total score for the APFT was given as a numeric value in the range of 0-300, pre-intervention and post-intervention total scores were compared. The events of the APFT were the two-minute pushup test, the two-minute sit-up test, and the two-mile run. This was measured using the APFT, where the data was pulled from DTMS (HQDA, 2012b).

Body Composition. Dependent variable, measured body composition points of Body Mass Index (BMI) value and Body Fat Percentage (BF%) through first establishing height and weight on a BMI table broken down by age and sex brackets. Then performing a girth comparison ratio where males use a two-point (neck and abdomen) comparison and females use a three-point (neck, abdomen, and hip) comparison to establish circumference values and BF%. This was measured using the ABCP screening, where the data was pulled from DTMS. The pre-intervention and post-intervention height and weight (BMI), and body fat percentages was gathered and compared for this study (HQDA, 2019d).

Application of the Goal Setting Resilience Strategy. Dependent variable, measured the ability to apply the resilience strategy of goal setting to develop a plan, self-regulate, and motivate to achieve success in obtaining the goal. Resultant range was an ordinal score from 1-5 on the Likert Scale per question. This was measured using the average reported scores for questions 1, 2, 12, 13, and 19 of the TOPS (See Appendix B). Average scores for this variable were compared against pre-intervention and post-intervention reporting. Data was pulled from the historical records of the National Guard's R2 Program (Gollwitzer & Oettingen, 2011; Locke & Latham, 2002; Thomas et al., 1999).

Application of the Emotion Control Resilience Strategy. Dependent variable, measured the ability to adapt to adversity through decreasing perception of negative emotions and cognitions to enhance performance. Resultant range was an ordinal score from 1-5 on the Likert Scale per question. This was measured using the average reported scores for questions 3, 4, 6, 11, 14, and 18 of the TOPS (See Appendix B). Average scores for this variable were compared against pre-intervention and post-intervention reporting. Data was pulled from the historical records of the National Guard's R2 Program (Thomas et al., 1999).

Application of the Imagery Resilience Strategy. Dependent variable, measured the ability to implement the skill of imagery to enhance physical performance. Resultant range was an ordinal score from 1-5 on the Likert Scale per question. This was measured using the average reported scores for questions 7, 9, 10, and 15 of the TOPS (See Appendix B). Average scores for this variable were compared against pre-intervention and post-intervention reporting. Data was pulled from the historical records of the National Guard's R2 Program (Thomas et al., 1999).

Application of the Energy Activation Resilience Strategy. Dependent variable, measured the ability to self-regulate energy levels as necessary to enhance physical performance. Resultant range was an ordinal score from 1-5 on the Likert Scale per question. This was measured using the average reported scores for questions 5, 8, 16, and 17 on the TOPS (See Appendix B). Average scores for this variable were compared against pre-intervention and post-intervention reporting. Data was pulled from the historical records of the National Guard's R2 Program (Thomas et al., 1999).

Age. Independent variable, measured by number of years the person has been alive and is reported as a numerical value. This study used age brackets for comparative data aligning with the ABCP's established age brackets. These age brackets were used to draw conclusions on effectiveness of dependent variables on sub-groups of the sample.

Sex. Independent variable, reported as a binary Male or Female as listed on the Defense Enrollment Eligibility Reporting System (DEERS) Profile. This study used sex-based brackets for comparative data. These sex brackets were used to draw conclusions on effectiveness of dependent variables on sub-groups of the sample.

Data Collection

The data collected for this study came from pre-existing data sources. The primary data collected for this study was the pre-intervention and post-intervention BRS and TOPS survey results, as well as APFT performance and ABCP screening results. Pre-intervention data that this study used was gathered on days one and two of the intervention, where ABCP screening and baseline BRS and TOPS surveys were collected on day one and the morning of day two consisted of the baseline APFT performance testing. Post-intervention data this study used was collected on days 14 and 15 of the intervention, where ABCP screening and post-intervention

BRS and TOPS surveys were collected on day 14 and the morning of day 15 consisted of the post-intervention APFT performance testing. The BRS and TOPS data was provided from the National Guard's Ready & Resilient Program's (R2P) historical records and the APFT performance and ABCP screening results were pulled from both the Army's DTMS program with permission of the G3 (Operations) Training Division and the National Guard R2P historical records (See Appendix D).

Upon receipt of the pre-intervention and post-intervention survey data from the R2P the researcher grouped the surveys by sex. Once grouped the researcher catalogued the results of each survey by sex groups onto specific Excel spreadsheets separated into pre-intervention and post-intervention outcomes. The Excel spreadsheets was used for input to the IBM® Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 26 to run appropriate statistical measures. The researcher ensured the data was deidentified to ensure study participant protection. The researcher gathered both APFT performance and ABCP screening data from DTMS and the R2P. These data were broken down by age and sex onto the appropriate pre-intervention and post-intervention Excel spreadsheets. The researcher ensured the data was deidentified to ensure study participant protection. The established resilience perception data from the BRS, the application of resilience as measured on the TOPS, the APFT total score data, and the APFT body composition screening results were deidentified and input into Excel spreadsheets in preparation to input data to SPSS. This data was later used to accept or reject the hypotheses. SPSS was used for data analysis.

Data Analysis

This study analyzed secondary data already gathered from the Army National Guard's records for soldiers that attended the Wellness Camp resilience-based intervention. The data

analyzed had been gathered for usage of proof of concept to the effectiveness of the Wellness Camp intervention, Eads (2018) discussed that the participants of the Wellness Camp intervention demonstrated a 70 percent retention rate in the National Guard, and a 31 percent APFT success rate at the end of the intervention (from 2015-2017 iterations), resulting in cost avoidance for the National Guard of \$3,766,000. Further, the 2019 iteration yielded even greater success with iteration one resulting in a 74 percent APFT success rate and iteration two resulting in a 57 percent success rate (HQFLARNG, 2020). These success rates in the removal of administrative flagging actions from profiles resulted in a cost avoidance of \$10,444,000 for the National Guard (HQFLARNG, 2020). These outcomes were the result of the primary data collection. This study conducted secondary data analysis in an attempt to prove what the cause of the success for the initiative was and to see if the cause could be drawn back to the resilience curriculum's ability to enhance resilience, motivation, and self-efficacy toward positive behavioral changes from the perspective of perception and application of resilience with additional attention directed to age bracket and sex specific groups.

The measures of central tendency from the primary data were used to conduct a multi-variable comparison of means, a two-way ANOVA. Both research groups, Jacobsen (2017) and Neutens and Rubinson (2014) described a two-way ANOVA as a measure of comparison between a continuous variable and two factors such as age and sex, the resultant being a *F*-ratio. The *F*-ratio represents the observed differences and/or errors as a test of the hypothesis (Neutens & Rubinson, 2014). The two-way ANOVA makes certain assumptions which include: the population is independent, there is a normal distribution of variables, there are no outliers, and homogeneity exists (Fields, 2018; Jacobsen, 2017; Neutens & Rubinson, 2014). A two-way ANOVA was conducted in SPSS for each of the research questions to establish statistical

significance between the pre-intervention and post-intervention noted data point outcomes and to establish the fit of the linear model to prove and accept the hypothesis (Fields, 2018).

The data used for this analysis was pretest and posttest perception of resilience as established on the soldiers' BRS results. The BRS is the instrument used to address Research Question 1 (RQ1). The BRS has been shown to be effective in gaging perception of resilience as was intended for RQ1 (Hidalgo-Rasmussen & Gonzalez-Betanzos, 2019; Mamen & Dias, 2016; Smith et al., 2008; Windle et al., 2011). A two-way ANOVA was conducted on the comparative data of the pre-intervention and post-intervention BRS scores with specific comparison to both age bracket and sex of the participants to establish acceptance or rejection of the hypothesis of RQ1.

Research Question 2 (RQ2) was addressed by comparing the outcomes from the soldiers' pre-intervention and post-intervention APFT scores. The Army has used the APFT since the 1980s as the standard of establishing fitness for duty and has established the APFT as the test for fitness related administrative flagging actions (HQDA, 2012b; HQDA, 2016). As the APFT was the measure used by the Army for fitness, it aligned with the intent of RQ2. A two-way ANOVA was conducted on the comparative data of the pre-intervention and post-intervention APFT scores with specific comparison to both age bracket and sex of the participants to establish acceptance or rejection of the hypothesis of RQ2.

Research Question 3 (RQ3) was addressed by comparing the outcomes from the soldiers' pre-intervention and post-intervention ABCP screenings. The ABCP screening was doctrinally conducted two-times per year to ensure health of the force and failure to meet the age bracket and sex specific requirements results in administrative flagging action (HQDA, 2016; HQDA, 2019d). As RQ3 addressed participant performance in the ABCP screening, the ABCP screening

results were used as the measure for RQ3. A two-way ANOVA was conducted on the comparative data of the pre-intervention and post-intervention ABCP screening outcomes with specific comparison to both age bracket and sex of the participants to establish acceptance or rejection of the hypothesis of RQ3.

Research Questions 4-7 (RQ4-RQ7) was addressed by comparing the values of specific questions in the pre-intervention and post-intervention TOPS results. These RQs addressed application of resilience techniques including goal setting, energy activation, imagery, and emotion control toward fitness endeavors. The TOPS has been shown to have a Cronbach's alpha of 0.74-0.91 with alpha coefficients as follows by each specific factor to be tested: Goal Setting (0.78), Imagery (0.72), Energy Activation (0.72), Emotion Control (0.72) (Hardy et al., 2010; Lane et al., 2004; Thomas et al., 1999). These data suggested to the researcher that the TOPS was an appropriate measure of RQs 4-7. A two-way ANOVA was conducted on the comparative data of the pre-intervention and post-intervention TOPS scores per factor areas with specific comparison to both age bracket and sex of the participants to establish acceptance or rejection of the hypothesis per RQ.

The two-way ANOVA was used as the statistical test to accept or reject the hypothesis for each RQ. The mean values of two independent variables to a dependent variable per each RQ was compared (Fields, 2018; Jacobsen, 2017; Neutens & Rubinson, 2014). Each RQ was accepted or rejected based on the *F*-statistic and confidence interval produced in the two-way ANOVA as compared to the established *F*-ratio (Fields, 2018; Neutens & Rubinson, 2014).

The researcher established specific mean values for the BRS, APFT, ABCP, and for the following factors on the TOPS: Goal Setting, Imagery, Emotion Control, and Energy Activation. Measures of central tendency values were used in SPSS to conduct two-way ANOVA

comparisons to note statistical significance in findings. This statistical significance was used to accept or reject the hypothesis for each research question based on the comparison of the independent and dependent variables' mean values that were measured.

Summary

This chapter discussed the research methods included within this study that addressed the effects of resilience training on soldier perception of resilience and application of resilience to fitness endeavors to drive positive behavior change in health promoting actions to decrease administrative flags and increase force readiness. The chapter approached each aspect of the methodology to ensure understanding of the appropriateness of the approach described. The methodology described supported a transition to the analysis of the outcomes.

A global view of this study was presented in this chapter. This portion of the dissertation re-addressed the issue of readiness in the force associated to increased administrative flagging actions in the National Guard and the potential benefit that resilience training has played in decreasing those administrative flags due to enhanced resilience (Bernstein et al., 2017; DMDC, 2019a; HQFLARNG, 2020; Meyer, 2018; Russell et al., 2019; Sih & Negus, 2016). From there the chapter moved to a recap of this study's seven research questions and null hypothesis associated to each research question to describe the phenomenon studied. This transitioned to a discussion on the appropriateness of both the selected methodology and research design to ensure the secondary data was accurately tested. A discussion on the prevalence of administratively flagged soldiers in the Army National Guard that attended the Wellness Camp resilience-based intervention defined the population and was used to describe this study's sample and sample size (n=87) due to availability of suitable population within the 2019 fiscal year. In

the establishment of these more general study guidelines, the stage was set for a deeper discussion on the process.

An in-depth discussion on the appropriateness of the two surveys the BRS and TOPS for this study of perception of resilience and application of resilience skills toward fitness endeavors established the rationale for the instruments selected. Both the TOPS and BRS were shown to be reliable and validated for the purpose in which they were used for this study (Hidalgo-Rasmussen & Gonzalez-Betanzos, 2019; Lourido et al., 2018; Neves et al., 2018; Okan, 2017; Smith et al., 2008; Thomas et al., 1999; Windle et al., 2011). With instruments established, variables needed to be defined.

A two-way ANOVA was used to compare mean values noted in pre-intervention and post-intervention data points. The two-way ANOVA looked at the depended variables of perception of resilience, APFT performance, ABCP screening results, use of goal setting, use of imagery, use of emotion control, and use of energy activation and compared those mean scores to the independent variables of age brackets and sex of the intervention's participants. The *F*-statistics that resulted from the two-way ANOVAs allowed for acceptance or rejection of the hypothesis presented within each research question.

The researcher obtained IRB exempt protocol approval through the University of Saint Augustine for Health Sciences (See Appendix C) and approval to use the primary data from the Wellness Camp intervention from the National Guard (See Appendix D). Data storage was protected using multifactor authentication that complies with cyber security recommendations. This study draws statistical support to accept or reject the hypothesis supported for each research question. The primary data was easily collected for secondary analysis. With the methodology's description complete, this leads the discussion to the data analysis of this study.

Chapter 4: Analysis of Data

The purpose of this study was to examine the mean values of pre- and post-intervention performance measures (dependent variables) against gender according to their Defense Enrollment Eligibility Reporting System (DEERS) profile and age bracket (independent variables) for statistically significant relationships and thusly draw conclusions on the effectiveness a resilience-based Wellness Camp intervention using the Army's Master Resilience Training curriculum in changing behaviors around perception of resilience, application of resilience to fitness endeavors, and performance in both the Army Physical Fitness Test (APFT) and Army Body Composition Program (ABCP) screening in traditional M-Day (non-full time) Army National Guard soldiers that have previously failed to meet the Army's fitness and/or body composition requirements. This population was the target of this study as unlike Active Duty (full time) soldiers, the traditional M-Day soldiers are left to their own levels of self-efficacy and motivation when not serving in a uniformed capacity. This quantitative, quasi-experimental, ex post facto, survey-based study sought to measure these performance areas for 87 soldiers that attended a two-week resilience-based Wellness Camp intervention in 2019. The soldiers in the sample completed a pre-intervention Brief Resilience Scale (BRS) (See Appendix A), Test of Performance Strategy (TOPS) (See Appendix B) survey, Army Physical Fitness Test (APFT), and Army Body Composition Program (ABCP) screening, which established the sample's baselines (pre-intervention) for the performance areas measured. Fourteen-days later the sample completed a post-intervention BRS, TOPS, and ABCP; the following morning they completed their post-intervention APFT.

The intervention was designed under the direction of the National Guard's Ready & Resilient (R2) Program's training team. The development team consisted of the R2 Program

Manager, State Resilience Coordinator, State Master Fitness Trainer, State Health Promotion Officer, and other soldiers qualified as both Master Fitness Trainers and Master Resilience Trainers with consultations from Department of the Army Contractors that are Sports Psychologists/Performance Experts (DA Contractors). This study endeavored to establish statistical significance of the beneficence of resilience training in this population for self-efficacy as established by application and perception of resilience when compared to the performance measures.

The data analysis for this study included quantitative evaluation of statistical significance between the pre- and post-intervention data collection time points for each measured event with the intent of establishing relationships between resilience-focused training and soldier performance. Data analysis for this study also included descriptive statistical analysis to determine the effectiveness of resilience training by both gender and age-brackets according to the ABCP age brackets. The contemporary literature surrounding resilience training has demonstrated its effectiveness on enhancing resilience and other positive behavioral changes that support the self-efficacy needed to perform better in both the APFT and ABCP (Black et al., 2017; Cacioppo et al., 2015; Cassidy, 2015; Lester et al., 2011; Nindle et al., 2018; Nindle et al., 2013). However, this research was primarily conducted on Active Duty Army units and/or mixed populations of Active Duty and Reserve Components (Army Reserves and National Guard). Thus, this study addressed a literature gap by examining the effects on traditional M-Day (non-full time) National Guard soldiers and further distinguished itself with a target population of generally lower overall resilience.

This chapter will address the data collected for this study. This will be presented by addressing the data preparation, validity and reliability of the data, a description of the sample,

the results of the statistical analyses conducted, aligning the data to each research question and null hypothesis of this study, evaluation of the findings, and a summary of what the chapter presented. The data will be reported without discussion to allow for unbiased interpretation of findings.

Data Preparation

IRB exempt protocol approval was obtained through the University of Saint Augustine for Health Sciences (See Appendix C) and permission to access soldier data was granted by the Army National Guard's State Training Officer (G3) (See Appendix D). The ex post facto data was collected by the Army National Guard and provided in a de-identified manner to the researcher. Each of the 87 soldiers that participated in one of the 2019 resilience-based Wellness Camp interventions were categorized by gender (according to DEERS) and age bracket according to the ABCP at the time of the intervention. Both their pre- and post- performance statistics in the APFT and ABCP were provided from their Digital Training Management System (DTMS) profile and associated to the same de-identified profile for the researcher. Finally, their pre- and post- intervention Brief Resilience Scale (BRS) and Test of Performance Strategies (TOPS) responses were provided to the researcher in a de-identified manner.

Data from each of the surveys was derived by the researcher according to the established operational definition of each variable. The researcher aligned each participant's total score outcome for both the pre- and post- BRS assessment of perception of resilience to the appropriate de-identified profile. The researcher aligned the averages of portions of the TOPS' questions according to their alignment with each research question. Goal Setting (GS) data was established by averaging the pre- and post- responses from questions 1, 2, 12, 13, and 19. Emotion Control (EC) data was established by averaging the pre- and post- responses from

questions 3, 4, 6, 11, 14, and 18. Imagery (IM) data was established by averaging the pre- and post- responses from questions 7, 9, 10, and 15. Energy Activation (EA) data was established by averaging the pre- and post- responses from questions 5, 8, 16, 17.

These de-identified data were then input to the IBM ® Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 26 for each of the 87 soldiers in the sample. The gender of each soldier in the sample was coded as nominal data and input in SPSS where a 1.00 represented female and a 0.00 represented male according to the soldiers DEERS profiles. The age of each soldier in the sample was coded as nominal data and input in SPSS for the age range of the soldier at the time of the intervention in line with the ABCP age brackets. The ABCP age brackets were categorized as 1.00 representing a soldier in the age range of 17-20, a 2.00 representing a soldier in the age range of 21-27, a 3.00 representing a soldier in the age range of 28-39, and a 4.00 representing a soldier in the age range of 40 plus.

Both the pre- and post- BRS perception of resilience scores for each soldier in the sample were coded as ordinal data and input to SPSS in separate columns with the average score for the questions which represented their score reported on the survey. The pre- and post- averages scores for each soldier in the sample from the TOPS questions listed above for Goal Setting (GS), Emotion Control (EC), Imagery (IM), and Energy Activation (EA) were coded as ordinal data and input to SPSS in separate columns for pre- and post- measures of application of resilience. The pre- and post- total scores in the APFT were coded as ordinal data and input in separate columns in SPSS for each soldier in the sample. The pre- and post- body composition scores were coded as ordinal data and input in separate columns in SPSS for each soldier in the sample. Upon completion of the above data input, this study was ready for analysis.

The data analysis plan was conducted in three phases. First, all study variables were presented using descriptive statistics, such as, means, standard deviation, and minimum/maximum values for continuous variables (Interval/Ratio level), frequencies, and percentages for categorical variables (Nominal/Ratio level). Next, a series of bivariate tests were used to produce inferential findings. Initially, pretest to posttest difference scores were computed by subtracting pretest scores from respective posttest scores. Bivariate tests (independent samples t-test, One-Way ANOVA) were then used to identify if pretest to posttest change scores had a statistically significant relationship with participant characteristics (age and gender). Any characteristics that were related to pretest/posttest change at a statistically significant level ($p < .05$), were included in the third phase of data analysis (multivariate analysis) for each respective dependent variable as a covariate variable.

The third phase of data analysis was multivariate analysis. Specifically, a repeated measures general linear model, was used to model pretest to posttest changes in matched paired scores while controlling for the effect of any covariate variable related to pretest to posttest changes at a statistically significant level in bivariate testing. The model was assessed in terms of overall statistical significance, the significance of individual predictors, and partial eta square (PES) effect size. Final hypothesis testing was based upon the findings of the multivariate analysis. If there were no covariates significantly related to change scores, only the pretest to posttest dependent variable measurements were included within the model. Within the final inferential analysis presented, all test assumptions related to parametric testing were examined, including normality, linearity, and no undue influence of outliers scores. No missing data values were present, so a complete case analysis was performed.

In terms of statistical power, the G*power software indicated that an approximately medium effect size effect (Cohen's $f=.25$) would be detected in a paired samples t-test (2-tailed) examining pretest to posttest score change with power set at .80 and alpha set at .05, using a sample size of 65 study participants. Thus, the current sample of 87 study participants would provide approximately sufficient statistical power for the current analysis.

Validity and Reliability of the Data

Based on the end-state goal of examining the resilience-based Wellness Camp intervention for the potentiality of any statistically significant relationships between both pre- and post-intervention outcomes, two-way ANOVAs were selected for comparison of mean values between pre- and post-test performance measures for statistical analysis of this study's outcomes (Fields, 2018; Jacobsen, 2017; Neutens & Rubinson, 2014). This study made specific assumptions regarding the data and the use of the two-way ANOVA to assess statistical significance of this study findings. These assumptions included the following: an independent population, data normality, equal variance/no outliers, and homogeneity (Fields, 2018; Jacobsen, 2017; Neutens & Rubinson, 2014). The two-way ANOVA's outcomes were considered valid if all four assumptions are met. The following will describe how this study met the requirements for the assumptions and the statistical outcomes for the instruments used.

The ANOVA assumptions can be addressed by examining the sample. The 87 soldiers in the sample all belonged to the Army National Guard, consisted of multiple age ranges, had representation from both genders, and were all administratively flagged for having failed to meet the Army's standards in the APFT and/or ABCP. This diverse sample would help add external validity to the outcomes of this study. Further, the ANOVA assumptions were addressed for the ex post facto data using the Shapiro-Wilk test for normality (Table 1), where any significance

found in normality was then controlled for in a Paired-Sample T-Test, then quantile-quantile (Q-Q) plots figures were produced from the data to demonstrate the compliance with the assumptions. These plots were used to indicate that the probability distribution of the sample adequately represent a common distribution from a population (Jacobsen, 2017; Neutens & Rubinson, 2014).

Table 1

Shapiro-Wilk analysis of data set normality by research question

Measure	Statistic	DF	Significance (P-Value)
BRS Difference Score	0.98	87	0.295
APFT Difference Score	0.99	87	0.428
ABCP Difference Score	0.96	87	0.006 ¹
GS Difference Score	0.97	87	0.029 ¹
EC Difference Score	0.98	87	0.201
IM Difference Score	0.94	87	0.001 ¹
EA Difference Score	0.97	87	0.052

* *P-values are considered significant if $P\text{-value} < 0.05$.*

¹ *indicates that the P-value was significant and a Paired-Sample T-Test was conducted controlling for Outliers.*

Paired-Sample T-Tests were conducted for the ABCP, GS, and IM outcomes due to the Shapiro-Wilk results in Table 1. Table 2 annotates the outcomes of the Paired-Sample T-Tests. All three performance measures' data sets were shown to have no influence of outliers.

Table 2*Paired-Samples T-Test analysis of data set controlling for outliers*

Measure	Mean	SD	t	Significance (P-Value)
ABCP (<i>n</i> =85)	-2.29	1.93	10.95	0.001
GS (<i>n</i> =83)	0.68	0.75	-8.32	0.001
IM (<i>n</i> =83)	0.56	0.54	-9.42	0.001

* *P-values are considered significant if P-value < 0.05.*

The Q-Q Plots offer visual analysis of the data sets for each performance measure. The Q-Q Plots were based on the results of the Shapiro-Wilk tests, and demonstrated minimal outliers. These Q-Q Plots demonstrated the data sets' compliance with the ANOVA assumptions. The Q-Q Plots were arranged in the order of the research questions, as follows: BRS outcomes (Figure 1), APFT score (Figure 2), ABCP screening results (Figure 3), GS outcomes (Figure 4), EC outcomes (Figure 5), IM outcomes (Figure 6), EA outcomes (Figure 7). Note that the Q-Q-Plots for ABCP, GS, and IM demonstrate outliers that were later controlled for and tested against the Paired-Sample T-Test in Table 2. The researcher chose to keep all data inputs in the data set due to the size of the sample and the fact that the Paired-Sample T-Tests results for performance areas showed that there was no undue effect associated to the outliers within the data sets.

Figure 1 Quantile-Quantile Plot for Pre- and Post-Intervention BRS Outcomes

Figure 2 Quantile-Quantile Plot for Pre- and Post-Intervention APFT Scores

Figure 3 *Quantile-Quantile Plot for Pre- and Post-Intervention ABCP Outcomes*

Figure 4 *Quantile-Quantile Plot for Pre- and Post-Intervention GS Outcomes*

Figure 5 *Quantile-Quantile Plot for Pre- and Post-Intervention EC Outcomes*

Figure 6 *Quantile-Quantile Plot for Pre- and Post-Intervention IM Outcomes*

Figure 7 Quantile-Quantile Plot for Pre- and Post-Intervention EA Outcomes

Having satisfied the assumptions of the ANOVA for this study, it was worth addressing the validity of the two instruments used, the Brief Resilience Scale (BRS) and the Test of Performance Strategies (TOPS) survey. The BRS has been considered to have notable internal consistency (Cronbach's alpha ranging from 0.80 to 0.91), test-retest reliability at both one month (0.69) and three months (0.62), factor loading outcomes ranging from 0.67 to 0.91 per question, and evidence supporting both convergent and discriminant validity earning it a rating as one of the top three resilience scales in psychometric ratings (Hidalgo-Rasmussen & Gonzalez-Betanzos, 2019; Mamen & Dias, 2016; Smith et al., 2008; Windle et al., 2011). The TOPS has been considered to have moderate to satisfactory reliability and internal consistency with Cronbach's alpha ranging from 0.74 to 0.80 for competition strategies and 0.66 to 0.91 for practice strategies and factor loading ranging between 0.412 to 0.845 with the majority of scores falling between 0.55 and 0.79 (Fernandes et al., 2019; Fikretoglu et al., 2019; Hardy et al., 2010; Lane et al., 2004; Lourido et al., 2018; Thomas et al., 1999). Both instruments were considered to be reliable and valid for the respective goals of this study.

Descriptive Statistics

The subjects in this study consisted of 87 non-Active Duty Army National Guard soldiers that were selected by their chain of command to attend a two-week resilience-based Wellness Camp intervention conducted by the Army National Guard's Ready & Resilient (R2) Program. All 87 soldiers in the sample were enrolled into the intervention based on meeting the criteria of having an administrative flag placed on their personnel file for failure to meet the Army's minimum standards for the APFT and/or ABCP. As part of the intervention pre-intervention tests were completed for the sample, participants completed the training, and then post-intervention testing was completed.

Table 3 presents a descriptive analysis of categorical study participant characteristics. Data indicated that the sample was about three-quarter male ($n=63$; 72.4%) and one-quarter female ($n=24$; 27.6%). The sample was predominantly in the age bracket of 21-27 years old ($n=45$; 51.7%), with representation in the other age brackets as follows: 17-20 ($n=16$; 18.4%), 21-27 ($n=20$; 23.0%), and 40+ ($n=6$; 6.9%).

Table 3

Descriptive Analysis of Categorical Demographic Characteristics (n=87)

Variable	N	%
Gender		
Male	63	72.4
Female	24	27.6
Age Bracket		
17-20	16	18.4
21-27	45	51.7
28-39	20	23.0
40+	6	6.9

Table 4 presented a descriptive analysis of this study variables, including study pretest and posttest scores by performance area. Data indicated that the mean outcomes were as follows

per performance area: BRS pretest score was 22.14 ($SD=4.47$, $MIN/MAX=6.00-30.00$) and posttest score was 23.90 ($SD=3.40$, $MIN/MAX=12.00-30.00$); APFT pretest score was 141.41 ($SD=39.80$, $MIN/MAX=48.00-209.00$) and posttest score was 179.55 ($SD=40.08$, $MIN/MAX=0.00-242.00$); ABCP pretest score was 25.31 ($SD=7.70$, $MIN/MAX=5.00-55.00$) and posttest score was 22.85 ($SD=7.61$, $MIN/MAX=51.00-55.00$); GS pretest score was 3.15 ($SD=0.75$, $MIN/MAX=1.60-5.00$) and posttest score was 3.87 ($SD=0.67$, $MIN/MAX=2.20-5.00$); EC pretest score was 3.09 ($SD=0.46$, $MIN/MAX=1.43-4.00$) and posttest score was 3.40 ($SD=0.45$, $MIN/MAX=2.29-5.00$); IM pretest score was 2.65 ($SD=0.53$, $MIN/MAX=1.25-3.80$) and posttest score was 3.30 ($SD=0.46$, $MIN/MAX=2.25-4.75$); and EA pretest score was 3.06 ($SD=0.58$, $MIN/MAX=1.50-4.25$) and posttest score was 3.59 ($SD=0.51$, $MIN/MAX=2.50-5.00$).

Thus, the average study participant (via the pre/post difference score) evidenced the following changes of 1.76 ($SD=4.95$, $MIN/MAX=-9.00-12.00$) from pretest to posttest for BRS; 38.14 ($SD=28.19$, $MIN/MAX=-51.00-118.00$) from pretest to posttest for APFT; -2.46 ($SD=2.20$, $MIN/MAX=-10.00-2.00$) from pretest to posttest for ABCP; 0.72 ($SD=0.91$, $MIN/MAX=-2.60-3.00$) from pretest to posttest for GS; 0.28 ($SD=0.51$, $MIN/MAX=-0.72-1.70$) from pretest to posttest for EC; 0.65 ($SD=0.68$, $MIN/MAX=-0.81-3.00$) from pretest to posttest for IM; and 0.53 ($SD=0.68$, $MIN/MAX=-1.00-2.00$) from pretest to posttest for EA. The distribution of all the scores were approximately normal as the skewness and kurtosis were not approximately two times each respective standard error of each.

Table 4*Descriptive Analysis of Pretest and Posttest Scores (n=87)*

Variable	M (SD)	Minimum/ Maximum	Skew (SE)	Kurtosis (SE)
<i>Brief Resilience Scale (BRS)</i>				
Pretest Scores	22.14 (4.47)	6.00-30.00	-0.48 (0.26)	1.21 (0.51)
Posttest Scores	23.90 (3.40)	12.00-30.00	-0.21 (0.26)	0.55 (0.51)
Pre/Post Difference Scores	1.76 (4.95)	-9.00-12.00	-0.21 (0.26)	-0.52 (0.51)
<i>Army Physical Fitness Test (APFT)</i>				
Pretest Scores	141.41 (39.80)	48.00-209.00	-0.47 (0.26)	-0.27 (0.51)
Posttest Scores	179.55 (40.08)	0.00-242.00	-1.74 (0.26)	4.77 (0.51)
Pre/Post Difference Scores	38.14 (28.19)	-51.00-118.00	0.06 (.26)	0.96 (0.51)
<i>Army Body Composition Program (ABCP)</i>				
Pretest Scores	25.31 (7.70)	5.00-55.00	0.63 (0.26)	1.90 (0.51)
Posttest Scores	22.85 (7.61)	5.00-51.00	0.77 (0.26)	1.72 (0.51)
Pre/Post Difference Scores	-2.46 (2.20)	-10.00-2.00	-0.60 (0.26)	1.20 (0.51)
<i>Goal Setting (GS)</i>				
Pretest Scores	3.15 (0.75)	1.60-5.00	0.35 (0.26)	0.09 (0.51)
Posttest Scores	3.87 (0.67)	2.20-5.00	-0.36 (.26)	0.08 (0.51)
Pre/Post Difference Scores	0.72 (0.91)	-2.60-3.00	-0.13 (.26)	1.60 (0.51)
<i>Emotion Control (EC)</i>				
Pretest Scores	3.09 (0.46)	1.43-4.00	-0.82 (0.26)	1.57 (0.51)
Posttest Scores	3.40 (0.45)	2.29-5.00	0.87 (0.26)	2.53 (0.51)
Pre/Post Difference Scores	0.28 (0.51)	-0.72-1.70	0.43 (0.26)	0.12 (0.51)

Imagery (IM)

Pretest Scores	2.65 (0.53)	1.25-3.80	-0.34 (0.26)	0.12 (0.51)
Posttest Scores	3.30 (0.46)	2.25-4.75	0.21 (0.26)	0.64 (0.51)
Pre/Post Difference Scores	0.65 (0.68)	-0.81-3.00	0.87 (0.26)	1.65 (0.51)

Energy Activation (EA)

Pretest Scores	3.06 (0.58)	1.50-4.25	-0.29 (0.26)	-0.15 (0.51)
Posttest Scores	3.59 (0.51)	2.50-5.00	0.37 (0.26)	0.09 (0.51)
Pre/Post Difference Scores	0.53 (0.68)	-1.00-2.00	0.22 (0.26)	0.03 (0.51)

Note: SD= Standard Deviation.

The Headquarters, Department of the Army (HQDA) established an APFT score range of 0-300 based on 100-point scales per three fitness events: pushup, sit-up, and two-mile run. Soldiers were required to score a minimum of 180 with at least 60 points per event to be considered passing (HQDA, 2012b). The closer the score is to 300, the better the physical performance of the soldier. According to HQDA (2019d), the ABCP produces body fat percentages based on BMI (height and weight) and girth measurement comparisons, soldiers were gauged on their personal body composition at or below the allowable levels per an age-based scale, as follows: Age bracket 17-20 (Male= 20%; Female=30%), age bracket 21-27 (Male=22%; Female=32%), age bracket 28-39 (Male=24%; Female=34%), and age bracket 40+ (Male=26%; Female=36%). Overall, the lower the overall outcomes of the ABCP screening the better the outcome.

The BRS consists of six-questions measured on a 5-point Likert scale, with the soldiers' total scores being averaged for perception of resilience. The following are subcomponents of the TOPS survey and are broken out by question number as follows: IM: 7, 9, 10, 15; EA: 5, 8, 16, 17; GS: 1, 2, 12, 13, 19; EC: 3, 4, 6, 11, 14. Each outcome mean score was a product of the

average of each questions' 5-point Likert score results as categorized above. The higher the mean scores in each of these areas the more enhanced the soldiers' perception of their resilience, use of IM, use of EA, use of GS, and use of EC is, respectively.

Table 5 presents an independent-samples t-test analysis of pre/post change scores by demographic characteristics. Data indicated that pre/post change scores were not significantly related to gender nor age bracket, as follows: BRS gender, $t(85)=-1.50$, $p=.14$, age bracket, $F(3,86)=-0.44$, $p=.72$; APFT gender, $t(85)=-0.69$, $p=.49$, age bracket, $F(3,86)=1.46$, $p=.23$; ABCP gender, $t(85)=-0.11$, $p=.91$, age bracket, $F(3,86)=2.40$, $p=.07$; GS gender, $t(81)=-0.41$, $p=.68$, age bracket, $F(3,83)=0.31$, $p=.82$; EC gender, $t(85)=0.63$, $p=.53$, age bracket, $F(3,86)=1.58$, $p=.20$; IM gender, $t(85)=0.10$, $p=.55$, age bracket, $F(3,86)=0.25$, $p=.86$; EA gender, $t(85)=0.83$, $p=.41$, age bracket, $F(3,86)=1.27$, $p=.29$. These data demonstrated that neither gender nor age had a statistically significant relationship to this study's findings.

Table 5

Independent Samples T-Test and one-way ANOVA Analysis of Pre/Post Change Scores by Demographic Characteristics (n=87)

Variable	n	M (SD)	t/F(df)	p
BRS				
Gender			-1.50 (85)	0.14
Male	63	1.27 (4.92)		
Female	24	3.04 (4.89)		
Age Bracket			-0.44 (3,86)	0.72
17-20	16	2.06 (5.45)		
21-27	45	1.27 (5.05)		
28-39	20	2.75 (5.01)		
40+	6	1.33 (4.95)		

APFT

Gender			-0.69 (85)	0.49
Male	63	36.84 (25.17)		
Female	24	41.54 (35.30)		
Age Bracket			1.46 (3,86)	0.23
17-20	16	44.00 (23.22)		
21-27	45	41.00 (33.00)		
28-39	20	26.95 (21.08)		
40+	6	38.33 (9.44)		

ABCP

Gender			-0.11 (85)	0.91
Male	63	-2.48 (2.11)		
Female	24	-2.42 (2.47)		
Age Bracket			2.40 (3,86)	0.07
17-20	16	-1.50 (1.90)		
21-27	45	-2.84 (2.45)		
28-39	20	-2.75 (1.65)		
40+	6	-1.17 (1.60)		

GS

Gender			-0.41 (81)	0.68
Male	63	0.66 (0.74)		
Female	24	0.74 (0.80)		
Age Bracket			0.31 (3,83)	0.82
17-20	16	0.67 (0.73)		
21-27	45	0.67 (0.82)		
28-39	20	0.64 (0.67)		
40+	6	0.97 (0.75)		

EC

Gender			0.63 (85)	0.53
Male	63	0.30 (0.52)		
Female	24	0.23 (0.48)		
Age Bracket			1.58 (3,86)	0.20
17-20	16	0.26 (0.40)		
21-27	45	0.20 (0.43)		
28-39	20	0.49 (0.62)		

40+	6	0.32 (0.80)		
<i>IM</i>				
<i>Gender</i>			0.10 (85)	0.55
Male	63	0.62 (0.68)		
Female	24	0.72 (0.66)		
<i>Age Bracket</i>			0.25 (3,86)	0.86
17-20	16	0.69 (0.85)		
21-27	45	0.61 (0.62)		
28-39	20	0.74 (0.73)		
40+	6	0.53 (0.45)		
<i>EA</i>				
<i>Gender</i>			0.83 (85)	0.41
Male	63	0.57 (0.65)		
Female	24	0.43 (0.76)		
<i>Age Bracket</i>			1.27 (3,86)	0.29
17-20	16	0.28 (0.68)		
21-27	45	0.52 (0.70)		
28-39	20	0.70 (0.68)		
40+	6	0.71 (0.46)		

Results

This study was conducted as a quantitative, quasi-experimental, ex post facto, survey-based study that investigated the effectiveness or ineffectiveness of the two-week resilience-based Wellness Camp, which presented the Army's Master Resilience Training (MRT) curriculum, in enhancing soldier performance in the APFT and ABCP; as well as, enhancing their self-efficacy as measured by perception of overall resilience, application of the skills of IM, EA, GS, and EC. The Wellness Camp intervention, for which this study examined, belongs to a state whose Army National Guard's Ready & Resilient (R2) Program has been repeatedly

recognized by the National Guard Bureau (NGB) for their performance outcomes and implementation of the resilience curriculum (Eads, 2018). Each of the Army National Guard's R2 Program's instructors were formally trained by the Army as a Master Resilience Trainer (MRT) and/or Master Fitness Trainer (MFT) and have been considered some of the top performers in these fields within their state (Eads, 2018). Both iterations of the Wellness Camp also had Army Sports Psychologist/Performance Expert Civilian Contractor support. Each member of the training team was given orientation training on the movement standards, testing/measuring sites, and grading scales for both the APFT and ABCP to ensure inter-rater and intra-rater reliability of pre- and post-intervention testing.

The selected measures of performance (APFT and ABCP) along with the selected instruments for measuring both resilience and application of resilience strategies to fitness endeavors created a valid comparison of both pre-intervention performance and outcomes and post-intervention performance and outcomes. To examine the relationship between the intervention and pre- and post-intervention outcomes the selected measurements and instruments enabled a method to test the hypotheses established. Two-way ANOVAs conducted via SPSS with a confidence level of 95% were selected to investigate these points of potential statistically significant relationships between the resilience-based intervention and the outcomes.

Table 6 presents a repeated measures general linear model examining pre- to post-intervention changes in mean scores. Multivariate analysis indicated, that while including study participant age as a covariate, changes in pretest to post scores remained statistically significant for the following: BRS $F(1, 86)=10.99, p<.0001$; APFT $F(1, 86)=159.27, p<.0001$; ABCP $F(1, 86)=108.99, p<.0001$; GS $F(1, 86)=54.53, p<.0001$; EC $F(1, 86)=27.15, p<.0001$; IM $F(1, 86)=80.25, p<.0001$; and EA $F(1, 86)=52.77, p<.0001$. Furthermore, the analysis evidenced the

following Partial Eta Squared effect sizes according to the G*Power analysis completed earlier: BRS medium effect size of .11; APFT large effect size of .65; ABCP large effect size of .56; GS large effect size of .39; EC medium effect size of .24; IM large effect size of .48; and EA large effect size of .38. Table 6 presents these findings by area of measure as an overview, then these are presented below by research question and null hypothesis.

Table 6

Repeated Measures General Model Examining Pretest to Posttest Score Changes While Controlling for the Effect of Study Participant Age (n=87)

Timepoint	n	M (SD)	F(df)	p	PES¹
<i>BRS</i>			10.99 (1, 86)	0.001	0.11¹
Pretest	87	22.14 (4.47)			
Posttest	87	23.90 (0.00)			
<i>APFT</i>			159.27 (1, 86)	0.001	0.65²
Pretest	87	141.41 (39.80)			
Posttest	87	179.55 (40.08)			
<i>ABCP</i>			108.92 (1, 86)	0.001	0.56²
Pretest	87	25.31 (7.70)			
Posttest	87	22.85 (7.61)			
<i>GS</i>			54.53 (1, 86)	0.001	0.39²
Pretest	87	3.15 (0.75)			
Posttest	87	3.88 (0.67)			
<i>EC</i>			27.15 (1, 86)	0.001	0.24¹
Pretest	87	3.10 (0.46)			
Posttest	87	3.38 (0.45)			
<i>IM</i>			80.25 (1, 86)	0.001	0.48²
Pretest	87	2.65 (0.53)			
Posttest	87	3.30 (0.46)			

EA			52.77 (1, 86)	0.001	0.38²
Pretest	87	3.06 (0.58)			
Posttest	87	3.59 (0.51)			

¹Partial Eta Squared Effect Size of 0.09 is a medium effect

²Partial Eta Squared Effect Side of 0.25 is a large effect

Initial examination and comparison of the pre- and post-intervention data was conducted using a Multivariate analysis. This demonstrated that each mean value finding per performance area had a statistically significant change ($p < 0.001$) and directionality of the findings were in the preferred direction. The magnitude of change will be discussed within each research question's section under the PES findings according to the statistical annotation in Table 6.

Research Question 1/Null Hypothesis 1

- RQ1: To what extent does a two-week resilience intervention have an effect on perceived levels of resilience when compared before and after intervention in traditional National Guard soldiers who fail to meet the Army's physical fitness requirements and minimum standards?
- H₀₁: Traditional M-Day National Guard soldiers that attend a two-week Wellness Camp resilience intervention will not demonstrate a statistically significant change in their post-screening perception of personal resilience when compared to their pre-screening resilience perception.

This study's first research question examined the potential statistically significant relationship attendance of the two-week resilience-based Wellness Camp intervention had with soldier perception of their resilience as measured on the BRS when compared between pre- and post-intervention evaluation. This investigated the effectiveness or ineffectiveness of the intervention if any statistically significant relationship existed between the sample's reported

perceptions of resilience from pre- to post-intervention. A two-way ANOVA set for a 95% confidence interval was conducted on the data sets of both pre- and post-intervention to examine the relationship and effect size using PES. If the data were found to have a statistically significant relationship ($p < 0.05$) then a one-way ANOVA was conducted to look for statistically significant differences between age bracket variables on the outcomes and an Independent Sample T-Test was conducted to look for statistically significant differences between the gender variable on the outcomes. Normality testing was also conducted to establish data set normality.

Data analysis indicated a statistically significant relationship was found between the pre- and post-intervention difference measure of 1.76 ($SD=4.95$), $F(1,86)=10.99$, $p < 0.001$, and evidenced a medium effect size ($PES=0.113$) for perception of resilience between the pre- and post-intervention data sets. A one-way ANOVA was conducted to look for differences between age brackets on the findings and no statistically significant differences were found between age brackets on reported outcomes ($F(3,86)=0.44$, $p=0.72$). Additionally, an Independent Samples T-Test was conducted on the data set to look for differences based on gender on the outcomes; the Levene's Test for Equality of Variance did not find any statistically significant differences ($F=0.01$, $p=0.92$) with the overall T-Test ($t(85)=-1.50$, $p=0.14$). A Shapiro-Wilk's test for normality was not statistically significant for normality on outcomes ($p=0.30$). Table 7 displays the findings of the two-way ANOVA for RQ1.

Table 7*Brief Resilience Scale (BRS) two-way ANOVA statistics*

Effect	Value	F	Hyp DF	Error DF	P-Value	PES	Observed Power
<i>Pillar's Trace</i>	.113	10.988	1.000	86.000	.001	.113	.906
<i>Wilks' Lambda</i>	.887	10.988	1.000	86.000	.001	.113	.906
<i>Hotelling's Trace</i>	.128	10.988	1.000	86.000	.001	.113	.906
<i>Roy's Largest Root</i>	.128	10.988	1.000	86.000	.001	.113	.906

After analysis of the pre- and post-intervention data sets for the BRS; the researcher rejected the null hypothesis. There was a statistically significant relationship between the intervention and post-intervention perception of resilience.

Research Question 2/Null Hypothesis 2

- RQ2: To what extent does a two-week resilience intervention have an effect on Army Physical Fitness Testing Scores on record fitness testing when compared to before and after record fitness testing results for National Guard soldiers who had previously failed to meet Army physical fitness requirements and minimum standards?
- H₀₂: Traditional M-Day National Guard soldiers that attend a two-week Wellness Camp resilience intervention will not demonstrate a statistically significant change in their fitness performance on their next record fitness testing when compared to their initial fitness test scores.

This study's second research question examined the potential statistical significance relationship attendance of the two-week resilience-based Wellness Camp intervention had with soldier performance in the APFT when compared between pre- and post-intervention evaluation. This investigated the effectiveness or ineffectiveness of the intervention if any statistically significant relationship existed between the sample's performance scores from pre- and post-intervention. A two-way ANOVA set for a 95% confidence interval was conducted on the data sets of both pre- and post-intervention to examine the relationship and effect size using PES. If the data were found to have a statistically significant relationship ($p < 0.05$) then a one-way ANOVA was conducted to look for statistically significant differences between age bracket variables on the outcomes and an Independent Sample T-Test was conducted to look for statistically significant differences between the gender variable on the outcomes. Normality testing was also conducted to establish data set normality.

Data analysis indicated a statistically significant relationship was found between the pre- and post-intervention difference score of 38.14 ($SD=28.19$), $F(1,86)=159.27$, $p < 0.001$, and evidenced a large effect size ($PES=0.649$) APFT performance between the pre- and post-intervention data sets. A one-way ANOVA was conducted to look for differences between age brackets on the findings and no statistically significant differences were found between age brackets on reported outcomes ($F(3,86)=1.46$, $p=0.23$). Additionally, an Independent Samples T-Test was conducted on the data set to look for differences based on gender on the outcomes; the Levene's Test for Equality of Variance did not find any statistically significant differences ($F=1.83$, $p=0.18$) with the overall T-Test ($t(85)=-0.69$, $p=0.49$). A Shapiro-Wilk's test for normality was not statistically significant for normality on outcomes ($p=0.43$). Table 8 displays the findings of the two-way ANOVA for RQ2.

Table 8

Army Physical Fitness Test (APFT) two-way ANOVA statistics

Effect	Value	F	Hyp DF	Error DF	P-Value	PES	Observed Power
<i>Pillar's Trace</i>	.649	159.269	1.000	86.000	<0.001	.649	1.000
<i>Wilks' Lamba</i>	.351	159.269	1.000	86.000	<0.001	.649	1.000
<i>Hotelling's Trace</i>	1.852	159.269	1.000	86.000	<0.001	.649	1.000
<i>Roy's Largest Root</i>	1.852	159.269	1.000	86.000	<0.001	.649	1.000

After analysis of the pre- and post-intervention data sets for APFT performance; the researcher rejected the null hypothesis. There was a statistically significant relationship between the intervention and post-intervention APFT performance.

Research Question 3/Null Hypothesis 3

- RQ3: To what extent does a two-week resilience intervention have an effect on body composition testing outcomes for record body composition screenings when compared to before and after record body composition screening results for National Guard soldiers who had previously failed to meet Army physical fitness requirements and minimum standards?
- H₀₃: Traditional M-Day National Guard soldiers that attend a two-week Wellness Camp resilience intervention will not demonstrate a statistically significant change in their body composition screening results on their next record body composition screening.

This study's third research question examined the potential statistical significance relationship attendance of the two-week resilience-based Wellness Camp intervention had with soldier performance in the ABCP when compared between pre- and post-intervention evaluation. This investigated the effectiveness or ineffectiveness of the intervention if any statistically significant relationship existed between the sample's performance scores from pre- and post-intervention. A two-way ANOVA set for a 95% confidence interval was conducted on the data sets of both pre- and post-intervention to examine the relationship and effect size using PES. If the data were found to have a statistically significant relationship ($p < 0.05$) then a one-way ANOVA was conducted to look for statistically significant differences between age bracket variables on the outcomes and an Independent Sample T-Test was conducted to look for statistically significant differences between the gender variable on the outcomes. Normality testing was also conducted to establish data set normality.

Data analysis indicated a statistically significant relationship was found between the pre- and post-intervention difference result of -2.46 ($SD=2.20$), $F(1,86)=108.92$, $p < 0.001$, and evidenced a large effect size ($PES=0.559$) for ABCP outcomes between the pre- and post-intervention data sets. A one-way ANOVA was conducted to look for differences between age brackets on the findings and no statistically significant differences were found between age brackets on reported outcomes ($F(3,86)=2.40$, $p=0.07$). Additionally, an Independent Samples T-Test was conducted on the data set to look for differences based on gender on the outcomes; the Levene's Test for Equality of Variance did not find any statistically significant differences ($F=2.45$, $p=0.12$) with the overall T-Test ($t(85)=-0.69$, $p=0.91$). A Shapiro-Wilk's test for normality was statistically significant for normality on outcomes ($p=0.01$); when controlling for outliers ($n=85$) a Paired-Sample T-Test resulted in a difference score of 2.29 ($SD=1.93$),

$t(84)=10.95, p<0.001$ showing despite the normality outliers the data set's outcomes still resulted in a statistically significant relationship to the intervention. Table 9 displays the findings of the two-way ANOVA for RQ3.

Table 9

Army Body Composition Program (ABCP) two-way ANOVA statistics

Effect	Value	F	Hyp DF	Error DF	P-Value	PES	Observed Power
<i>Pillar's Trace</i>	.559	108.924	1.000	86.000	<0.001	.559	1.000
<i>Wilks' Lamba</i>	.441	108.924	1.000	86.000	<0.001	.559	1.000
<i>Hotelling's Trace</i>	1.267	108.924	1.000	86.000	<0.001	.559	1.000
<i>Roy's Largest Root</i>	1.267	108.924	1.000	86.000	<0.001	.559	1.000

After analysis of both the pre- and post-intervention data sets for the ABCP screening results; the researcher rejected the null hypothesis. There was a statistically significant relationship between the intervention and post-intervention ABCP screening outcomes.

Research Question 4/Null Hypothesis 4

- RQ4: To what extent does a two-week resilience intervention have an effect on the application of goal setting as a performance enhancement resilience strategy when compared to before and after self-reported perception of the strategy for National Guard soldiers who had previously failed to meet Army physical fitness requirements and minimum standards?
- H₀₄: Traditional M-Day National Guard soldiers that attend a two-week Wellness Camp resilience intervention will not demonstrate a statistically significant change

in their application of goal setting performance enhancement strategy of resilience when compared to their pre-intervention baseline ability.

This study's fourth research question examined the potential statistical significance relationship attendance of the two-week resilience-based Wellness Camp intervention had with soldier application of the Goal Setting (GS) resilience strategy when compared between pre- and post-intervention evaluation. This investigated the effectiveness or ineffectiveness of the intervention if any statistically significant relationship existed between the sample's performance scores from pre- and post-intervention. A two-way ANOVA set for a 95% confidence interval was conducted on the data sets of both pre- and post-intervention to examine the relationship and effect size using PES. If the data were found to have a statistically significant relationship ($p < 0.05$) then a one-way ANOVA was conducted to look for statistically significant differences between age bracket variables on the outcomes and an Independent Sample T-Test was conducted to look for statistically significant differences between the gender variable on the outcomes. Normality testing was also conducted to establish data set normality.

Data analysis indicated a statistically significant relationship was found between the pre- and post-intervention difference measure of 0.72 ($SD=0.91$), $F(1,86)=54.54$, $p < 0.001$, and evidenced a large effect size ($PES=0.388$) for GS application outcomes between the pre- and post-intervention data sets. A one-way ANOVA was conducted to look for differences between age brackets on the findings and no statistically significant differences were found between age brackets on reported outcomes ($F(3,86)=0.31$, $p=0.82$). Additionally, an Independent Samples T-Test was conducted on the data set to look for differences based on gender on the outcomes; the Levene's Test for Equality of Variance did not find any statistically significant differences

($F=0.29$, $p=0.60$) with the overall T-Test ($t(81)=-0.41$, $p=0.68$). A Shapiro-Wilk's test for normality was statistically significant for normality on outcomes ($p=0.03$); when controlling for outliers ($n=83$) a Paired-Sample T-Test resulted in a difference score of 0.68 ($SD=0.75$), $t(82)=-8.32$, $p<0.001$ showing despite the normality outliers the data set's outcomes still resulted in a statistically significant relationship to the intervention. Table 10 displays the findings of the two-way ANOVA for RQ4.

Table 10

Goal Setting (GS) two-way ANOVA statistics

Effect	Value	F	Hyp DF	Error DF	P-Value	PES	Observed Power
<i>Pillar's Trace</i>	.388	54.537	1.000	86.000	<0.001	.388	1.000
<i>Wilks' Lamba</i>	.612	54.537	1.000	86.000	<0.001	.388	1.000
<i>Hotelling's Trace</i>	.634	54.537	1.000	86.000	<0.001	.388	1.000
<i>Roy's Largest Root</i>	.634	54.537	1.000	86.000	<0.001	.388	1.000

After analysis of both the pre- and post-intervention data sets for perception of application for GS results; the researcher rejected the null hypothesis. There was a statistically significant relationship between the intervention and post-intervention outcomes of perception of application of GS as a resilience skill.

Research Question 5/Null Hypothesis 5

- RQ5: To what extent does a two-week resilience intervention have an effect on the application of emotional control performance enhancement resilience strategies when compared to before and after self-reported perception of the strategy for

National Guard soldiers who had previously failed to meet Army physical fitness requirements and minimum standards?

- H_{05} : Traditional M-Day National Guard soldiers that attend a two-week Wellness Camp resilience intervention will not demonstrate a statistically significant change in their application of the emotional control performance enhancement strategy of resilience when compared to their pre-intervention baseline ability.

This study's fifth research question examined the potential statistical significance relationship attendance of the two-week resilience-based Wellness Camp intervention had with soldier application of the Emotion Control (EC) resilience strategy when compared between pre- and post-intervention evaluation. This investigated the effectiveness or ineffectiveness of the intervention if any statistically significant relationship existed between the sample's performance scores from pre- and post-intervention. A two-way ANOVA set for a 95% confidence interval was conducted on the data sets of both pre- and post-intervention to examine the relationship and effect size using PES. If the data were found to have a statistically significant relationship ($p < 0.05$) then a one-way ANOVA was conducted to look for statistically significant differences between age bracket variables on the outcomes and an Independent Sample T-Test was conducted to look for statistically significant differences between the gender variable on the outcomes. Normality testing was also conducted to establish data set normality.

Data analysis indicated a statistically significant relationship was found between the pre- and post-intervention difference measure of 0.28 ($SD=0.51$), $F(1,86)=27.15$, $p < 0.001$, and evidenced a medium effect size ($PES=0.240$) for EC application outcomes between the pre- and post-intervention data sets. A one-way ANOVA was conducted to look for differences between

age brackets on the findings and no statistically significant differences were found between age brackets on reported outcomes ($F(3,86)=1.58, p=0.20$). Additionally, an Independent Samples T-Test was conducted on the data set to look for differences based on gender on the outcomes; the Levene's Test for Equality of Variance did not find any statistically significant differences ($F=0.02, p=0.89$) with the overall T-Test ($t(85)=0.63, p=0.53$). A Shapiro-Wilk's test for normality was not statistically significant for normality on outcomes ($p=0.20$). Table 11 displays the findings of the two-way ANOVA for RQ5.

Table 11

Emotion Control (EC) two-way ANOVA statistics

Effect	Value	F	Hyp DF	Error DF	P-Value	PES	Observed Power
<i>Pillar's Trace</i>	.240	27.145	1.000	86.000	<0.001	.240	.999
<i>Wilks' Lamba</i>	.760	27.145	1.000	86.000	<0.001	.240	.999
<i>Hotelling's Trace</i>	.316	27.145	1.000	86.000	<0.001	.240	.999
<i>Roy's Largest Root</i>	.316	27.145	1.000	86.000	<0.001	.240	.999

After analysis of both the pre- and post-intervention data sets for perception of application for Emotion Control results; the researcher rejected the null hypothesis. There was a statistically significant relationship regarding the perception of application of Emotion Control as a resilience skill and the intervention.

Research Question 6/Null Hypothesis 6

- RQ6: To what extent does a two-week resilience intervention have an effect on the application of imagery performance enhancement resilience strategies when

compared to before and after self-reported perception of the strategy for National Guard soldiers who had previously failed to meet Army physical fitness requirements and minimum standards?

- H_{06} : Traditional M-Day National Guard soldiers that attend a two-week Wellness Camp resilience intervention will not demonstrate a statistically significant change in their application of the imagery performance enhancement strategy of resilience when compared to their pre-intervention baseline ability.

This study's sixth research question examined the potential statistical significance relationship attendance of the two-week resilience-based Wellness Camp intervention had with soldier application of the Imagery (IM) resilience strategy when compared between pre- and post-intervention evaluation. This investigated the effectiveness or ineffectiveness of the intervention if any statistically significant relationship existed between the sample's performance scores from pre- and post-intervention. A two-way ANOVA set for a 95% confidence interval was conducted on the data sets of both pre- and post-intervention to examine the relationship and effect size using PES. If the data were found to have a statistically significant relationship ($p < 0.05$) then a one-way ANOVA was conducted to look for statistically significant differences between age bracket variables on the outcomes and an Independent Sample T-Test was conducted to look for statistically significant differences between the gender variable on the outcomes. Normality testing was also conducted to establish data set normality.

Data analysis indicated a statistically significant relationship was found between the pre- and post-intervention difference measure of 0.65 ($SD=0.68$), $F(1,86)=80.25$, $p < 0.001$, and evidenced a large effect size ($PES=0.483$) for IM application outcomes between the pre- and

post-intervention data sets. A one-way ANOVA was conducted to look for differences between age brackets on the findings and no statistically significant differences were found between age brackets on reported outcomes ($F(3,86)=0.25, p=0.86$). Additionally, an Independent Samples T-Test was conducted on the data set to look for differences based on gender on the outcomes; the Levene's Test for Equality of Variance did not find any statistically significant differences ($F=0.10, p=0.75$) with the overall T-Test ($t(85)=0.10, p=0.55$). A Shapiro-Wilk's test for normality was statistically significant for normality on outcomes ($p<0.001$); however, when controlling for the outliers ($n=83$) the Paired-Sample T-Test resulted in a mean value of -0.56 ($SD=0.54$), $t(82)=-9.42, p<0.001$ showing despite the normality outliers the data set's outcomes still resulted in a statistically significant relationship to the intervention. Table 12 displays the findings of the two-way ANOVA for RQ6.

Table 12

Imagery (IM) two-way ANOVA statistics

Effect	Value	F	Hyp DF	Error DF	P-Value	PES	Observed Power
<i>Pillar's Trace</i>	.483	80.248	1.000	86.000	<0.001	.483	1.000
<i>Wilks' Lamba</i>	.517	80.248	1.000	86.000	<0.001	.483	1.000
<i>Hotelling's Trace</i>	.933	80.248	1.000	86.000	<0.001	.483	1.000
<i>Roy's Largest Root</i>	.933	80.248	1.000	86.000	<0.001	.483	1.000

After analysis of both the pre- and post-intervention data sets for perception of application for Imagery results; the researcher rejected the null hypothesis. There was a

statistically significant relationship between the intervention and post-intervention perception of application of Imagery as a resilience skill.

Research Question 7/Null Hypothesis

- RQ7: To what extent does a two-week resilience intervention have an effect on the application of energy activation performance enhancement resilience strategies when compared to before and after self-reported perception of the strategy for National Guard soldiers who had previously failed to meet Army physical fitness requirements and minimum standards?
- H₀₇: Traditional M-Day National Guard soldiers that attend a two-week Wellness Camp resilience intervention will not demonstrate a statistically significant change in their application of the energy activation performance enhancement strategy of resilience when compared to their pre-intervention baseline ability.

This study's final research question examined the potential statistical significance relationship attendance of the two-week resilience-based Wellness Camp intervention had with soldier application of the Energy Activation (EA) resilience strategy when compared between pre- and post-intervention evaluation. This investigated the effectiveness or ineffectiveness of the intervention if any statistically significant relationship existed between the sample's performance scores from pre- and post-intervention. A two-way ANOVA set for a 95% confidence interval was conducted on the data sets of both pre- and post-intervention to examine the relationship and effect size using PES. If the data were found to have a statistically significant relationship ($P < 0.05$) then a one-way ANOVA was conducted to look for statistically significant differences between age bracket variables on the outcomes and an Independent Sample T-Test was

conducted to look for statistically significant differences between the gender variable on the outcomes. Normality testing was also conducted to establish data set normality.

Data analysis indicated a statistically significant relationship was found between the pre- and post-intervention difference measure of 0.53 ($SD=0.68$), $F(1,86)=52.77$, $p<0.001$, and evidenced a large effect size ($PES=0.380$) for EA application outcomes between the pre- and post-intervention data sets. A one-way ANOVA was conducted to look for differences between age brackets on the findings and no statistically significant differences were found between age brackets on reported outcomes ($F(3,86)=1.27$, $p=0.29$). Additionally, an Independent Samples T-Test was conducted on the data set to look for differences based on gender on the outcomes; the Levene's Test for Equality of Variance did not find any statistically significant differences ($F=0.60$, $p=0.44$) with the overall T-Test ($t(85)=0.83$, $p=0.41$). A Shapiro-Wilk's test for normality was not statistically significant for normality on outcomes ($p=0.052$). Table 13 displays the findings of the two-way ANOVA for RQ7.

Table 13

Energy Application (EA) two-way ANOVA statistics

Effect	Value	F	Hyp DF	Error DF	P-Value	PES	Observed Power
<i>Pillar's Trace</i>	.380	52.765	1.000	86.000	<0.001	.380	1.000
<i>Wilks' Lamba</i>	.620	52.765	1.000	86.000	<0.001	.380	1.000
<i>Hotelling's Trace</i>	.614	52.765	1.000	86.000	<0.001	.380	1.000
<i>Roy's Largest Root</i>	.614	52.765	1.000	86.000	<0.001	.380	1.000

After analysis of both the pre- and post-intervention data sets for perception of application for Imagery results; the researcher rejected the null hypothesis. There was a statistically significant relationship between the intervention and post-intervention perception of application of Energy Activation as a resilience skill.

Evaluation of the Findings

This study rejected all null hypothesis and found statistically significant relationships existed between pre- and post-intervention for all seven research questions. There were only three research questions that required controlling for outliers; however, the analysis of the controlled data still supported statistically significant relationships between the data. All ANOVA assumptions were supported through statistical analysis and neither gender nor age bracket were shown to have statistically significant differences on outcomes. A more thorough description by research question will follow to demonstrate the evaluation of the findings.

The first research question explored the relationship of reported perception of resilience outcomes by the sample both before and after attending the resilience-based Wellness Camp intervention. The goal of this question was to establish the potential existence of a statistically significant relationship in the reported outcomes of perception of resilience between pre- and post-intervention differences in BRS survey mean values. Investigating this outcome required analysis of pre- and post-intervention survey results on the BRS with examination of both age brackets and gender groups to ensure outcomes could be assumed to be related to the sample's participation in the intervention. Through a two-way ANOVA set to 95% confidence interval, a statistically significant relationship was found between the outcomes for resilience perception. Differences between age bracket and gender groups were ruled out through respective one-way ANOVA testing and Independent-Sample T-Testing.

The mean pre-intervention BRS score was 22.14 ($SD=4.46$) and the mean post-intervention BRS score was 23.90 ($SD=3.40$). The two-way ANOVA provided verification of a statistically significant relationship and qualification of a medium effect size for the intervention with a difference score of 1.76 ($SD=4.95$), $F(1,86)=10.99$, $p<0.001$, and $PES=0.113$ for perception of resilience on the BRS. The differences between age brackets were ruled out using a one-way ANOVA ($F(3,86)=0.44$, $p=0.72$) and differences based on gender were ruled out using an Independent Samples T-Test where the Levene's Test for Equality of Variance found no statistically significant differences ($F=0.01$, $p=0.92$) nor did the T-Test ($t(85)=-1.50$, $p=0.14$). This resulted in the null hypothesis being rejected. The p -values listed, and PES established suggested these are strong findings.

The second research question explored the relationship of soldier performance on the Army Physical Fitness Test (APFT) by the sample both before and after attending the resilience-based Wellness Camp intervention. The goal of this question was to establish the potential existence of a statistically significant relationship in the APFT score outcomes between pre- and post-intervention APFT mean values. Investigating this outcome required analysis of pre- and post-intervention APFT performance results with examination of both age brackets and gender groups to ensure outcomes could be assumed to be related to the sample's participation in the intervention. Through a two-way ANOVA set to 95% confidence interval, a statistically significant relationship was found between the outcomes for APFT performance. Differences between age bracket and gender group were ruled out through respective one-way ANOVA testing and Independent-Sample T-Testing.

The mean pre-intervention APFT score was 141.41 ($SD=39.80$) and the mean post-intervention APFT score was 179.55 ($SD=40.08$). The two-way ANOVA provided verification

of a statistically significant relationship and qualification of a large effect size for the intervention with a difference score of 38.14 ($SD=28.19$), $F(1,86)=159.27$, $p<0.001$, and $PES=0.649$ for APFT performance. Differences between age brackets were ruled out using a one-way ANOVA ($F(3,86)=1.46$, $p=0.23$) and differences based on gender were ruled out using an Independent Samples T-Test where the Levene's Test for Equality of Variance found no statistically significant differences ($F=1.83$, $p=0.18$) nor did the T-Test ($t(85)=-0.69$, $p=0.49$). This resulted in the null hypothesis being rejected. The P -values listed, and PES established suggested these are strong findings.

The third research question explored the relationship of soldier performance on the Army Body Composition Program (ABCP) screening by the sample both before and after attending the resilience-based Wellness Camp intervention. The goal of this question was to establish the potential existence of a statistically significant relationship in the ABCP screening outcomes between pre- and post-intervention ABCP mean values. Investigating this outcome required analysis of pre- and post-intervention ABCP performance results with examination of the differences between both age brackets and gender groups to ensure outcomes could be assumed to be related to the sample's participation in the intervention. Through a two-way ANOVA set to 95% confidence interval, a statistically significant relationship was found between the outcomes for ABCP performance. Differences between age bracket and gender group were ruled out through respective one-way ANOVA testing and Independent-Sample T-Testing.

The mean pre-intervention ABCP score was 25.31 ($SD=7.70$) and the mean post-intervention ABCP score was 22.85 ($SD=7.61$). The two-way ANOVA provided verification of a statistically significant relationship and qualification of a large effect size for the intervention with a difference score of -2.46 ($SD=2.20$), $F(1,86)=108.92$, $p<0.001$, and $PES=0.559$ for ABCP

screening performance. Differences between age brackets were ruled out using a one-way ANOVA ($F(3,86)=-2.40, p=0.07$) and differences based on gender were ruled out using an Independent Samples T-Test where the Levene's Test for Equality of Variance found no statistically significant differences ($F=2.45, p=0.12$) nor did the T-Test ($t(85)=-0.69, p=0.91$). This resulted in the null hypothesis being rejected. The P -values listed, and PES established suggested these are strong findings.

The fourth research question explored the relationship of soldier perception of application of Goal Setting (GS) by the sample both before and after attending the resilience-based Wellness Camp intervention. The goal of this question was to establish the potential existence of a statistically significant relationship in the GS outcomes between pre- and post-intervention GS mean values. Investigating this outcome required analysis of pre- and post-intervention GS results with examination of the differences between both age brackets and gender groups to ensure outcomes could be assumed to be related to the sample's participation in the intervention. Through a two-way ANOVA set to 95% confidence interval, a statistically significant relationship was found between the outcomes for GS performance. Differences between age bracket and gender groups were ruled out through respective one-way ANOVA testing and Independent-Sample T-Testing.

The mean pre-intervention GS application outcome was 3.15 ($SD=0.75$) and the mean post-intervention GS application outcome was 3.88 ($SD=0.67$). The two-way ANOVA provided verification of a statistically significant relationship and qualification of a large effect size for the intervention with a difference score of 0.72 ($SD=0.91$), $F(1,86)=54.54, p<0.001$, and $PES=0.388$ for GS application outcomes. Differences between age brackets were ruled out using a one-way ANOVA ($F(3,86)=0.31, p=0.82$) and differences based on gender were ruled out using an

Independent Samples T-Test where the Levene's Test for Equality of Variance found no statistically significant differences ($F=0.29, p=0.60$) nor did the T-Test ($t(81)=-0.41, p=0.68$). This resulted in the null hypothesis being rejected. The P -values listed, and PES established suggested these are strong findings.

The fifth research question explored the relationship of soldier perception of application of Emotion Control (EC) by the sample both before and after attending the resilience-based Wellness Camp intervention. The goal of this question was to establish the potential existence of a statistically significant relationship in the EC outcomes between pre- and post-intervention EC mean values. Investigating this outcome required analysis of pre- and post-intervention EC results with examination of the differences between both age brackets and gender groups to ensure outcomes could be assumed to be related to the sample's participation in the intervention. Through a two-way ANOVA set to 95% confidence interval, a statistically significant relationship was found between the outcomes for EC performance. Differences between age bracket and gender groups were ruled out through respective one-way ANOVA testing and Independent-Sample T-Testing.

The mean pre-intervention EC application outcome was 3.10 ($SD=0.46$) and the mean post-intervention EC application outcome was 3.38 ($SD=0.45$). The two-way ANOVA provided verification of a statistically significant relationship and qualification of a medium effect size for the intervention with a difference score of 0.28 ($SD=0.51$), $F(1,86)=27.15, p<0.001$, and $PES=0.240$ for EC application outcomes. Differences between age brackets were ruled out using a one-way ANOVA ($F(3,86)=1.58, p=0.20$) and differences based on gender were ruled out using an Independent Samples T-Test where the Levene's Test for Equality of Variance found no statistically significant differences ($F=0.02, p=0.89$) nor did the T-Test ($t(85)=0.63, p=0.53$).

This resulted in the null hypothesis being rejected. The *P*-values listed, and PES established suggested these are strong findings.

The sixth research question explored the relationship of soldier perception of application of Imagery (IM) by the sample both before and after attending the resilience-based Wellness Camp intervention. The goal of this question was to establish the potential existence of a statistically significant relationship in the IM outcomes between pre- and post-intervention IM mean values. Investigating this outcome required analysis of pre- and post-intervention IM results with examination of the differences between both age brackets and gender groups to ensure outcomes could be assumed to be related to the sample's participation in the intervention. Through a two-way ANOVA set to 95% confidence interval, a statistically significant relationship was found between the outcomes for IM performance. Differences between age bracket and gender groups were ruled out through respective one-way ANOVA testing and Independent-Sample T-Testing.

The mean pre-intervention IM application outcome was 2.66 ($SD=0.53$) and the mean post-intervention IM application outcome was 3.30 ($SD=0.46$). The two-way ANOVA provided verification of a statistically significant relationship and qualification of a large effect size for the intervention with a difference score of 0.65 ($SD=0.68$), $F(1,86)=80.25$, $p<0.001$, and PES=0.483 for IM application outcomes. Differences between age brackets were ruled out using a one-way ANOVA ($F(3,86)=0.25$, $p=0.86$) and differences based on gender were ruled out using an Independent Samples T-Test where the Levene's Test for Equality of Variance found no statistically significant differences ($F=0.10$, $p=0.75$) nor did the T-Test ($t(85)=0.10$, $p=0.55$). This resulted in the null hypothesis being rejected. The *P*-values listed, and PES established suggested these are strong findings.

The final research question explored the relationship of soldier perception of application of Energy Activation (EA) by the sample both before and after attending the resilience-based Wellness Camp intervention. The goal of this question was to establish the potential existence of a statistically significant relationship in the EA outcomes between pre- and post-intervention EA mean values. Investigating this outcome required analysis of pre- and post-intervention EA results with examination of the differences between both age brackets and gender groups to ensure outcomes could be assumed to be related to the sample's participation in the intervention. Through a two-way ANOVA set to 95% confidence interval, a statistically significant relationship was found between the outcomes for EA performance. Differences between age bracket and gender groups were ruled out through respective one-way ANOVA testing and Independent-Sample T-Testing.

The mean pre-intervention EA application outcome was 3.06 ($SD=0.58$) and the mean post-intervention EA application outcome was 3.59 ($SD=0.51$). The two-way ANOVA provided verification of a statistically significant relationship and qualification of a large effect size for the intervention with a difference score of 0.53 ($SD=0.68$), $F(1,86)=52.77$, $p<0.001$, and $PES=0.380$ for EA application outcomes. Differences between age brackets were ruled out using a one-way ANOVA ($F(3,86)=1.27$, $p=0.29$) and differences based on gender were ruled out using an Independent Samples T-Test where the Levene's Test for Equality of Variance found no statistically significant differences ($F=0.60$, $p=0.44$) nor did the T-Test ($t(85)=0.83$, $p=0.41$). This resulted in the null hypothesis being rejected. The P -values listed, and PES established suggested these are strong findings.

The overall results showed that a statistically significant relationship was found for all areas of this study and that these results were not shown to be statistically different between age

brackets or gender groups. The current study builds upon the research conducted on Active Duty Army soldiers that discovered an association between resilience levels and aspects of behavior that can either harm or benefit a person's military career (Curley et al., 2020; Curley & Warner, 2017; Harms et al., 2013; Lester et al., 2011). Further, this study approached the research from the perspective addressing self-efficacy as a by-product of resiliency training (Black et al., 2017; Cacioppo et al., 2015; Cassidy, 2015; Lester et al., 2011; Nindle et al., 2018; Nindle et al., 2013). The findings lend themselves to expand the current body of literature on the influence of resilience on service members.

Summary

The purpose of this quantitative, quasi-experimental, ex post facto, survey-based study was to analyze the influence that the two-week resilience-based Wellness Camp intervention had upon pre- and post-intervention data sets for perception of resilience, performance on fitness testing, performance in body composition screening, and perception of application of the GS, EA, EC, and IM resilience strategies. The completion of the descriptive statistics, normality statistics, satisfaction of assumptions, and relationship statistics assisted in identifying the presence of statistically significant relationships between the outcomes and the intervention for the seven research questions. Age and gender were used as independent variables. Dependent variables for this study included: perception of resilience scores using the BRS, physical performance scores on the APFT, outcomes from the ABCP screening, and outcomes from the TOPS measuring the use of the strategies of Goal Setting, Emotion Control, Imagery, and Energy Activation. Each research question evaluated the role of age and gender for potential statistically significant differences in outcomes, and the normality of the distribution was also analyzed for outliers.

Two-way ANOVAs were used to examine both the independent and dependent variables for statistically significant relationships. A statistically significant relationship was found between the differences of pre- and post-intervention mean values for all seven research questions and the intervention. Based on the findings listed, the resilience-based Wellness Camp intervention was assumed to have resulted in enhanced performance outcomes (ABCP and APFT), perceptions of the resilience strategies (EA, EC, IM, and GS), and the perception of resilience.

Chapter 5: Conclusions, Implications, and Recommendations

This study's purpose was to test the potential relationship between the two-week resilience-based Wellness Camp intervention and, pre- and post-intervention dependent values in the areas of perception of resilience, APFT performance, ABCP screening outcomes, perception of use of goal setting (GS), perception of use of emotion control (EC), perception of use of imagery (IM), and perception of use of energy activation (EA). The intervention consisted of a two-week resilience-based Wellness Camp that administered the Army's Master Resilience Training (MRT) curriculum at an increased frequency to Army National Guard soldiers that were administratively flagged due to failure to meet the Army's minimum standards for fitness testing and/or body composition screening. This was important as the Army National Guard's Army Physical Fitness Test (APFT) failure rate have been reported to be notably higher than that of the Active Duty component and it has been described that soldiers in reserve components (Army Reserve or Army National Guard) are at an elevated risk of APFT failure (Bernstein et al., 2017; DMDC, 2019a; HQFLARNG, 2020; Meyer, 2018; Russell et al., 2019; Sih, & Negus, 2016). This elevated rate of administrative flags across the Army National Guard becomes both a readiness and fiscal problem due to the limitation of favorable actions and potential of separation from service that accompanies an administrative flag (HQDA, 2016; HQDA, 2016a; HQDA, 2017b; Pendleton, 2019).

While identifying the root of the issue of elevated failure rates in the Army National Guard was beyond the scope of this study, Feickert and Kapp (2014) suggested that one of the major factors affecting these differences between Active Duty and reserve component soldiers was the fact that Active Duty soldiers are soldiers 365 days a year and attend regular physical readiness training (PRT), while Army National Guard soldiers only drill one-weekend a month

and two-weeks a year. During the remaining time, the civilian careers of Army National Guard soldiers may not allow time for physical training or these soldiers may be left to rely solely on their willpower and motivation to find time to train. To account for these concerns this study examined this issue through the lens of resilience and resiliency training, as enhanced resilience results in enhanced self-efficacy which promotes healthy behavior initiation and motivation which in turn are keys to success in passing fitness testing and body composition screenings (Cacioppo et al., 2015; Nindle et al., 2013; Nindle et al., 2018). The overarching hypotheses for this study was that the sample of traditional (attending drill one-weekend-a-month and two-weeks-a-year) National Guard soldiers' outcomes after attending the two-week resilience-based Wellness Camp intervention would demonstrate a statistically significant relationship between the pre- and post-test outcomes being measured.

To evaluate this stance, the research design selected for this study was a quasi-experimental, ex post facto, outcomes comparison. The independent variables evaluated were gender of the soldier (as listed on their DEERS profile) and age bracket of the soldier based on the Army Body Composition Program (ABCP) doctrine. Seven research questions were designed to evaluate the relationship between the pre- and post-intervention dependent variables of perception of resilience (using the BRS), APFT performance scores, ABCP screening outcomes, application of Goal Setting (GS), application of Imagery (IM), application of Emotion Control (EC), and application of Energy Activation (EA). These research questions guided this study in its search for statistical significance in both performance and perception outcomes.

This study's limitations and delimitations were addressed. The limitations included soldier participation based on their selection by their respective chains of command, soldiers geographically distributed across their state and their local areas may not support their needs

after the intervention, and the nature of the Army's command structure did not provide the researcher command authority over the soldiers of the sample leading to potential issues with compliance. Regarding delimitations of these issues, compliance concerns were addressed through the soldiers' chain of command, the published memorandum of information (MOI) acted as a syllabus for expectations of the participants, and the researcher collected a list of phone contacts and emails for the participants to provide necessary resources post-intervention if not available due to geographic dispersion.

Chapter five serves to summarize the results of this study. Included within this chapter will be discussion points on outcomes, conclusion, contributions to existing literature, implications, and recommendations for expansion on the topic. This chapter serves to deliver a summary analysis of resilience-driven outcomes that could potentially be used to benefit the reserve components of the Army and could be further adapted to benefit the Army as a whole.

Conclusions

This study explored seven quantitative outcomes for 87 soldiers in the sample regarding perception of resilience, application of resilience, and performance in both fitness testing and body composition screening. The resilience curriculum delivered during the two-week resilience-based Wellness Camp intervention was presented in a manner that supported Adult Learning Theory by leaning heavily on the assumption that adult learners enter an educational environment with past experiences (Kenner & Weinerman, 2011; Malik, 2016; McCall et al., 2018). The curriculum was built around leveraging these past experiences as examples to allow for deeper reflection on the processes and outcomes associated to those experiences. Adult Learning Theory was used to help the soldiers discover how they could improve their personal resilience and develop a deeper understanding of the process-based view of the construct of

resilience (Joyce et al., 2018; Shaw et al., 2016; Van Breda, 2018). While data analysis of these areas was presented in the previous chapter, this section will focus on interpretation of these findings.

- RQ1: To what extent does a two-week resilience intervention have an effect on perceived levels of resilience when compared before and after intervention in traditional National Guard soldiers who fail to meet the Army's physical fitness requirements and minimum standards?

This research question examined the relationship of the intervention to the pre- and post-intervention outcome of perception of personal resilience as measured by Ohio State University's Brief Resilience Scale (BRS) (See Appendix A). The research question further explored the potential differences between outcomes found from independent variables of age bracket and gender group. The null hypothesis was rejected for this research question as there was a statistically significant relationship found for the intervention and the between differences measures using a two-way ANOVA (1.76 ($SD=4.95$), $F(1,86)=10.99$, $p<0.001$). The pre-intervention BRS mean value for the sample was 22.14 ($SD=4.46$) and the post-intervention mean value was 23.90 ($SD=3.40$), which showed that the sample reported an elevated level of perception of personal resilience post-intervention. The effect size for perception of resilience was medium ($PES=0.113$) for this intervention. No relationship was found based on the differences between outcomes due to age brackets nor gender group. This was examined using a one-way ANOVA ($F(3,86)=0.44$, $p=0.72$) for age-brackets and the differences between outcomes based on gender group were examined using an Independent Samples T-Test ($t(85)=-1.50$, $p=0.14$).

While it is expected that a two-week resilience-based intervention would result in enhanced perception of resilience; the two-way ANOVA resulted in a difference score of 1.76 ($SD=4.95$), $F(1,86)=10.99$, $p<0.001$, with a only a medium effect size of ($PES=0.113$). This finding of the medium effect size for the perception of resilience was of interest. Further, the results of the one-way ANOVA and Independent Samples T-Test added to the findings regarding differences between genders and age brackets. The one-way ANOVA for age brackets found that the largest post-intervention mean value was in the 28–39 years-old age bracket (2.75 ($SD=5.01$)) and the smallest change was seen in the 21-27 years-old age bracket (1.27 ($SD=5.05$)) with the 40+ year-old age bracket not far behind (1.33 ($SD=4.95$)). Further, the Independent Sample T-Test found a larger post-intervention change for female soldiers in the sample (3.04 ($SD=4.89$)) compared to the male soldiers in the sample (1.27 ($SD=4.92$)). In this study the results found the intervention was most effective for enhancing perception of resilience in the 28-39 years-old female component of the sample and least effective in the 21-27 years-old male component of the sample. It is possible that the effect size was only medium for perception of resilience due to the post-intervention change outcomes differences for females over two-times that of the males. However, the notable finding of significance in the overall outcome ($p=0.001$) suggested the intervention had significant impact on soldiers' perception of resilience overall, despite the differences in outcomes between sub-components of the population. These outcomes should be taken into consideration as healthy behavior starting and motivation have been associated with enhanced self-efficacy, a by-product of enhanced perception of resilience (Black et al., 2017; Cacioppo et al., 2015; Lines et al., 2019; Van Breda, 2018; Wang et al., 2017).

Another point of discussion in the findings associated to the age bracket results, was the unique finding in this measure of variance in outcomes. The two-week resilience-based Wellness Camp intervention was designed to implement Adult Learning Theory, an instructional design that targeted learners in the twenty-five years-old and up age bracket (McCall et al., 2018). The age bracket containing the starting age expressed the lowest mean difference value between pre- and post-intervention screening. However, this was not seen across all seven measures of this study and was unique to the perception of resilience. The age bracket in question included ages below the Adult Learning Theory target population ages of 21-24. This may have accounted for this finding; but it did not account for the second lowest performing age bracket being the forty years-old and up age-bracket. This unique outcome for perception of resilience may also help explain the lower effect size rating for this measure. Having said this, the strongest performers were the age bracket of 28-39 which were within the Adult Learning Theory age range. Despite all of this, the overarching low recidivism rates and notable long-term retention rates of Wellness Camp participants reported by the Army National Guard's R2 Program (Eads, 2018; HQFLARNG; 2018) combined with the outcomes of this study shed light on a potential association between the intervention's increased frequency of resilience training effects on resilience perception and soldier performance.

- RQ2: To what extent does a two-week resilience intervention have an effect on Army Physical Fitness Testing Scores on record fitness testing when compared to before and after record fitness testing results for National Guard soldiers who had previously failed to meet Army physical fitness requirements and minimum standards?

The second research question examined the relationship of the intervention to the pre- and post-intervention outcome on the Army Physical Fitness Test (APFT) as a total score of all

three events. The research question further explored the potential differences between outcomes from independent variables of age bracket and gender group. The null hypothesis was rejected for this research question as there was a statistically significant relationship found for the between differences measures in the two-way ANOVA (38.14 ($SD=28.19$), $F(1,86)=159.27$, $p<0.001$) and the intervention. The pre-intervention APFT mean score for the sample was 141.41 ($SD=39.80$) and the post-intervention mean value was 179.55 ($SD=40.08$), which showed that the sample enhanced their physical performance levels on the APFT post-intervention. The effect size for perception of resilience was large ($PES=0.649$) for this intervention. No relationship was found based on the differences between outcomes due to age brackets nor gender group. This was examined using a one-way ANOVA ($F(3,86)=1.46$, $p=0.23$) for age-brackets and the differences between outcomes based on gender group were examined using an Independent Samples T-Test ($t(85)=-0.69$, $p=0.49$).

Unlike the outcome of the first research question, these data show less variance between the independent variable results for age bracket and gender group and a large effect size. The two-way ANOVA for the differences in outcomes resulted in 38.14 ($SD=28.19$), $F(1,86)=159.27$, $p<0.001$, with a large effect size of ($PES=0.649$). When examining the outcomes by gender using a one-way ANOVA, the female mean difference score (41.54 ($SD=35.30$)) was higher than the male mean difference score (36.84($SD=25.17$)). The Independent Samples T-Test for age brackets found the highest mean difference scores to belong to the 17-20 years-old age bracket (44.00 ($SD=23.22$)) and the lowest to belong to the 28-39 years-old age bracket (26.95($SD=21.08$)). These data found the intervention to be most effective for female members of the sample that were in the 17-20 years-old age bracket. Of note, while the 28-39 years-old age bracket had the most enhanced outcome for perception of resilience, they

demonstrated the least enhancement in APFT performance post-intervention. Deeper exploration may need to be conducted as to the application of resilience on enhanced performance in this sample to explain these findings.

The two-week intervention did include daily physical training and this likely played a role in the enhanced post-intervention performance on the APFT. The reported statistical significance of difference score means comparison ($p < 0.001$) suggested that the intervention had significant impact on soldier physical performance in the APFT. There are drastic military readiness and fiscal concerns associated with soldiers that are flagged for failing to meet the APFT requirements, including overburdening deployable soldiers and recruiting costs averaging \$180,000.00 per soldier to be replaced from separation due to administrative flagging actions (Eads, 2018; HQDA, 2014b; HQFLARNG, 2018; Pendleton, 2019).

While performance enhancement is a likely by-product of two-weeks of physical readiness training, the role that the resilience aspect played cannot yet be deciphered. Contrasting testing results between the perception of resilience outcomes and the APFT performance outcomes lend themselves to gray areas in this portion of the discussion. This study found opposite performances in the 28-39 years-old age bracket for perception of resilience and APFT performance difference means values yet also found relatively high performance in both perception of resilience and APFT performance in the 17-20 years-old age bracket. Regarding the Adult Learning Theory and construct of resilience, adult learners are problem-oriented and enhancing self-efficacy supports their ability to overcome a program such as a failed APFT (Lines et al., 2019; Malik, 2016; Pierson, 2017; Van Breda, 2018; Wang et al., 2017). These findings are mostly in line with the contemporary literature in that enhanced resilience has been

shown to positively effect physical performance by way of enhanced self-efficacy (Bandura, 1982; Cassidy, 2015; Crane et al., 2017; Hong et al., 2018).

- RQ3: To what extent does a two-week resilience intervention have an effect on body composition testing outcomes for record body composition screenings when compared to before and after record body composition screening results for National Guard soldiers who had previously failed to meet Army physical fitness requirements and minimum standards?

The third research question examined the relationship of the intervention to the pre- and post-intervention outcome of Army Body Composition Program (ABCP) screening. The research question further explored the potential differences between outcomes found from independent variables of age bracket and gender group. The null hypothesis was rejected for this research question as there was a statistically significant relationship found for the between differences measures in the two-way ANOVA (-2.46 ($SD=2.20$), $F(1,86)=108.92$, $p<0.001$) and the intervention. The pre-intervention ABCP mean score for the sample was 25.31 ($SD=7.70$) and the post-intervention mean value was 22.85 ($SD=7.61$), which showed that the sample decreased their body fat levels on the ABCP post-intervention. The effect size for perception of resilience was large ($PES=0.559$) for this intervention. No relationship was found based on the differences between outcomes due to age brackets nor gender group. This was examined using a one-way ANOVA ($F(3,86)=2.40$, $p=0.07$) for age-brackets and the differences between outcomes based on gender group were examined using an Independent Samples T-Test ($t(85)=-0.11$, $p=0.91$).

This study's body composition findings per the two-way ANOVA for the differences in outcomes were -2.46 ($SD=2.20$), $F(1,86)=108.92$, $p<0.001$, with a large effect size of ($PES=0.559$). The gender group findings were very closely aligned, a one-way ANOVA resulted

in a slightly lower female mean difference score (-2.42 ($SD=2.47$)) compare to the male mean difference score (-2.48 ($SD=2.11$)), both showing directionality toward loss of body fat. The Independent Samples T-Test for age brackets found some variance in outcomes. The two highest mean difference scores belonged to the 21-27 years-old age bracket (-2.84 ($SD=2.45$)) and the 28-39 years-old age bracket (-2.75 ($SD=1.65$)); while the lowest two belonged to the 17-20 years-old age bracket (-1.50($SD=1.90$)) and the 40+ years-old age bracket (-1.17 ($SD=1.60$)). Despite the age bracket variance, the intervention and difference outcomes findings were significant and effect size was large for this measure ($p<0.001$, $PES=0.559$).

The two-week resilience-based Wellness Camp intervention's physical readiness training would be reasonably expected to result in a decrease in participant body fat with potential increase in lean muscle tissue. The statistical significance of means comparison, combined with both the effect size and the directionality of results suggested that the intervention had significant impact on the soldier's performance on the ABCP screening. Further, the 21-27 years-old age bracket showed elevated results in difference mean values between performance on both the APFT (41.00 ($SD=33.00$)) and the ABCP (-2.84 ($SD=2.45$)). The sample demonstrated in this age bracket decreased body fat composition and enhanced fitness performance could be linked. However, in comparison the 28-39 years-old age bracket demonstrated the opposite association of outcomes between performance on the APFT (26.95 ($SD=21.08$)) and ABCP (-2.75 ($SD=1.65$)). In this age bracket enhanced loss of body fat coincided with the lowest levels of fitness testing performance. It is important to note that the group still performed well in both measures, they just performed the least well in fitness testing performance.

The continuum of results along the construct of resilience in support of self-efficacy in both healthy behavior-starting and motivation noted by Black et al. (2017), Cacioppo et al.

(2015), Lines et al. (2019), Van Breda (2018), and Wang et al. (2017) became an important adaptation and potential cause of the noted outcome. By leveraging the Army's resilience curriculum to embed self-efficacy concepts of healthy behavior starting to get soldiers to choose healthier food intake levels and motivation to maintain those decisions, military readiness to deploy and fiscal concerns can be addressed. Thus, these data and study outcomes shed light on a potential association between the intervention's increased frequency of resilience training effects on healthy eating and exercise behaviors to support lower overall Body Mass Indexes and body fat measures across the fighting force.

- RQ4: To what extent does a two-week resilience intervention have an effect on the application of goal setting as a performance enhancement resilience strategy when compared to before and after self-reported perception of the strategy for National Guard soldiers who had previously failed to meet Army physical fitness requirements and minimum standards?

The fourth research question examined the relationship of the intervention to the pre- and post-intervention outcome of perception of application of Goal Setting (GS) as a resilience performance strategy. The research question further explored the potential differences between outcomes found from independent variables of age bracket and gender group. The null hypothesis was rejected for this research question as there was a statistically significant relationship found for the between differences measures in the two-way ANOVA (0.72 ($SD=0.91$), $F(1,86)=54.54$, $p<0.001$) and the intervention. The pre-intervention GS mean score for the sample was 3.15 ($SD=0.75$) and the post-intervention mean value was 3.88 ($SD=0.67$), which showed that the sample enhanced their application of the GS strategy post-intervention. The effect size for perception of resilience was large ($PES=0.388$) for this intervention. No

relationship was found based on the differences between outcomes due to age brackets nor gender group. This was examined using a one-way ANOVA ($F(3,86)=0.31, p=0.82$) for age-brackets and the differences between outcomes based on gender group were examined using an Independent Samples T-Test ($t(85)=-0.41, p=0.68$).

This study's findings for application of GS per the two-way ANOVA for the differences in outcomes were $0.72 (SD=0.91), F(1,86)=54.54, p<0.001$, with a large effect size of ($PES=0.388$). The gender group findings were closely aligned, a one-way ANOVA resulted in a slightly higher female mean difference score ($0.74 (SD=0.80)$) compare to the male mean difference score ($0.66 (SD=0.74)$), both showing directionality toward enhanced application of the strategy. The Independent Samples T-Test for age brackets found three of the four age brackets to have commonality in outcomes: 17-20 years-old ($0.67 (SD=0.73)$), 21-27 years-old ($0.67 (SD=0.82)$), and 28-39 years-old ($0.64 (SD=0.67)$). Meanwhile, the 40+ years-old age bracket demonstrated a more notable change in difference scores ($0.97 (SD=0.75)$). Based on these findings from this sample, while all groups saw success it appears that the sample's males and females in the 40+ years-old age bracket had the most notable change in application of GS as a performance strategy after attendance of the intervention.

It is possible that the two-week nature of the resilience-based Wellness Camp intervention's implementation of Adult Learning Theory effectively assisted in translating the concept and application of the GS strategy to the 40+ years-old age bracket. Their life experience may lend itself better to understanding the need of this strategy and thusly show greater results for this strategy. According to Adult Learning Theory, adult learners want to know the 'why' behind the need to learn (Malik, 2016; Pierson, 2017; Teaching Excellence in Adult Literacy, 2011). It is also possible that the two-week intervention did stress enough of the rationale of

effective GS to secure participant ‘buy-in’ to develop enhanced perception of application of the skill. Regarding the sample, the intervention appears to have been effective in enhancing usage of this strategy across both genders and all age brackets, but more effective in soldiers that are 40+ years-old.

- RQ5: To what extent does a two-week resilience intervention have an effect on the application of emotional control performance enhancement resilience strategies when compared to before and after self-reported perception of the strategy for National Guard soldiers who had previously failed to meet Army physical fitness requirements and minimum standards?

The fifth research question examined the relationship of the intervention to the pre- and post-intervention outcome of perception of application of Emotion Control (EC) as a resilience performance strategy. The research question further explored the potential differences between outcomes found from independent variables of age bracket and gender groups. The null hypothesis was rejected for this research question as there was a statistically significant relationship found for the between differences measures in the two-way ANOVA (0.28 ($SD=0.51$), $F(1,86)=27.15$, $p<0.001$) and the intervention. The pre-intervention EC mean score for the sample was 3.10 ($SD=0.46$) and the post-intervention mean value was 3.38 ($SD=0.45$), which showed that the sample enhanced their application of the EC strategy post-intervention. The effect size for perception of resilience was medium ($PES=0.240$) for this intervention. No relationship was found based on the differences between outcomes due to age brackets nor gender group. This was examined using a one-way ANOVA ($F(3,86)=1.58$, $p=0.20$) for age-brackets and the differences between outcomes based on gender group were examined using an Independent Samples T-Test ($t(85)=0.63$, $p=0.53$).

This study's findings for application of EC per the two-way ANOVA for the differences in outcomes were 0.28 ($SD=0.51$), $F(1,86)=27.15$, $p<0.001$, with a medium effect size of ($PES=0.240$). The gender group findings were closely aligned, a one-way ANOVA resulted in a slightly lower female mean difference score (0.23 ($SD=0.48$)) compare to the male mean difference score (0.30 ($SD=0.52$)), both showing directionality toward enhanced application of the strategy. The Independent Samples T-Test for age brackets found the two younger age brackets to have a lower range of outcomes: 17-20 years-old (0.26 ($SD=0.40$)) and 21-27 years-old (0.20 ($SD=0.43$)). While the two older age brackets had a higher range of outcomes: 28-39 years-old (0.49 ($SD=0.62$)) and 40+ years-old (0.32 ($SD=0.80$)). Based on these findings from this sample, while all groups saw success it is evidenced that older males and females in the sample experienced the most notable change in application of EC as a performance strategy after attendance of the intervention.

Only two measures of this study resulted in a medium effect size, the perception of resilience and EC ($PES=240$). This finding for EC could be associated to the strongest outcomes for EC being found in the 40+ years-old age bracket which had the smallest size ($n=6$), the remaining age brackets consisted of 93.1% of the sample size ($n=81$). While the entire sample was found to have a significant relationship between the intervention and their difference mean values for EC, the measure did not meet the gate for large effect size due to the outcomes for sample members in the age range of 17-39 years-old.

The statistically significant relationship between intervention and mean difference outcomes for pre- and post-intervention for EC were supported by two of the Army's MRT curriculum's core competencies, self-awareness and self-regulation that were a focal point of the intervention (Reivich, 2014; Reivich, 2020a; Reivich et al., 2011). The strategy of EC allowed

for soldiers to have a stronger locus of control over their responses and performances and enabled enhanced perception of resilience based on their self-efficacy as part of the construct of resilience (Cassidy, 2015; Crane et al., 2017; Lines et al., 2019). Further, it was possible to associate the significant relationships found to the intervention's inclusion of multiple instructional sessions applying Adult Learning Theory's assumption of self-concept where the learners perceived responsibility for their own actions (Kenner & Weinerman, 2011; Malik, 2016; McCall et al., 2018; Pierson, 2017). These data combined with the outcomes of this study lend themselves to a suggested potential association between the intervention's increased frequency of resilience training effects on soldier perception of application of EC toward their performance.

- RQ6: To what extent does a two-week resilience intervention have an effect on the application of imagery performance enhancement resilience strategies when compared to before and after self-reported perception of the strategy for National Guard soldiers who had previously failed to meet Army physical fitness requirements and minimum standards?

The sixth research question examined the relationship of the intervention to the pre- and post-intervention outcome of perception of application of Imagery (IM) as a resilience performance strategy. The research question further explored the potential differences between outcomes found from independent variables of age bracket and gender group. The null hypothesis was rejected for this research question as there was a statistically significant relationship found for the between differences measures in the two-way ANOVA (0.65 ($SD=0.68$), $F(1,86)=80.25$, $p<0.001$) and the intervention. The pre-intervention IM mean score for the sample was 2.65 ($SD=0.53$) and the post-intervention mean value was 3.30 ($SD=0.46$),

which showed that the sample enhanced their application of the IM strategy post-intervention. The effect size for perception of resilience was large ($PES=0.483$) for this intervention. No relationship was found based on the differences between outcomes due to age brackets nor gender group. This was examined using a one-way ANOVA ($F(3,86)=0.25, p=0.86$) for age-brackets and the differences between outcomes based on gender group were examined using an Independent Samples T-Test ($t(85)=0.10, p=0.55$).

This study's findings for application of IM per the two-way ANOVA for the differences in outcomes were $0.65 (SD=0.68), F(1,86)=80.25, p<0.001$, with a large effect size of ($PES=0.483$). The gender group findings were closely aligned, a one-way ANOVA resulted in a slightly higher female mean difference score ($0.72 (SD=0.66)$) compare to the male mean difference score ($0.62 (SD=0.68)$), both showing directionality toward enhanced application of the strategy. The Independent Samples T-Test for age brackets found the three younger age brackets to have the highest range of outcomes: 17-20 years-old ($0.69 (SD=0.85)$), 21-27 years-old ($0.61 (SD=0.62)$), and 28-39 years-old ($0.74 (SD=0.73)$). While the oldest age brackets had the lowest outcome, 40+ years-old ($0.53 (SD=0.45)$). Based on these findings from this sample, while all groups saw success it appeared that younger males and females in the sample experienced the most notable change in application of IM as a performance strategy after attendance of the intervention.

The pre-intervention application of IM mean difference value ($2.65 (SD=0.53)$) was the lowest of all four performance strategies evaluated (GS, EC, IM, and EA). The difference score between pre- and post-intervention for IM ($0.65 (SD=0.68)$) was the second highest range of change resulting from the four performance strategies. The large change between pre- and post-intervention scores likely resulted in the large effect size, suggesting that for the sample this

intervention was effective at enhancing the use of IM. The low mean value pre-intervention score was likely a result of the state of the soldiers selected for the intervention. To understand the potential factor influencing the pre-intervention IM mean value, it was important to bear in mind that the participants of this study were selected for participation by their respective chains of command based on their previous failure to meet the established Army standards for fitness testing and/or body composition. Hardy et al. (2010) suggested that those that relied upon imagery as a performance enhancement skill also tended to score higher on measures of self-confidence. Soldiers whose careers are on the line and pending separation from service are likely experiencing increased levels of psychological stress and according to Nindle et al. (2018) demonstrate poor self-efficacy and resilience. As this study investigated a population that was likely starting with a lower pre-intervention measure of resilience and sense of self-worth, this could explain why the initial IM findings were so low. However, there was a notable increase in perception of application of IM, suggesting that the statistically significant relationship of the intervention and perception of resilience may have positively affected application of the IM strategy.

- RQ7: To what extent does a two-week resilience intervention have an effect on the application of energy activation performance enhancement resilience strategies when compared to before and after self-reported perception of the strategy for National Guard soldiers who had previously failed to meet Army physical fitness requirements and minimum standards?

The last research question examined the relationship of the intervention to the pre- and post-intervention outcome of perception of application of Energy Activation (EA) as a resilience performance strategy. The research question further explored the potential differences between

outcomes found from independent variables of age bracket and gender group. The null hypothesis was rejected for this research question as there was a statistically significant relationship found for the between differences measures in the two-way ANOVA (0.53 ($SD=0.68$), $F(1,86)=52.77$, $p<0.001$) and the intervention. The pre-intervention EA mean score for the sample was 3.06 ($SD=0.58$) and the post-intervention mean value was 3.59 ($SD=0.51$), which showed that the sample enhanced their application of the EA strategy post-intervention. The effect size for perception of resilience was large ($PES=0.380$) for this intervention. No relationship was found based on the differences between outcomes due to age brackets nor gender group. This was examined using a one-way ANOVA ($F(3,86)=1.27$, $p=0.29$) for age-brackets and the differences between outcomes based on gender group were examined using an Independent Samples T-Test ($t(85)=0.83$, $p=0.29$).

This study's findings for application of EA per the two-way ANOVA for the differences in outcomes were 0.53 ($SD=0.68$), $F(1,86)=52.77$, $p<0.001$, with a large effect size of ($PES=0.380$). A one-way ANOVA resulted in a slightly lower female mean difference score (0.43 ($SD=0.76$)) compare to the male mean difference score (0.57 ($SD=0.65$)), both showing directionality toward enhanced application of the strategy. The Independent Samples T-Test for age brackets found that the younger two age brackets had the lowest range of outcomes: 17-20 years-old (0.28 ($SD=0.68$)) and 21-27 years-old (0.52 ($SD=0.70$)). While the oldest two age brackets had the highest outcomes: 28-39 years-old (0.70 ($SD=0.68$)) and 40+ years-old (0.71 ($SD=0.46$)). Based on these findings from this sample, while all groups saw success it is evidenced that older males in the sample experienced the most notable change in application of EC as a performance strategy after attendance of the intervention.

The Adult Learning Theory's principles of self-concept and the adult learner's seeking of how to use the information at that point in time appear to best represent the findings for this research question (Kenner & Weinerman, 2011; Malik, 2016; McCall et al., 2018; Pierson, 2017). Adult learners seek to have control over themselves and their performance and combining that with the ability to immediately apply the skills in their life and see change could explain why the statistical analysis lent itself to reject the null hypothesis. This is further enabled by the enhancement of resilience in the construct of resilience which empowers optimism and enables learning of new skills (Reivich, 2014; Reivich, 2020c; Reivich & Shatte, 2002; Seligman & Csikszentmihalyi, 2000).

The overarching findings for this study were statistically significant relationships between the intervention and post-intervention mean value outcomes for perception of resilience, APFT performance, ABCP outcomes, application of GS, application of EC, application for IM, and application of EA. The intervention resulted in large effect sizes being found for APFT performance, ABCP performance, application of GS, application of IM, application of EA. Medium effect sizes was found for perception or resilience and EC. Despite effect size, all areas demonstrated a directionality of outcomes at the post-intervention evaluation time point that supported enhanced performance or healthy behavioral change. The sample increased their perception of resilience, APFT performance, and applications of all four strategies (GS, EC, IM, and EA); while decreasing body fat. The instructional methodology implemented, where the resilience training materials were presented through the lens of the Adult Learning Theory could have played an important role in the noted findings and success of the intervention. The sample age-brackets that were within the Adult Learning Theory's age ranges of 25 years-old and older had enhanced outcomes at post-intervention testing for the areas of ABCP performance,

application of GS, application of EC, and application of EA. However, the younger age brackets seemed to demonstrate elevated outcomes in the areas of perception of resilience, APFT performance, and application of IM. The Army's implementation of Adult Learning Theory across all aspects of Professional Military Education (PME) and the fact that soldiers are considered non-traditional learners supported the use of Adult Learning Theory in this intervention (Pierson, 2017). These data showed that the sample's participation in the two-week resilience-based Wellness Camp intervention resulted in enhanced resilience, physical performance, and perception of application of various resilience strategies that promote healthy behaviors and outcomes, along with decreased body composition scores.

Contributions to the Literature

This study's findings could be used to supplement current gaps in the contemporary literature. The effects of the Army's Master Resilience Training (MRT) curriculum have been extensively examined on large scales in the Army; however, these studies that resulted in beneficial findings of enhanced resilience being linked to positive professional outcomes and positively effecting social and emotional fitness were only conducted on Active Duty soldiers (Lester et al., 2011; Lester et al., 2011). This created a knowledge gap that the current study begins the process of filling. The results of this study find their niche in that one of the noted outcomes of resilience training was enhanced self-efficacy with particular focus on healthy behavior starting and motivation to continue healthy behaviors (Bandura, 1982; Black et al., 2017; Cassidy, 2015; Nindle et al., 2018; Nindle et al., 2013) and the Army National Guard, a reserve component of the Army experiences high rates of both APFT and ABCP failure (Russell et al., 2019).

The findings of statistically significant relationships between pre- and post-intervention testing for performance measures of APFT and ABCP outcomes, perception of resilience, and perception of application of resilience strategies for performance (GS, EC, IM, and EA) in traditional M-Day (non-full time) National Guard soldiers lend themselves to support a need for enhanced resilience training in the reserve components of the Army and build upon the findings of the foundational research conducted on the Army's MRT program. Army doctrine currently requires a decreased frequency of resiliency training for reserve components (HQDA, 2014; HQDA, 2017a), yet the reserve components are suggested to be the component of the Army that could benefit most from enhanced self-efficacy, a by-product of enhanced perception of resilience (Black et al., 2017; Cacioppo et al., 2015; Cassidy, 2015; Lester et al., 2011; Nindle et al., 2018; Nindle et al., 2013). These findings and identified need create a confluence of contribution to the current body of literature on the topic.

Implications for Practice

Potential beneficence for non-full-time soldiers in the areas of resilience and performance to enable enhanced self-efficacy are evidenced in this study's findings. A primary implication based on the statistically significant relationships in perception of resilience, fitness testing performance, body composition screening, and application of the strategies of goal setting, emotion control, imagery, and energy activation as part of fitness endeavors was that the Army's embedded MRTs could apply concepts of Adult Learning Theory to their instructional models to assist in enhancing their unit's readiness to deploy through the lifting of administrative flags. A secondary implication identified by the researcher builds upon the finding of statistically significant relationships in perception of resilience, in that Army commanders at all levels should prioritize implementing increased frequency of resiliency training to see enhanced performance

through the development of self-efficacy as a by-product of enhanced perception of resilience. A final implication identified by the researcher was a recommendation to increase doctrinally required frequency of resilience training in the reserve components (Army Reserve and Army National Guard) to decrease the elevated number of administrative flags for those components of the force through enhanced self-efficacy and motivation. These implications could enhance the readiness to deploy and performance across all components of the Army.

Recommendations for Future Research

As this study only examined the outcomes for an intervention group that received the MRT curriculum at an increased frequency than doctrinally required upon immediate completion of the intervention, future studies should look at randomized control studies using both an intervention and control group. Future research should further explore long term outcomes at six-months and/or a year post-intervention. Based on the resilience age bracket findings differences, it would benefit future research to also examine the effects of both the construct of resilience and the Adult Learning Theory on the different learner generations (Generation X, Millennials, and Generation Z). A final research recommendation would be to examine a separate population of Army National Guard soldiers, particularly those not administratively flagged. These recommended expansions of this study would help further fill the identified research gaps in contemporary literature and extend the validity externally to a wider military group.

The limitations of this study included a sample from only one of the 54 states and territories of the United States that has an Army National Guard, the lack of a control group, no long-term follow-up on outcomes, and minimal female representation in the third and fourth age brackets. Additionally, the current study examined only 17.4% of the population of Army National Guard soldiers that had attended the resilience-based Wellness Camp intervention;

however, the entire National Guard is much larger. This adds concerns for external validity for the findings beyond a population of soldiers that are administratively flagged within the Army National Guard of the hosting state. If future research examined multiple intervention groups and larger samples sizes, then the concern for external validity could be decreased.

Five of the seven research questions (RQs: 1, 4, 5, 6, and 7) relied upon soldier self-reported outcomes of their perceptions on quantitative surveys. Soldiers could potentially over-rate themselves at pre-intervention which could skew outcomes for those research questions in comparison to post-intervention reporting. It could be feasible to decrease this concern in future studies if researchers used qualitative measures and/or behavioral analysis to establish pre- and post-intervention outcomes.

Summary

The purpose of this study was to test for a potential relationship between the two-week resilience-based Wellness Camp intervention and the pre-intervention and post-intervention performance and perception measures. This study sought to examine a population that would help to fill gaps in contemporary literature surrounding the effects of resiliency on military service members. This quantitative, quasi-experimental, ex post facto, survey-based study added insights toward the effects of increased frequencies of resilience training (beyond the Army's doctrinal requirements) effects on soldier perception of resilience, performance in fitness testing and body composition screening, and perception of application of resilience strategies such as goal setting, energy management, imagery, and emotion control. This study's results showed that a statistically significant relationship existed between pre- and post-intervention measures of perception of resilience, APFT performance, ABCP screening outcomes, and perception of application of all four strategies evaluated. The quantitative data supports the effectiveness of the

two-week resilience-based Wellness Camp intervention in promoting healthy behaviors, motivation, and their application to performance for traditional M-Day (non-full time) Army National Guard soldiers. The medium and large effect sizes found for this sample added value to the outcome for the National Guard's fiscal and readiness to deploy areas of concern. In summary, traditional M-Day (non-full time) Army National Guard soldiers that were administratively flagged for failure to meet Army standards in fitness and/or body composition demonstrated beneficence from the increased rate of resilience training in the areas of physical performance, resilience perception, and resilience strategy application.

While not all soldiers experienced success in the intervention, a statistically significant relationship was discovered along with notable success rates (74% in one iteration) on post-intervention performance testing resulting in the lifting of numerous administrative flags and a cost avoidance of ~\$56,700,000.00 over the five years of one state's Army National Guard's implementation of the intervention (Eads, 2018; HQFLARNG, 2018; HQFLARNG, 2020). These results, this study's outcomes, and the expansion of the contemporary literature based on the recommended future research could assist the Army in enhancing its operational and deployable readiness for the reserve components (Army Reserves and Army National Guard)

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Appendices

Appendix A: Brief Resilience Scale

THE OHIO STATE UNIVERSITY

Brief Resilience Scale (BRS)

Please respond to each item by marking <u>one box per row</u>		Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
BRS 1	I tend to bounce back quickly after hard times	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5
BRS 2	I have a hard time making it through stressful events.	<input type="checkbox"/> 5	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 1
BRS 3	It does not take me long to recover from a stressful event.	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5
BRS 4	It is hard for me to snap back when something bad happens.	<input type="checkbox"/> 5	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 1
BRS 5	I usually come through difficult times with little trouble.	<input type="checkbox"/> 1	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 5
BRS 6	I tend to take a long time to get over set-backs in my life.	<input type="checkbox"/> 5	<input type="checkbox"/> 4	<input type="checkbox"/> 3	<input type="checkbox"/> 2	<input type="checkbox"/> 1

Scoring: Add the responses varying from 1-5 for all six items giving a range from 6-30. Divide the total sum by the total number of questions answered.

My score: _____ item average / 6

Smith, B. W., Dalen, J., Wiggins, K., Tooley, E., Christopher, P., & Bernard, J. (2008). The brief resilience scale: assessing the ability to bounce back. *International journal of behavioral medicine*, 15(3), 194-200.

Appendix B: Test of Performance Strategies (TOPS) Survey

Last 4 #s of SSN: _____

QUESTIONNAIRE

Directions: Each item describes a specific situation that you may have encountered. Please read each statement and circle the appropriate number that best fits you.

(1=NEVER, 2=RARELY, 3=SOMETIMES, 4=OFTEN, 5=ALWAYS)

		<i>Never</i>	<i>Rarely</i>	<i>Sometimes</i>	<i>Often</i>	<i>Always</i>
1.	I rehearse my performance in my mind before starting the APFT.	1	2	3	4	5
2.	I always set specific goals for the APFT.	1	2	3	4	5
3.	My emotions prevent me from performing my best during the APFT.	1	2	3	4	5
4.	I like doing things that I'll learn from even if I make a lot of errors.	1	2	3	4	5
5.	I can increase my energy to get in the zone for the APFT.	1	2	3	4	5
6.	I am aware of what I say to myself before, during, and after the APFT.	1	2	3	4	5
7.	My attention wanders while I am training or performing.	1	2	3	4	5
8.	When the pressure is on, I have strategies to relax.	1	2	3	4	5
9.	During the APFT, I don't think about my performance I just let it happen.	1	2	3	4	5
10.	I can visualize each component of the APFT going exactly how I want.	1	2	3	4	5
11.	During the APFT I have thoughts of failing.	1	2	3	4	5
12.	When something is hard, it makes me want to spend more time on it, not less.	1	2	3	4	5
13.	After performing, I evaluate if I achieved my goals for the APFT.	1	2	3	4	5
14.	My APFT performance suffers if I get upset by something.	1	2	3	4	5
15.	I use specific cue words/statements to help my APFT performance.	1	2	3	4	5
16.	When getting ready for the APFT, I psych myself up.	1	2	3	4	5
17.	My nerves get in the way of performing my best during the APFT.	1	2	3	4	5
18.	My thoughts during the APFT are productive for my performance.	1	2	3	4	5
19.	I have a routine set up for myself so I feel prepared for the APFT.	1	2	3	4	5
20.	I am able to motivate myself when training for or taking the APFT.	1	2	3	4	5

Thomas, P. R., Murphy, S., and Hardy, L. (1999). Test of Performance Strategies: Development and Preliminary Validation of a Comprehensive Measure of Athlete's Psychological Skills. *Journal of Sports Sciences*, 697-711.

Appendix C: Institutional Review Board Exempt Protocol Approval

UNIVERSITY OF ST. AUGUSTINE

FOR HEALTH SCIENCES

To: Dr. Lori Kupczynski– Principal Investigator

From: Elizabeth Ardolino, PT, MPT, PhD

Date: July 18, 2020 – Exempt Review

Re: IRB EXEMPT Protocol Application

Your IRB application submitted entitled, *"A QUANTITATIVE ANALYSIS OF RESILIENCE TRAINING'S INFLUENCE ON ARMY NATIONAL GUARDSMEN RESILIENCE AND PERFORMANCE"*, Protocol # EDD-0714-269, falls under the Exempt Review category as listed in 45 CFR §46.

- This application was reviewed as exempt as written on July 18, 2020.
 - Exempt Category 45 CFR §46.104
- The protocol number is EDD-0714-269.

Please note that any changes to the exempt protocol must be re-reviewed by the IRB committee. Upon completion of the study please notify the IRB so we can update the study file and provide any results you may have from completing the study.

As Chair of the Texas IRB, I have reviewed this protocol and determined that it qualifies as exempt per 45 CFR §46.104.

Elizabeth Ardolino
 University IRB Chair
 Office: (737) 202-3343
 Email: eardolino@usa.edu

PLEASE NOTE: It is the responsibility of the primary researcher to amend their IRB protocol to add any future individuals who will be handling research data before they join the study. These individuals must be added to the protocol via an approved protocol amendment and must complete the required CITI online course before they may handle research data or interact with human research subjects. If new individuals are not added to the protocol and trained PRIOR TO ANY HUMAN SUBJECTS CONTACT, the IRB may revoke the primary researcher's approval to conduct the research project.

*Note: Please keep a copy of this Approval with your protocol documents and retain per the USAHS records retention schedule.

A copy of all approvals must be kept in the Research Facility or office to be viewed during inspections.

Appendix D: Military Memorandum of Understanding (MOU) to Use Data

DEPARTMENTS OF THE ARMY AND THE AIR FORCE

MED-DSS

27 MAY 2020

MEMORANDUM OF UNDERSTANDING
 BETWEEN
 G3 TRAINING DIVISION
 AND
 CW2 JEREMY HOWARD (DOCTORAL CANDIDATE UNIVERSITY OF SAINT
 AUGUSTINE FOR HEALTH SCIENCES)

SUBJECT: Memorandum of Understanding between the G3 Training Division and CW2 Jeremy Howard of the OTSS-Ready & Resilient Program for the Use of APFT/ABCP Data from DTMS for Doctoral Dissertation Research with the University of Saint Augustine for Health Sciences to be Awarded an Educational Doctoral Degree

1. BACKGROUND: CW2 Jeremy Howard is a Doctoral Candidate at the University of Saint Augustine and has requested the permission to use Army Physical Fitness Test (APFT), Army Combat Fitness Test (ACFT), and Army Body Composition Program (ABCP) screening data as reported in the Digital Training Management System (DTMS) for Soldiers that had attended the Wellness Camp Initiative in order to conduct an Ex Post Facto Quasi-Experimental Study on the effects of the Master Resilience Training curriculum on Soldier Self-Efficacy through perception and application of resilience skills in order to earn an Educational Doctorate.

2. PURPOSE: This Memorandum of Understanding (MOU) between the G3 Training and CW2 Jeremy Howard is to establish an agreement allowing permission to use the Soldier specific APFT, ACFT, and ABCP data for the dissertation process. The permission to use this data will be granted provided:

- a. All data used for the study is to be de-identified from the Soldier that attended the intervention.
- b. All data used for the study will be de-identified from the Soldiers' units of assignment.
- c. All data used for the study will be de-identified from the National Guard State of Origin.
- d. Data for the study will only be taken for Soldiers that attended the Wellness Camp intervention during FY19 (n=89 Soldiers).

██████████ MED-DSS

SUBJECT: Memorandum of Understanding between the ██████████ G3 Training and CW2 Jeremy Howard of the OTSS-Ready & Resilient Program for the Use of APFT/ABCP Data from DTMS for Doctoral Dissertation Research with the University of Saint Augustine for Health Sciences to be Awarded an Educational Doctoral Degree

3. POINTS OF CONTACT: Parties involved will communicate the implementation of this MOU through the points of contact listed below.

- a. ██████████ G3 State Training Officer: LTC ██████████ and ██████████
- b. Doctoral Candidate: CW2 Jeremy Howard: (██████████) and ██████████

4. GENERAL PROVISIONS:

- a. MODIFICATION OF THE MOU: This MOU may only be modified by written agreement of the parties.
- b. ENTIRE UNDERSTANDING: Signature of the MOU represents express understanding and agreed upon actions of the parties involved as written in the MOU's subject matter.
- c. EFFECTIVE DATE: This MOU takes effect beginning on the day after the last party signs.
- d. EXPIRATION DATE: This MOU expires upon formal award of the Educational Doctorate to CW2 Jeremy Howard and Dissertation Research Data Publication.

APPROVED:

FOR THE ██████████ G3 TRAINING OFFICE: FOR DOCTORAL CANDIDATE:

██████████

 LTC, AD, ██████████
 State Training Officer
 27 May 2020

 (Date)

 Digitally signed by
 JEREMY D. HOWARD
 DN: cn=JEREMY D. HOWARD,
 o=US ARMY, ou=US ARMY,
 email=j.howard@army.mil
 Date: 2020.05.27 13:27:08
 +0000

 JEREMY D. HOWARD
 CW2, AD, FLARNG
 Doctoral Candidate
 27 May 2020

 (Date)